

A Survey Module of Unpaid Labour: Measuring Unpaid Labour within Paid Jobs¹

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Abstract

This paper outlines the methodology and process behind the quantitative data collection primarily focused on the development of a survey module on unpaid labour within paid jobs. This module was created as part of the ERC Advanced Grant ResPecTMe, led by Principal Investigator Valeria Pulignano. The survey builds upon an extensive qualitative study, which involved work-life narrative biographies and working diaries from several European countries. The survey module quantifies this precarity in the form of unpaid labour by measuring the time and material resources that individuals invest in tasks that, while part of their job responsibilities, often go unpaid and/or underpaid. Its primary utility lies in disentangling these various forms and aspects of unpaid labour. To identify the predictors and consequences of unpaid labour as well as its relationship with other working conditions, the survey also includes various socio-demographic characteristics and working conditions questions that have been tested and used in international surveys such as European Working conditions Survey and European Social Survey. The paper provides a detailed account of how the survey module was developed and implemented across four European countries - the UK, France, Sweden, and the Netherlands - through nationally representative panel surveys, such as LORE (Sweden), ELIPSS (France), and LISS (the Netherlands), following a pilot conducted in the UK through Kantar. It also covers the survey's design, data collection process, and the specific items and codes used in each country to ensure transparency and to be used as a guide for researchers who wish to use this data.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The emergence of new non-standard work arrangements and increased labour precariousness has challenged the traditional sociological dichotomy between paid (productive or waged) and unpaid (reproductive or unwaged) work. People spend more time working for their paid job without getting paid for (either as they are part of their job description or in order to get into a paid job) – namely, unpaid labour within paid jobs (Pulignano et al., 2024²). For example, the task-based work arrangements that are prevalent in gig-economy, where workers are not paid by hours but by tasks, blurs which part of their job is paid and unpaid (e.g., Moore and Newsome 2018³). The jobs that are not directly paid for but are part of the job, such as the courier workers' waiting time, remain on such a blurred zone between paid and unpaid work. At the same time, under welfare and labour market reforms in the last few decades, workers are increasingly becoming precarious (Kalleberg and Vallas, 2018⁴; Bosch, 2004⁵). While there is growing diversity in the kinds of contracts covering paid work (Rubery and Grimshaw, 2016⁶), paid work is also becoming less secure (Vosko, 2011⁷). People can be dismissed through restructuring or company closure, without the job necessarily being contractually 'temporary' (Weil, 2014⁸) and the quality of paid jobs with an indeterminate duration is deteriorating (Lewchuk, 2017⁹; Pulignano and Doerflinger, 2013¹⁰). The increased precariousness pushes workers to undertake more unpaid work activities to respond to employer's demands (e.g. long hours, additional tasks) and/or to advance their careers in a competitive labour market (e.g. internships, working extra hours) (Crain et al. 2016; Rubery et al. 2018; Weil 2014).

The blurred boundary between the paid and unpaid labour, especially with regards to unpaid labour within paid jobs, demonstrates the complexity of precariousness that exists in contemporary post-industrialised labour market. However, this complexity remains underexplored (Pulignano and

² Pulignano, V., Grimshaw, D., Domecka, M., & Vermeerbergen, L. (2024). Why does unpaid labour vary among digital labour platforms? Exploring socio-technical platform regimes of worker autonomy. *Human Relations*, 77(9), 1243-1271.

³ Moore, S., & Newsome, K. (2018). Paying for free delivery: dependent self-employment as a measure of precarity in parcel delivery. *Work, Employment and Society*, 32(3), 475-492.

⁴ Kalleberg, A. L., & Vallas, S. P. (Eds.). (2018). Probing precarious work: Theory, research, and politics. In *Precarious work* (pp. 1-30). Emerald Publishing Limited.

⁵ Bosch, G. (2004). Towards a new standard employment relationship in Western Europe. *British journal of industrial relations*, 42(4), 617-636.

⁶ Rubery, J. and Grimshaw, D. (2016) 'Precarious work and the commodification of the employment relationship: the case of zero hours in the UK and mini jobs in Germany', in G. Bäcker, S. Lehndorff and C. Weinkopf (eds.) *Den Arbeitsmarkt verstehen, um ihn zu gestalten: Festschrift für Gerhard Bosch*. Springer.

⁷ Vosko, L. F. (2011). *Managing the margins: Gender, citizenship, and the international regulation of precarious employment*. OUP Oxford.

⁸ Weil, D. (2014). Fissured employment: Implications for achieving decent work. *Creative Labour Regulation: Indeterminacy and Protection in an Uncertain World*, 35-62.

⁹ Lewchuk, W. (2017). Precarious jobs: Where are they, and how do they affect well-being?. *The Economic and Labour Relations Review*, 28(3), 402-419.

¹⁰ Pulignano, V., & Doerflinger, N. (2013). A head with two tales: trade unions' influence on temporary agency work in Belgian and German workplaces. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 24(22), 4149-4165.

Domencka, 2025¹¹; Seo et al., 2024¹²). While some studies have qualitatively explored this phenomenon (e.g., Cole et al 2022¹³; Moore and Newsome, 2018³), the lack of quantitative measurement has limited our knowledge in terms of its prevalence, applicability to wider working population, and its characteristics, such as who are more likely to engage in unpaid labour and what the consequences are (Pulignano and Domecka, 2025).

Against this background, the ERC project ResPecTMe has investigated the precariousness at the paid-unpaid continuum, through conducting a comparative European in-depth study on how precariousness is classified and experienced through affected people's subjective accounts of their work activities, across and within different societal contexts. It uses a mixed-method exploratory sequential approach, consisting of qualitative and quantitative methods, to understand this phenomenon of unpaid labour within paid jobs (see Seo et al Forthcoming¹¹ about the methodology).

This paper is on the survey questionnaire developed as part of the quantitative study within ResPecTMe. In the following chapter of this report, we first describe the design of the key novel questions developed to identify different types of unpaid labour and potential mechanisms behind it with regards to stigma, drawing from the findings from the qualitative study conducted in ResPecTMe. This is followed by the data collection procedure and ethical considerations for the four surveys conducted in four European countries (UK, France, Sweden, and The Netherlands). The next chapter provides description of all questions: how they are constructed, the rationale behind the differences in question construction across countries, and how they are coded in each dataset. Finally, this report includes all full versions of the questionnaires in the appendix.

1.2 The ResPecTMe quantitative study

The ResPecTMe quantitative study develops a measurement for the novel theory of precariousness at the continuum between paid and unpaid labour. Essentially, the study was designed to quantify the concept of unpaid labour in paid employment through a survey module in order to assess the extent to which unpaid labour could be considered a valid dimension for precariousness.

The measurement of unpaid labour is based on concepts stemming from a qualitative study in eight European countries (Belgium, the Netherlands, Sweden, Poland, Germany, Italy, France, United Kingdom) in three work areas (care work, creative work, platform work) within the ResPecTMe project (grant agreement n° 833577: PI Valeria Pulignano). The qualitative study brought to light different forms of unpaid labour (i.e. unpaid labour time, material assets – see below) and different mechanisms driving unpaid labour (e.g., punishment, reward – see below) that were operationalized in survey-items in the quantitative survey module. The development of survey-items involved to first consult available international surveys, such as the European Working Conditions' Survey (EWCS), the Labour Force survey (LFS) and the European Social Survey (ESS), in search of existing items that could be used to measure our concepts. Where possible, existing and already validated items were used within the ResPecTMe survey module, sometimes after small adaptations were made to the question wording

¹¹ Pulignano V. and Domecka M. (2025) *The Politics of Unpaid Labour. How can Unpaid Labour Help Address Inequality in Precarious Work*, Oxford: OUP.

¹² Seo, H., Pulignano, V., Meuleman, B., and Domecka, M. (2024) "Researching Unpaid Labour in Paid Employment: A Mixed-Method Exploratory Sequential Approach" Book Chapter in *Field Guide to Researching Employment Relations*, edited by Jane Parker, Noelle Donnelly, Susan Ressa and Mihajla Gavin. Edward Elgar Publishing.

¹³ Cole, M., Stuart, M., Hardy, K., & Spencer, D. (2024). Wage theft and the struggle over the working day in hospitality work: a typology of unpaid labour time. *Work, Employment and Society*, 38(1), 103-121.

and/or answer categories. We also consulted with the International Labour Organisation (ILO) and Eurofound to receive feedback and improve the survey module. A pilot survey was developed and conducted in the UK to validate and test the survey instrument. Subsequently, the survey module was revised and improved, leading to a final standard questionnaire (SQ) that was implemented in Sweden, France and the Netherlands, after translation and some adjustments based on national contexts based on consulting with the experts in the national probability panels. By quantifying the qualitative concept of unpaid labour within paid employment through a survey module, this study contributes to knowledge on work at the boundaries between paid and unpaid work in both the public and private sphere of work and life of individuals. In particular, the module allows to examine who is more likely to be exposed to different forms of unpaid labour and their implications for people’s work and life experiences.

2. Survey Design and Data Collection

2.1 Description of the survey design

The survey module offers a measure of unpaid labour within paid work (hereafter unpaid labour). Two conceptualisations of unpaid labour are introduced: unpaid labour as *time* and unpaid labour in terms of material assets. Unpaid labour as *time* refers to any time that is put into work that is not paid. Key examples emerging from the qualitative research conducted within the scope of ResPecTMe include waiting time between tasks, preparation time for the main tasks, communication time, administrative time, travel time between tasks, maintenance time for equipment used and networking time to continue with the job or get future jobs. Unpaid labour in terms of material assets refers to assets that are not provided or compensated by the employer/contractor that is necessary for the job, resulting in costs for the worker. Some examples include expenses for buying or maintaining equipment/tools, traveling costs, expenses for appearance, work-related communication and working spaces.

In our survey, we quantify and measure unpaid labour time by asking whether the respondents have engaged in certain tasks (e.g., waiting, traveling, administrative, etc.), how frequently they engage in these tasks and to what extent those tasks are paid by the employer/contractor. In addition, we also ask about the unpaid overtime work. For the material assets approach, we ask whether the respondents use certain equipment/tools for their job (e.g., mode of transportation, tools related to safety, appearance, and communication, etc.) and to what extent the expenses are covered by their employers/contractors. If the tasks/equipment are unpaid, even partially, we consider them as unpaid labour. Table 1 lists the different tasks and equipment/tool that were included in the survey. We use these as indicators to derive latent variable of unpaid labour to identify the different types of unpaid labour.

Table 1. Operationalisation of unpaid labour in terms of time and material assets

Unpaid in terms of time	Unpaid in terms of material assets
A. Waiting between tasks/clients	A. Transportation means used during the working hours (e.g., car, bike, truck, etc.) excluding commuting between home and work
B. Communication with clients/employers (e.g., negotiating, email exchanges, meetings)	B. Safety equipment (e.g., personal protective equipment (PPE), gloves, etc.)
C. Administrative/paper work (e.g., dealing with HR, physical paper work, writing reports)	C. Specific clothing or accessories (including uniform)
D. Traveling between jobs and tasks (excluding commuting time between home and work)	D. Computer (e.g., PC, laptop, tablet, and other connected device)
E. Maintaining work equipment or tools	

<p>F. Networking (e.g., any efforts made to get more clients/orders/business in the current job or maintain them over time, such as contacting or meeting people, attending events)</p> <p>G. Preparing for the main task agreed by contract (e.g., getting ready or practicing or gathering materials for the main tasks, drawing up schedule or plan of the day)</p> <p>H. Training for the main job (including workshops, conference)</p> <p>Have you ever done overtime work in the past months? If so, how frequently do you do it? *overtime is the working hours that are done in addition to normal (contractual) working hours during a day or a week (ILO definition)</p> <p>Do you get paid or compensations for your overtime work?</p>	<p>E. Phone</p> <p>F. Internet</p> <p>G. Gifts/rewards for clients (including business dinners)</p> <p>H. Working space</p>
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Another set of questions that are related to unpaid labour is aimed at examining the reasons for doing unpaid work (cf. table 2).

First, we approach it by explicitly asking why people do unpaid work in three aspects drawn from the qualitative research, which are inevitability, reward and penalty. First, people may engage in unpaid labour due to the inevitability of it within their jobs. It may be that unpaid labour is inherent in the job or there is no one to replace them if they do not do additional labour that ends up being unpaid. Second, people may engage in unpaid labour with the prospect of rewards afterwards, such as career advancement, being seen favourably by co-workers/clients, or even thinking that it is more altruistic or caring to do such a labour. Third, people may engage in unpaid labour to avoid certain penalty, such as negative consequence on their career, seen negatively by their colleagues or feeling guilty.

Table 2. Operationalisation of reasons for doing unpaid labour

<p>To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?</p> <p>A. Unpaid work is part of my job</p> <p>B. I do unpaid work, because there is no one to replace me</p> <p>C. I do unpaid work with because it might help my career (e.g., promotion, increase in wage, bonus, finding a better job, etc.)</p> <p>D. I do unpaid work because it is seen good by colleagues/clients/employers</p> <p>E. I do unpaid work out of care or kindness</p> <p>F. If I don't do unpaid work, I feel guilty</p> <p>G. Not doing unpaid work is seen badly by colleagues/clients/employers</p> <p>H. If I don't do unpaid work, it might harm on my career (e.g., promotion, finding better job in the future, wage, losing clients)</p>

Second, while the above questions are asked on the basis that the workers 'choose' to do unpaid labour (especially for the latter two aspects), we acknowledge that such choices are often 'constrained' as they are driven by certain structure or culture within workplace or profession. It is closely related

to the ideal worker norm (Acker, 1990¹⁴ ; Bailyn, 2006¹⁵; Reid, 2015¹⁶; Williams et al., 2013¹⁷) defined as the norm that rewards or considers an ‘ideal’ when worker is showing full commitment to work which can be demonstrated in terms of working long hours or being always available for work even when unpaid, or otherwise they are stigmatized as not hard working. Unpaid labour within paid jobs can therefore be driven by such ideal worker norm, where workers are pushed to undertake unpaid labour in order to not be stigmatized and penalized (Pulignano and Domecka, 2025)¹⁸. Thus, we have created a job stigma index based on the existing scale on stigma for those with (mental) health issues (e.g., Angermeyer et al., 2004¹⁹; Berger et al., 2001²⁰; King et al 2007²¹; Reavley and Jorm 2011²²) to test the hypothesis as to how stigma is related to unpaid labour. As shown in table 2, the index measures the extent to which workers feel their job is useful, recognized and appreciated in society and in the labour market, whether others think less of or discriminate against people doing their job and whether they think that people doing their jobs feel they are not as good as others.

Table 3. Operationalisation of job stigma

<p>A. My job gives me the feeling of work well done B. I have the feeling of doing useful work C. I feel like my job is being recognized D. I feel appreciated in the society because of my job E. Considering all my efforts and achievements in my job, I feel I get paid appropriately F. My job offers good prospects for career advancement G. I might lose my job in the next 6 months H. If I were to lose or quit my current job, it would be easy for me to find a job of similar salary</p>	<p>A. Other people think less of people in a similar job to mine B. People who work in a similar job to mine feel we’re not as good as others C. Other people discriminate against me because of my job</p>
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¹⁴ Acker, Joan. 1990. “Hierarchies, Jobs, Bodies: A Theory of Gendered Organizations.” *Gender & Society* 4(2): 139–158.

¹⁵ Bailyn, L. (2006). *Breaking the mold: Redesigning work for productive and satisfying lives*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press.

¹⁶ Reid, E. (2015). Embracing, passing, revealing, and the ideal worker image: How people navigate expected and experienced professional identities. *Organization science*, 26(4), 997-1017.

¹⁷ Williams, J. C., Blair-Loy, M., & Berdahl, J. L. (2013). Cultural schemas, social class, and the flexibility stigma. *Journal of social issues*, 69(2), 209-234.

¹⁸ Pulignano, V. and Domecka, M. (2025). *The Politics of Unpaid Labour: How the study of unpaid labour can help address inequality in precarious work*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

¹⁹ Angermeyer, M. C., Beck, M., Dietrich, S., & Holzinger, A. (2004). The stigma of mental illness: patients’ anticipations and experiences. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 50(2), 153-162.

²⁰ Berger, B. E., Ferrans, C. E., & Lashley, F. R. (2001). Measuring stigma in people with HIV: Psychometric assessment of the HIV stigma scale. *Research in nursing & health*, 24(6), 518-529.

²¹ King, M., Dinos, S., Shaw, J., Watson, R., Stevens, S., Passetti, F., ... & Serfaty, M. (2007). The Stigma Scale: development of a standardised measure of the stigma of mental illness. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 190(3), 248-254.

²² Reavley, N. J., & Jorm, A. F. (2011). Stigmatizing attitudes towards people with mental disorders: findings from an Australian National Survey of Mental Health Literacy and Stigma. *Australian & New Zealand Journal of Psychiatry*, 45(12), 1086-1093.

Other questions in the survey are included to examine the predictors or consequences of the different types of unpaid labour. Figure 1 below outlines the initial hypotheses that guided the questionnaire (i.e. survey module of unpaid labour) design. The survey includes questions on socio-demographic characteristics such as gender, age, education level, and migration status, as well as job-related factors like employment contract type, income level, firm size, sector, occupation, and working hours. Additionally, family characteristics, including marital status, household income, parental status, and the age of children, are covered. Various indices from well-established international surveys - such as the ESS, the EWCS, and the LFS - have been incorporated. These indices capture elements such as feelings about work, emotional labor, work-related stress, control over work, work regularity, flexible working arrangements, work-life balance, and health and safety. Furthermore, specific questions were developed to assess perceptions of social protection, including whether workers believe they could make ends meet in the event of illness, unemployment, or childbirth.

Figure 1. Unpaid labour, predictors and consequences

2.2 Data collection and Sample composition for each country

2.2.1 The United Kingdom

The UK survey was conducted online between 3 and 22 August 2022. It was a pilot survey conducted through the existing panels in the commercial company “Kantar”. Kantar’s panels consist of individuals who meet certain eligibility requirements, they register as members of the ‘Lifepoints’ research panel and are invited to participate in various market-research related activities. Participation in research earns panelists a certain number of ‘points’ that they can use to purchase giftcards or PayPal credit. Respondents are recruited through various sources (to reduce recruitment bias) and voluntarily chose to be part of the survey. For the ResPecTMe survey, respondents were recruited from the adult working population stratified by even proportion of age groups. In total, 2500 individuals participated in the survey. As Kantar’s privacy policy treats the response rate as confidential information, sharing this information for our survey was not possible. Table 4 provides an overview of some socio-demographic and job-related characteristics of the respondents who participated the survey.

Table 4. Sample composition in the UK: socio-demographic and job-related characteristics (N=2500)

Variable	Categories	% (N)
Gender	Female	52,7% (1317)
	Male	46,9% (1172)
	Non-binary	0,4% (10)
Age	18-34	34,9% (873)
	35-49	31,9% (799)
	50+	33,1% (828)
Educational level	Lower secondary and below	5,5% (138)
	Upper secondary	54,0% (1351)
	Tertiary	40,4% (1011)
Employment status	Employee	84,0% (2100)
	Self-employed	14,2% (355)
	In family's business	1,3% (33)
	Working under government scheme	0,1% (3)
	Other	0,4% (9)
Contract	Contract of unlimited duration	65,9% (1648)
	Contract of limited duration	12,7% (318)
	Temporary employment agency contract	2,6% (66)
	An apprenticeship or other training scheme	0,5% (13)
	Zero hours contract (without agreed minimum working hours)	8,4% (209)
	On-call, on-demand jobs (with agreed minimum working hours)	3,6% (90)
	Other	6,2% (28)
Sector	Private sector	61,0% (1525)
	Public sector	32,3% (808)
	Joint private-public organization or company	2,6% (65)
	Not-for-profit sector or NGO	3,2% (81)
	Other	0,8% (21)

For more information on the Kantar panel, we refer the reader to the websites:

<https://www.kantar.com/uki/campaigns/pf/lifepoints> ; <https://www.lifepointspanel.com/en-us>

2.2.2 France

In France, the survey was conducted online through the national probability panel ELIPSS (Longitudinal Internet Studies for Social Sciences). The ELIPSS panel is implemented by Sciences Po's Center for Socio-Political Data, in partnership with the Survey Service of the National French Institute for Demographic Studies. The ResPecTMe data was collected between 12 October and 9 November 2023. Respondents consisted of all panel members of ELIPSS. ELIPSS is an internet panel representative of the French adult population (age 18 or older on January 2023, residence in mainland France), inviting respondents every month to participate in social scientific research on various topics. ELIPSS uses stratified random probability sampling to select respondents. For the ResPecTMe survey panel, reminders were sent to respondents who had not yet filled in the survey on respectively 27/10/2023, 03/11/2023, 08/11/2023. In total, 80.8% of the 2507 invited panelists participated in the survey,

leading to a total of 2023 respondents, 1114 of them are currently working²³. 1090 participated through their mobile phones and 933 through computer/ tablet. The dataset contains two sets of initial weights (corresponding to the first phase of correction of non-response of recruitment in 2020 and 2023), - and two weights specific to the survey (corresponding to the second phase of correction of non-response for 2020 and 2023 recruitment). Table 5 shows the socio-demographic and job-related characteristics of the subsample of currently working respondents. Information on the sector (public/private) is contained in the categories on employment status.

Table 5. Sample composition in France: socio-demographic and job-related characteristics (N=1114)

Variable	Categories	% (N)
Gender	Female	43,5% (485)
	Male	56,5% (629)
Age	18-25 years	11,8% (132)
	26-35 years	14,5% (162)
	36-45 years	25,4% (283)
	46-55 years	31,5% (351)
	56-65 years	15,2% (169)
	66-75 years	1,4% (16)
	76+ years	0,1% (1)
Educational level	No diploma	6,3% (70)
	Occupational / Professional studies certificate (CAP/ BEP)	9,5% (106)
	Secondary education	19,1% (213)
	Undergraduary degree (DEUG, BTS, DUT)	38,1% (424)
	University degree	26,9% (300)
Employment status	Self-employed	10,8% (120)
	Employee in the public sector	27,8% (310)
	Employee in the private sector	59,5% (663)
	Other	1,9% (21)
Contract ²⁴	Contract of limited duration	15,0% (167)
	Contract until completion of a task	0,9% (10)
	Contract of unlimited duration, until retirement	56,2% (626)
	Continuous contract until new order	15,6% (174)

For more information, we refer to the ELIPSS website: ELIPSS: <https://quanti.dime-shs.sciences-po.fr/en/>

2.2.3 Sweden

In Sweden, the survey was administered through the national probability panel LORE (Swedish Citizens Panel) at the SOM Institute, a university based research organization at the University of Gothenburg. The survey was conducted online between 9 November and 28 November 2023. The Swedish panel consists of approximately 75000 pre-recruited panelists who have agreed to participate in research surveys in earlier recruitment efforts. Panelists are contacted a few times every year to participate in

²³ Note that for France, the survey was not limited to working populations due to difficulty identifying their current work status without asking a filter question and to not exclude the panel members through filter question.

²⁴ The respondents could select multiple answers, therefore the total does not add up to 100%

studies on various topics. The ResPecTMe survey was conducted specifically to the working population of the panel, selecting only participants with full-time or part-time occupation, and using probability-based methods for recruitment, reflecting the characteristics of the Swedish working population. Two reminders to fill in the survey were sent on 15 November and 21 November 2023. A total number of 3137 people participated in the ResPecTMe survey, of which 2908 answered more than 80% of the applicable questions, 47 answered between 50-80% and 182 fewer than 50% of the questions. 1547 respondents refused to participate and 91 didn't complete the survey due to e-mail bounce backs or failed deliveries. Of the respondents who participated, 131 turned out not to be working and hence the survey ended for them, leading to a final sample size of 2978 respondents that will be used for analysis. The survey was completed online via computer (33%), mobile device (60%) and tablet (7%) and took on 13,57 minutes to answer on average. Table 6 displays socio-demographic and job-related characteristics of the Swedish sample.

Table 6. Sample composition in Sweden: socio-demographic and job-related characteristics (N=2978)

Variable	Categories	% (N)
Gender	Female	45,2% (1345)
	Male	54,8% (1633)
Age	Under 30 years	3,2% (95)
	30-39 years	18,9% (563)
	40-49 years	26,5% (788)
	50-59 years	33,8% (1008)
	60-69 years	17,6% (524)
Educational level	Lower secondary or below	1,1% (34)
	Upper secondary	17% (500)
	Post-secondary	10% (298)
	University education (Bachelor/ Master)	66,6% (1979)
	PhD	5,5% (162)
Employment status	Employee	89,3% (2659)
	Self-employed	10,5% (313)
	Employment in labour market policy/ undergoing training	0,2% (6)
Contract²⁵	Permanent employment	93,3% (2743)
	Fixed-term employment	2,9% (28)
	Project employment	1,4% (40)
	On-call employment	0,8% (24)
Sector	Private sector	53,9% (1599)
	Public sector	42,1% (1251)
	Not-for-profit sector	4% (119)

For more information on the panel, we refer the reader to the LORE website:
<https://www.gu.se/en/som-institute/the-swedish-citizen-panel>

2.2.4 The Netherlands

In the Netherlands, the survey was conducted online through the LISS panel. The data was collected between 6 May and 30 July 2024. The LISS panel is managed by Centerdata, an independent non-profit research institute at Tilburg University that collects data that is made available to researchers for

²⁵ The respondents could select multiple answers, therefore the total does not add up to 100%

scientific, policy and social research. To establish the LISS panel, a traditional random sample was drawn from the population registers in the Netherlands. For the ResPecTMe survey, the sample was limited to panel members that either perform paid work as an employee, work or participate in a family business or are self-employed (professional freelancers). A total of 3200 respondents were selected, of which 2044 (63,9%) filled in the survey and 2013 (62,9%) filled in the complete survey. The survey was sent out three times: once in the beginning of May (leading to 1643 responses), once in June (driving up the response to 1730), and once in July (leading to the final 2044 responses). These repeated attempts were due to the lower than expected number of responses in the first month. One potential explanation for this is that LISS launched several (longer) survey in the same period (May – June 2024) that the same respondents were invited to participate in. The average duration of the ResPecTMe survey was 13,67 minutes. Table 7 shows an overview of the socio-demographic and job-related characteristics of the final sample.

Table 7. Sample composition in the Netherlands: socio-demographic and job-related characteristics (N=2044)

Variable	Category	% (N)
Gender	Female	51,9% (1061)
	Male	48,0% (981)
Age	15 - 24 years	6,4% (130)
	25 - 34 years	19,6% (400)
	35 - 44 years	20,1% (411)
	45 - 54 years	20,6% (421)
	55 - 64 years	26,0% (532)
	65 years and older	7,3% (150)
Educational level	Primary education (<i>basisonderwijs</i>)	2,9% (59)
	Primary vocational education (<i>vmbo</i>)	9,5% (193)
	Secondary general education (<i>havo/vwo</i>)	8,6% (175)
	Secondary vocational education (<i>mbo</i>)	28,2% (575)
	Higher professional education (<i>hbo</i>)	31,2% (635)
	University education (<i>wo</i>)	19,6% (399)
Employment status	Employee	86,7% (1769)
	Self-employed	9,0% (184)
	In family's business	1,1% (23)
	Apprentice/ intern	1,0% (20)
	Other	2,2% (45)
Contract²⁶	Contract of unlimited duration	73,9% (1505)
	Contract of limited duration	13,2% (268)
	Contract until completion of a task	1,7% (35)
	Temporary employment agency contract	0,7% (17)
	On-call contract (e.g. zero hours contract)	2,8% (57)
	Other	1,3% (28)
Sector	Private sector	49,4% (1004)
	Public sector	22,0% (448)
	Joint private-public organization or company	6,6% (134)
	Not-for-profit sector or NGO	8,0% (163)
	Other	14,0% (285)

For more information on the LISS panel, we refer the reader to the website: <https://www.lissdata.nl/>

²⁶ The respondents could select multiple answers, therefore the total does not add up to 100%

2.3 Ethical considerations

This project was approved by the internal ethics review board of KU Leuven (SMEC) and below we describe in detail how the data is collected and managed in each panels/companies with regards to data protection.

2.3.1 The United Kingdom

In the UK, respondents give their consent when joining the panel. They are not asked for consent again for each survey, unless the survey collects personal or sensitive data. The 'LifePoints' privacy policy (<https://www.lifepointspanel.com/en-us/privacy#1>) provides an extensive overview of the kind of data collected and the storage and use of the data.

Data collected includes:

- IP address, operating system information, browser type
- Name, email address, postal address, mobile device ID, GMC Number (UK)
- Demographics and any detail the respondents share about themselves and their household

Kantar's data retention policy is 12 months for primary data (i.e., survey data), and 24 months for secondary data (i.e., questionnaire, script).

Personal data of the panelists is stored for as long as they are a member of the Panels. In the event that panelists unsubscribe, data is retained for no longer than 3 months, unless otherwise required by law. Appropriate technological and organisational measures are taken to protect personal data, both during transmission and once the panel receives it, adhering with local standards and laws.

Personal data may be shared with LifePoints third-party vendors and processors. Third-party data partners and publishers are all contractually bound to keep any information they collect and disclose, or that Kantar collects and discloses to them, confidential and must protect it with security standards and practices that are equivalent to the ones of Kantar.

Respondents have the right to change their mind and to withdraw their consent, the right to access, rectify or erase their personal data; the right to port their personal data (portability right); the right to restrict or object to the processing of their personal data; the right to opt out of the sale of their personal data (if Kantar sells their data) and the right to not be discriminated against for exercising any of the rights available to you under applicable data protection laws.

2.3.2 France

ELIPSS respondents must read and sign an informed consent form containing information on the research project and survey module as well as on the storage, use and protection of their data in line with GDPR before starting to fill in the survey. ELIPSS collects and processes the following kinds of data:

Country of birth / country of origin

- Gender
- Date of birth, age, etc.
- Personal life (lifestyle, family situation, etc.)
- School, academic and professional life
- Economic and financial information (income, financial situation, etc.)
- Political, philosophical, religious, union opinions, data relating to sexual life, ethnic origin
- Data relating to health or disability

- Data allowing us to assess the social difficulties of people, or to make a value judgment
- Infringement data (category of specific data subject to consent of the person concerned)

The informed consent lists the following data protection measures:

- Participation in this survey is optional
- None of the personal data collected by the research team can be published or made public in such a way that the participants can be identified
- An anonymization and pseudonymization protocol is implemented: This provides for pseudonymization from the design of the database of responses to the questionnaire and definitive anonymization within a maximum of 20 years
- Data access rights will be:
 - o limited and only accessible to the research team
 - o secured by a personal identifier and password
- The panelists' contact data and the responses to the questionnaires constitute two separate databases, by default, with distinct access authorizations
- Research data is encrypted from data collection and throughout the duration of the project, until its definitive anonymization

ELIPSS data hosting and storage policy involves that the ResPecTMe data is collected via the Qualtrics platform (Germany), then hosted by Sciences Po (France), then transmitted to the ResPecTMe research team at CeSO (Belgium) after pseudonymization. To implement the survey, the ELIPSS team exclusively accesses and uses the personal data necessary to contact respondents. The ResPecTMe research team does not have access to this data. All data collected by the ELIPSS team is secured in particular by data access management based on authentication and a strong password management policy.

For scientific research purposes, identifying data previously archived in the current database will be pseudonymized and kept in intermediate archiving. The retention period of pseudonymized data is planned for a period of twenty years. All technical and organizational measures necessary to protect the privacy of the persons concerned as best as possible have been taken within the meaning of Article 89 of the GDPR. Consequently, the regulations relating to the protection of personal data will be applicable to any new processing. The data may also be hosted in a European research data warehouse under these same conditions and may only be kept for later reuse for scientific research purposes only.

The data is stored anonymized and secure for scientific and historical purposes in the Sciences Po research data warehouse (France), i.e. the definite archive. The anonymized data will be deposited on the social sciences data archiving and dissemination portal [data.sciencespo](https://data.sciencespo.fr) (France) for the purpose of sharing with the scientific community.

Respondents' rights relating to the protection of personal data within the framework of the GDPR Regulations and the Data Protection Act are the right to information, access, erasure of data. The Sciences Po University ensures compliance with the data protection principles in force in Europe and France by its staff and any subcontractors. They also ensure the coordination of any request concerning its joint controller if concerned.

One of the aims of the ELIPSS panel, in addition to the production of data, is to make the data produced available to the scientific community, after they have been documented according to international standards. The data from the ResPectMe survey are now available on the site data.sciencespo.fr. It can be cited as: Seo, Hyojin; Pulignano, Valeria; Meuleman, Bart, 2024, "Exploration de la précarité dans le continuum travail rémunéré/non rémunéré (ELIPSS 2023)", doi: 10.21410/7E4/VMX38G

2.3.3 Sweden

Before starting the survey, all participants have to accept the terms and conditions, which constitutes their consent to be invited and participate in studies via the LORE citizen panel. By accepting the terms and conditions, respondents confirm that they have agreed to the conditions on data collection, use and storage for research purposes.

Lore processes the following personal data:

- Contact information: e-mail address, postal address and telephone number
- Information provided through survey responses, such as opinions, experiences, habits and more
- Data about the technical equipment used when answering the online surveys (e.g. the size of the screen, whether it is a mobile phone, a tablet or a larger computer/laptop, information about the operating system)

As described in the terms and conditions, respondents' personal data is processed in accordance with the European Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other supplementary legislation, as well as in accordance with the University of Gothenburg's rules for handling personal data. Respondents' answers and individual results will be processed so that unauthorized persons cannot access them.

Respondents' contact details are used to invite them to answer surveys and thereby participate in various research studies. The answers provided to the questionnaires are processed for research purposes. Answers from previous surveys may be combined with answers from later surveys to be able to follow how opinions change over time, as well as to streamline data collection by reducing the number of questions asked in each survey. All results are presented so that no participant can be identified. The survey answers are coded so that each respondent is assigned a serial number/ID number, so-called pseudonymisation. When the survey answers are downloaded from a survey, the e-mail addresses and other contact information that can identify respondents from the answers are removed immediately and replaced with this ID number for the further data processing. Employees at the SOM institute who work with the LORE Citizen Panel have access to the contact details to manage e-mails. This information is protected so that unauthorized persons cannot access it.

Respondents' personal data in the form of survey responses, but not their contact details, may be shared with other research groups at various Swedish universities, other countries within the EU, or in other countries outside the EU and EEA area (so-called third countries). Personal data can only be shared with researchers outside the EU area if it is a country that is judged by the European Commission to have an adequate level of data protection and thus meets the requirements for a corresponding protection of respondents' privacy as in Sweden.

2.3.4 The Netherlands

Before participating in the panel, respondents need to give their official informed consent for LISS to save their responses and to make these responses available for scientific, policy and social research, in compliance with GDPR. The LISS panel is managed by Centerdata, which collects the following personal data for the purpose of scientific research:

- Name and address details;
- E-mail address;
- Company name;

- (Mobile) phone number;
- IP-address;
- Login credentials;
- Any personal data respondents provide through the panel;
- Any personal data respondents provide by handing in a questionnaire

Researchers working for third parties (institutions other than Centerdata) are never given access to respondents' contact details without their prior explicit consent. It is not possible to trace the respondents' data back to them. Their privacy is remain fully protected as Centerdata always keeps respondents' contact details separately from their response. Centerdata does not store personal data longer than necessary to achieve the research purposes. Responses will not be used for commercial research and respondents may discontinue your participation at any time without having to give any reasons.

Respondents have the following rights with regard to data protection:

- Right of access: the right to see what kind of personal data is processed about them;
- Right of rectification: the right to rectify any personal data, if this information is (partially) wrong;
- Right to be forgotten: filing a request to delete any personal data processed about them;
- Right to object: the right to object against the processing of their personal data;
- Right to data portability: if technically feasible, respondents have the right to request Centerdata to transfer their processed personal data to a third party;
- Right to restriction: filing a request with us to (temporarily) restrict the processing of their personal data;
- The right to withdraw their consent

3. Questionnaires in each country

This section presents each survey question in each country. We first present the question in the Standard Questionnaire (SQ) that is drafted in English, and the actual wordings used for each national panel in the respective language. Note that the UK survey was a pilot survey for the SQ, so that it serves as the first survey that was revised to the SQ. For the questionnaires in French, Swedish and Dutch, they are the translations of the SQ with some adjustments based on national contexts after consulting with the experts in the national probability panels. Note that the order presented in this report is based on the SQ, and some surveys based on their own logics and regulations the order of the questionnaire were changed. Here, we also mention if the question is followed by another question when necessary. It is important to note that the length of the questionnaire varied due to different regulations and methods to measure of survey length in each panel. Some questions had to be deleted in some panels due to ethical issues and some questions due to the limited space in the survey. Key differences for specific questions are discussed with the questions below. Some question are derived from validated international surveys, such as the European Social Survey (ESS), European Working Conditions Survey (EWCS) and Labor Force Survey (LFS). To see the full questionnaire and the actual order of the questions for each country, please refer to the appendix.

Question 1 and 2 were used as filter questions as the main target of the questionnaire is the working population. We used the questions from the ESS (see UK questions), which were later revised after consulting with ILO (see SQ question Q1). Those who answered 1-3 for question 1 or answered yes to question 2 in the SQ, 1-2 for question 1 or yes to question 2 in the UK, 1 for question 1 and yes for question 2 in FR, 1-4 for question 1 in SE and 1-3 in the Netherlands are the primary target are defined

as working population. For the UK pilot survey, those who answered 3 and 5 are also included. For France, we could not drop the participants from the survey even if they're not currently working, so depending on the answers for question 1 and 2, they were categorised into three groups: Group A, Group B and Group C. Group A are those who answered 1 for question 1, Group B are those who did not answer 1 to question 1 but 1 for question 2, and Group C are those who did not answer 1 for question 1 and who answered 2 for question 2. Group A refers to those who are currently at paid work, Group B refers to those who have worked in a paid job in the past, and Group C refers to those who have not had a paid job. Questions that start with QA are for only for Group A, questions that start with QX are for both Group A and B but with different time tenses – namely, present tense for A and past tense for B, and questions that start with Q are for all three groups. For Sweden, we used the question that LORE panel already had for employment status, and those who answered 5-9 are filtered out from the survey (namely, survey ends for them). In the Netherlands, the LISS survey had already collected information on the respondents' employment status in a prior round, so we asked respondents to verify whether this information was still correct and to adapt if necessary, using the existing categories of the LISS survey (the 'p_belbezig' variable). Only those respondents who checked the categories 1-3 (potentially in combination with other categories) could continue the survey.

Q1	SQ	<p>To start with, we would like to ask you some questions about your current job(s).</p> <p>1. Which of these descriptions applies to what you have been doing for the last 7 days? <i>Select all that apply</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Working for someone else for pay (including when you' away temporarily for vacation, sickness or leave) 2. Working in own or family farming, animal rearing or fishing activities 3. Working in any other kind of business activity 4. Taking care of the household or family 5. Studying or training 6. Looking for work 7. Doing unpaid voluntary, community, village, charity work 8. Retired or pensioner 9. With a long-term illness, injury or disability 10. Other (write:)
	UK	<p>To start with, we would like to ask you some questions about your current job(s).</p> <p>1. Which of these descriptions applies to what you have been doing for the last 7 days? <i>Select all that apply</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. In paid work (or away temporarily, on leave or furlough) (employee, self-employed, working for your family business) 2. Paid internship 3. Unpaid internship 4. In education, (not paid for by employer) even if on vacation 5. Unemployed and actively looking for a job 6. Unemployed, wanting a job but not actively looking for a job 7. Permanently sick or disabled 8. Retired 9. In community or military service 10. Doing housework, looking after children or other persons 11. Other (write:)

FR	<p>Q01 Parmi ces situations, quelles sont celles qui s'appliquent à ce que vous avez fait au cours de ces 7 derniers jours ? (Plusieurs réponses possibles)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Travail rémunéré (salarié, à son compte, travail dans l'entreprise familiale) même si absence ou congés temporaires 2. Études ou en formation (non payée par l'employeur) même si vous êtes actuellement en vacances 3. Sans emploi et recherchant activement un emploi 4. Sans emploi et voulant trouver un emploi mais sans le chercher activement pour le moment 5. Malade ou handicapé(e) de manière permanente 6. Retraité(e) ou pré-retraité(e) 7. Au foyer, s'occupant des enfants ou d'une autre personne 8. Autre (préciser)
SE	<p>Q9 Vilken av de här grupperna beskriver bäst dig själv just nu?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Har heltidsanställning (även kortvarigt sjukskriven, föräldraledig) 2. Har deltidsanställning (även kortvarigt sjukskriven, föräldraledig) 3. Egen företagare 4. Har arbete i arbetsmarknadspolitiska åtgärder/genomgår arbetsmarknadsutbildning 5. Arbetslös 6. Pensionär 7. Har sjukersättning/aktivitetsersättning 8. Studerande 9. Annan grupp: <p><i>If NOT 1-4</i></p> <p>Q11 Den här studien riktar sig till de som främst identifierar sig som arbetande. Du angav på föregående fråga att 5-8 stämmer bäst in på dig. När du klickar dig vidare kommer enkäten därför att avslutas. Tack för din medverkan, och välkommen att delta i kommande undersökningar.</p>
NL	<p><i>p_belbezig</i></p> <p>In het onderstaande overzicht staat welke situatie of bezigheid op u van toepassing is volgens onze gegevens.</p> <p>Wilt u de gegevens controleren en zo nodig wijzigen?</p> <p>Kies alle opties die van toepassing zijn.</p> <p><i>Answer type: Checkboxes</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Verricht betaald werk in loondienst 2. Werkt of is meewerkend in gezins- of familiebedrijf 3. Is vrijeberoepsbeoefenaar, freelancer of zelfstandige 4. Zoekt werk na verlies werkring 5. Zoekt voor het eerst werk 6. Vrijgesteld van werkzoeken na verlies van werkring 7. Gaat naar school of studeert 8. Verzorgt de huishouding 9. Is met pensioen (vervroegd, AOW of VUT) 10. Is (gedeeltelijk) arbeidsongeschikt 11. Verricht onbetaald werk met behoud van uitkering 12. Verricht vrijwilligerswerk 13. Doet iets anders 14. Is te jong, heeft nog geen bezigheden

Q2	SQ	ASK Q2 ONLY IF Q1=4 OR Q1=5 OR Q1=6 OR Q1=7 OR Q1=8 OR Q1=9 OR Q1=10 2. Have you ever had a paid work? (including having your own business and paid internship) 1. Yes 1. No
	UK	ASK Q2 ONLY IF CODE 1 or 2 NOT SELECTED IN Q1 2. Did you do any paid work of an hour or more in the last 7 days? 1. Yes 2. No SCREENOUT IF CODE 2 SELECTED
	FR	Q02 Avez-vous déjà occupé un travail rémunéré, même il y a longtemps ? 1. Oui 2. Non
	SE	Deleted for LORE
	NL	Deleted for LISS

Note that for Q3, more specific questions about the respondents' second or third jobs have been deleted for the SQ after the pilot survey. Respondents with more than one job were asked to fill in the remainder of the survey about their main job – i.e. the one in which the respondent performed the most hours.

Q3	SQ	ASK Q3 IF Q1=1 OR Q1=2 OR Q1=3 3. In the last month did you work in more than 1 job? <i>(note that this does not apply to changing the job but doing several jobs at the same time – namely, multi-jobs)</i> 1. Yes 2. No <i>Info Screen</i> We are going to ask you some questions about the income generating activity in which you usually work the most hours, which is referred to as the 'main job' in this survey. <i>SHOW IF Q3=1</i> If you have two jobs that are exactly equal, please answer about the more highly paid of the two.
	UK	ASK Q3 ONLY IF Q1=1 OR Q1=2 OR Q2=1 3. In the last month did you work in more than 1 job? <i>(note that this does not apply to changing the job but doing several jobs at the same time – namely, multi-jobs)</i> 1. Yes 2. No <i>ASK ONLY IF Q3=1</i> 7. Other than your main job, how many jobs do you have? 1. 1 2. 2 3. 3

	<p>4. 4 5. 5 6. More than 5</p> <p><i>ASK ONLY IF Q3=1</i> 8. What is the title of your second job?</p> <p><i>ASK ONLY IF Q7=2 TO 6</i> 9. What is the title of your third job?</p> <p><i>INFO SCREEN – SHOW IF Q3=1</i> If you have more than one job, please answer about the one that takes up the most hours per week. If you have two jobs that are exactly equal, please answer about the more highly paid of the two. That job will be defined as the ‘main job’ for this survey.</p>
FR	<p><i>Si Groupe A</i> QA03 Au cours du dernier mois, avez-vous occupé plus d’un emploi ? <i>À noter que cela ne s’applique pas au changement d’emploi, mais à l’occupation de plusieurs emplois en même temps.</i></p> <p>1. Oui 2. Non</p> <p><i>Si QA03 = {2}</i> <i>TRANSITION</i> Nous allons vous poser quelques questions sur votre emploi principal, c’est-à-dire sur l’emploi rémunéré pour lequel vous réalisez le plus d’heures.</p> <p><i>Si QA03 <> {2}</i> <i>TRANSITION</i> Nous allons vous poser quelques questions sur votre emploi principal, c’est-à-dire sur l’emploi rémunéré pour lequel vous réalisez le plus d’heures. Si vous occupez plusieurs emplois parfaitement identiques, veuillez répondre en considérant l’emploi le mieux rémunéré.</p>
SE	<p>q13 Har du under den senaste månaden arbetat på mer än ett jobb? Observera att detta inte gäller vid byte av jobb utan när du har flera jobb/anställningar samtidigt.</p> <p>1. Ja 2. Nej</p> <p><i>Display This Question: If Har du under den senaste månaden arbetat på mer än ett jobb? Observera att detta inte gäller vid... = Ja</i></p> <p>q15 I den här enkäten ställs frågor om ditt arbete. Om du har fler än ett jobb ska du svara enbart utifrån ditt <i>huvudsakliga arbete</i>, vilket är där du arbetar flest timmar. Om du har flera arbeten med exakt samma timmar ska du svara utifrån det arbete där du får mest betalt.</p>
NL	<p>Q2 Hebt u de afgelopen maand 2 of meer banen gecombineerd? We bedoelen dat u tegelijkertijd meerdere banen had, niet dat u van baan veranderd bent.</p> <p><i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i> <i>Categories:</i></p>

		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nee 2. Ja <p><i>if (Q2 = 2)</i></p> <p>We stellen u nu een paar vragen over de baan waar u het meeste tijd aan besteedt. Dit noemen we in deze vragenlijst uw belangrijkste baan.</p> <p>Als u evenveel tijd besteedt aan twee banen, beantwoord de vragen dan over de baan waar u het meeste voor betaald krijgt.</p>
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Question 4 in the pilot survey was the combination of similar questions from EWCS, ESS and LFS, but was revised for the SQ after consulting with the International Labour organization (ILO). For France and for the Netherlands, there is an additional question that was not included for the other surveys. It's QA04BIS in France and 'JobSwitch' in the Netherlands and the English translation is "Have you changed job in the last twelve months?". This is because for those who have not changed their jobs, some of the data that the ELIPSS and LISS panel already had were used so that we can minimise the length for those who have already answered those questions for the annual survey. For Sweden, the question on the employment status is replaced with question 1, but additional question was asked about working for a family business or in an internship for the categories that are not included in question 1.

Q4	SQ	<p><i>ASK Q4 IF Q1=1 OR Q1=2 OR Q1=3 OR Q2=1</i></p> <p><i>For Q2=1, use past tense, e.g., "did you work" for questions that are related to their main job (Q4-27, Q29-30, Q35-42, Q51-54 (blue for ELIPSS Group B)</i></p> <p>4. Do you work...</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. As an employee 2. In your own business activity 3. Helping in a family or household business 4. As an apprentice, intern 5. Helping a family member who works for someone else 6. Other (write:)
	UK	<p><i>ASK ONLY IF Q1=1 OR Q1=2 OR Q2=1</i></p> <p>4. Are you working as an employee or are you self-employed? (or working for your own family's business)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Employee (paid a salary or wage by an employer) 2. Self-employed 3. Working for your own family's business 4. Working under government scheme 5. Other (write:)
	FR	<p><i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i></p> <p>QX04 Êtes-vous...</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. À votre compte (y compris gérant de société ou chef d'entreprise salarié) 2. Salarié(e) de la fonction publique (d'État, territoriale, hospitalière) 3. Salarié(e) d'un autre employeur (entreprise, association, de particulier, etc.) 4. Non rémunéré(e), mais vous travaillez avec un membre de votre famille 5. Autre (préciser) <p><i>Si Groupe A</i></p> <p>QA04BIS</p> <p>Avez-vous changé d'emploi au cours des douze derniers mois?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Oui 2. Non

SE	<p>q27 Stämmer något av följande in på din arbetssituation? Välj <i>allt som stämmer</i>.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Arbetar i ett familje-eller hushållsföretag 2. Arbetar som lärling/praktiserar 3. Arbetar med en familjemedlem som arbetar för någon annan 4. Inget av ovanstående
NL	<p><i>if (ISCO8 is response and sector is response)</i> <i>JobSwitch</i> Bent u in de afgelopen 12 maanden van baan veranderd? Als een andere functie hebt gekregen binnen dezelfde organisatie telt dit ook als verandering.</p> <p><i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i> <i>Categories:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nee 2. Ja

Questions 5 and 6 are used to identify the occupations of the respondents. The questions are derived from the EWCS. For Sweden, based on the experience from the panel, we have agreed that question 5 is sufficient. In the Netherlands, questions 5 and 6 were only asked to those respondents who had changed their job within the last 12 months, for respondents who hadn't changed their jobs the ISCO8 scores collected in the prior round of the LISS survey were used.

Q5	SQ	5. What is the title of your main paid job? By main paid job, we mean the one where you spend most hours.
	UK	<i>ASK ONLY IF Q1=1 OR Q1=2 OR Q2=1</i> 5. What is the title of your main paid job? By main paid job, we mean the one where you spend most hours.
	FR	<i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i> QX05 Quel est l'intitulé de votre emploi principal ? Merci d'être le plus précis possible. <i>[Champ texte]</i>
	SE	q33 Vilket är ditt huvudsakliga yrke? När du börjar skriva in ditt yrke kommer du få upp en lista med passande förslag. Välj det yrke i listan som ligger närmast dina arbetsuppgifter. Skriv annars vad du själv skulle kalla det.
	NL	<i>if ((ISCO8 is empty and sector is empty) or JobSwitch = 2)</i> Q4 Wat is de functietitel van uw [/ belangrijkste] baan? <i>Answer type: String</i>

Q6	SQ	6. What do you mainly do in your job?
	UK	<i>ASK ONLY IF Q1=1 OR Q1=2 OR Q2=1</i> 6. What do you mainly do in your job?
	FR	<i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i> QX06 Dans votre emploi principal, quel type de travail faites-vous habituellement ? Merci d'être le plus précis possible. <i>[Champ texte]</i>
	SE	Deleted for LORE

	NL	<i>if ((ISCO8 is empty and sector is empty) or JobSwitch = 2)</i> Q5 Wat zijn de belangrijkste taken van uw [/ belangrijkste]baan? <i>Answer type: Text</i>
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Questions 7 and 8 are specifically asked to the self-employed. These questions serve to identify the different types of self-employment, especially the dependent self-employed. Those who answer 6 to question 7 are recoded to the employee category.

Q7	SQ	<i>ASK ONLY IF Q4=2</i> 7. Looking at this card, please select the category or categories which apply to your main paid job? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sole director of own business 2. A partner in a business or professional practice 3. Working for yourself 4. Working as a sub-contractor 5. Doing freelance work 6. Paid a salary or a wage by an agency → <i>recode it to Q4=1</i> 7. Other (write:)
	UK	<i>ASK ONLY IF Q4=2</i> 10. Looking at this card, please select the category or categories which apply to your main paid job? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sole director of own business 2. A partner in a business or professional practice 3. Working for yourself 4. Working as a sub-contractor 5. Doing freelance work 6. Paid a salary or a wage by an agency 7. Other (write:)
	FR	<i>Si QX04 = {1}</i> QX07 Laquelle ou lesquelles de ces catégories décrit ou décrivent le mieux votre principal emploi rémunéré? <i>(Plusieurs réponses possibles)</i> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Unique dirigeant de sa propre entreprise 2. Associé au sein d'une entreprise ou d'un cabinet de profession libérale 3. À son compte 4. Sous-traitant 5. Free-lance 6. Salarié par une agence d'intérim 7. Autre (préciser)

SE	<p><i>Display This Question: If Vilken av de här grupperna beskriver bäst dig själv just nu? = Egen företagare</i></p> <p>q21 Välj den eller de kategorier som gäller för ditt arbete.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensam VD för eget företag 2. Partner i ett företag eller yrkesverksamhet 3. Arbetar för dig själv 4. Arbetar som underleverantör 5. Arbetar som frilans 6. Arbetar via ett bemanningsföretag 7. Annat, nämligen:
NL	<p><i>if (Q3 = 2)</i></p> <p>Q6 Als u denkt aan uw [/ belangrijkste] baan, welke van de onderstaande beschrijvingen zijn dan van toepassing?</p> <p><i>Answer type: Checkboxes</i></p> <p><i>Categories:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Enige directeur van uw eigen zaak 2. Partner in een zaak of professionele praktijk 3. Zelfstandige 4. Onderaannemer 5. Freelancer 6. Uitzendkracht voor een uitzendbureau 7. Anders namelijk:

Q8	<p>SQ</p> <p><i>ASK ONLY IF Q4=2</i></p> <p><i>SC PER ROW</i></p> <p>1. Regarding your business, do you</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="344 1234 1385 1525"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Yes</th> <th>No</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>A. Have the authority to hire or dismiss employees?</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>B. Get paid an agreed fee on a weekly or monthly basis?</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>C. Have employees (working for you)?</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>D. Generally, have more than one client or customer?</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Yes	No	A. Have the authority to hire or dismiss employees?	1	2	B. Get paid an agreed fee on a weekly or monthly basis?	1	2	C. Have employees (working for you)?	1	2	D. Generally, have more than one client or customer?	1	2
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UK	<p><i>ASK ONLY IF Q4=2</i></p> <p><i>SC PER ROW</i></p> <p>11. Regarding your business, do you</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="344 1637 1385 1924"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Yes</th> <th>No</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>E. Have the authority to hire or dismiss employees?</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>F. Get paid an agreed fee on a weekly or monthly basis?</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>G. Have employees (working for you)?</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>H. Generally, have more than one client or customer?</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Yes	No	E. Have the authority to hire or dismiss employees?	1	2	F. Get paid an agreed fee on a weekly or monthly basis?	1	2	G. Have employees (working for you)?	1	2	H. Generally, have more than one client or customer?	1	2
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FR	<p><i>Si QX04 = {1}</i></p> <p>QX08 Dans votre entreprise ou votre structure...</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="344 300 1385 808"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Oui</th> <th>Non</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>QX08_A Avez-vous le pouvoir d'embaucher ou de licencier des employés?</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>QX08_B Recevez-vous des honoraires convenus, sur une base hebdomadaire ou mensuelle?</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>QX08_C Avez-vous des employés (qui travaillent pour vous)?</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>QX08_D Avez-vous plusieurs clients?</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Oui	Non	QX08_A Avez-vous le pouvoir d'embaucher ou de licencier des employés?	1	2	QX08_B Recevez-vous des honoraires convenus, sur une base hebdomadaire ou mensuelle?	1	2	QX08_C Avez-vous des employés (qui travaillent pour vous)?	1	2	QX08_D Avez-vous plusieurs clients?	1	2
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NL	<p><i>if (Q3 = 2)</i></p> <p>Q7_table Beantwoord de volgende vragen over uw werk.</p> <p><i>Question type: Table</i></p> <p><i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i></p> <p><i>Sub-questions:</i></p> <p>Q7A Hebt u de bevoegdheid om werknemers aan te nemen of te ontslaan?</p> <p>Q7B Krijgt u regelmatig uitbetaald? (dus elke week of elke maand)?</p> <p>Q7C Hebt u werknemers (die voor u werken)?</p> <p>Q7D Hebt u in het algemeen meer dan één klant?</p> <p><i>Categories:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nee 2. Ja 															

Question 9 is asked to the employees and question 10 is asked to those who answered yes to having a contract or agreement. The two questions were one question in the pilot survey, but to make the survey flow easier, we have separated them to two questions.

Q9	SQ	ASK ONLY IF Q4=1 9. Do you have a contract or agreement? 1. Yes 2. No
	UK	ASK ONLY IF Q4=1 12. Do you have a contract? If so, does it specify the agreed working hours? 1. No 2. Yes, specified 3. Yes, not specified
	FR	Si QX04 = {2,3} QX09 Avez-vous un contrat de travail ? 1. Oui 2. Non
	SE	<i>Display This Question:</i> <i>If Vilken av de här grupperna beskriver bäst dig själv just nu? = Har heltidsanställning (även kortvarigt sjukskriven, föräldraledig)</i> <i>Or Vilken av de här grupperna beskriver bäst dig själv just nu? = Har deltidsanställning (även kortvarigt sjukskriven, föräldraledig)</i> <i>Or Vilken av de här grupperna beskriver bäst dig själv just nu? = Har arbete i arbetsmarknadspolitiska åtgärder/genomgår arbetsmarknadsutbildning</i> <i>Or Välj den eller de kategorier som gäller för ditt arbete. = Arbetar via ett bemanningsföretag</i> q25 Har du ett kontrakt eller anställningsavtal? 1. Ja 2. Nej
NL	if (Q3 = 1) Q8 Hebt u een arbeidscontract of arbeidsovereenkomst? Answer type: Radio buttons Categories: 1. Nee 2. Ja	

Q10	SQ	10. Do you have a fixed agreement of the number of hours to work? 1. Yes 2. No
	UK	Included in Q9
	FR	Si QX09 = {1} QX10 Le contrat de travail de votre emploi principal précise-t-il le nombre d'heures de travail que vous devez effectuer? 1. Oui 2. Non

SE	<p>q35 Nu följer några frågor om dina arbetstider.</p> <p><i>Display This Question:</i></p> <p><i>If Vilken av de här grupperna beskriver bäst dig själv just nu? = Har heltidsanställning (även kortvarigt sjukskriven, föräldraledig)</i></p> <p><i>Or Vilken av de här grupperna beskriver bäst dig själv just nu? = Har deltidsanställning (även kortvarigt sjukskriven, föräldraledig)</i></p> <p><i>Or Vilken av de här grupperna beskriver bäst dig själv just nu? = Har arbete i arbetsmarknadspolitiska åtgärder/genomgår arbetsmarknadsutbildning</i></p> <p>q37 Har du ett fast avtal om antalet timmar du ska arbeta?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ja 2. Nej
NL	<p><i>if (Q3 = 1)</i></p> <p>Q9 Is het aantal uren dat u werkt vastgelegd in een overeenkomst?</p> <p><i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i></p> <p><i>Categories:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nee 2. Ja

Question 11 is only asked to those who have agreed working hours in the UK, France and Sweden. In the Netherlands, this question was asked to those without agreed working hours. Note that after the pilot survey, we have included the phrase that the unpaid meal breaks are excluded to make the question clearer and comparable across countries with different rules regarding working hours.

Q11	SQ	<p>ASK Q11 ONLY IF Q10=1</p> <p><i>OE NUM – 0-100</i></p> <p>11. In a typical work week, how many working hours are you expected to work per week according to your employment contract? – please exclude meal breaks that is not paid</p>
	UK	<p>The next questions are about your paid and unpaid working hours in your main job (that takes up most hours per week, or the one with higher pay if several jobs have the same hour)</p> <p><i>ASK Q17 ONLY IF Q12=2</i></p> <p><i>OE NUM – 0-100</i></p> <p>17. In a typical work week, what is the agreed working hours according to the contract?</p>
	FR	<p><i>Si QX10 = {1}</i></p> <p>QX11 Au cours d'une semaine de travail « normale », quel est le nombre d'heures hebdomadaire prévu dans votre contrat de travail ?</p> <p><i>(Exclure les pauses repas non rémunérées)</i></p> <p><i>Saisissez un nombre entier ou demi-entier (par exemple « 37.5 » pour 37 heures et demie)</i></p> <p>[Champ numérique] heure(s)/semaine</p>
	SE	<p><i>Display This Question: If Har du ett kontrakt eller anställningsavtal? = Ja</i></p> <p>q43 Under en typisk arbetsvecka, hur många timmar förväntas du arbeta enligt ditt anställningsavtal?</p>

		Räkna bara med de timmar som är betalda, uteslut obetalda matraster. Avrunda till hela timmar.
	NL	<i>if (Q9 = 1)</i> Q10 Hoeveel uur wordt u verwacht in een gemiddelde werkweek te werken volgens uw arbeidsovereenkomst? Tel hier onbetaalde pauzes, zoals de lunch niet in mee <i>Answer type: Integer</i> <i>Min: 0</i> <i>Max: 168</i> <i>Label-right: uur per week</i>

Question 12 is asked to everyone (who is working or has worked) and it was derived from the Labour Force Survey (LFS). We have included this question as a way of identifying the additional working hours workers actually engage in outside of agreed working hours.

Q12	SQ	<i>OE NUM – 0-100</i> 12. How many hours per week do you usually work in your main job/business – please exclude meal breaks that is not paid?
	UK	<i>OE NUM – 0-100</i> 18. How many hours per week do you usually actually work in your main job/business – please exclude meal breaks?
	FR	<i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i> QX12 Habituellement, combien d’heures par semaine travaillez-vous dans votre emploi principal ? (Exclure les pauses repas non rémunérées) Saisissez un nombre entier ou demi-entier (par exemple « 37.5 » pour 37 heures et demie) <i>[Champ numérique] heure(s)/semaine</i>
	SE	q44 Hur många timmar per vecka arbetar du vanligtvis i ditt arbete? Räkna bara med de timmar som är betalda, uteslut obetalda matraster. Avrunda till hela timmar.
	NL	Q11 Hoeveel uur per week werkt u gemiddeld in uw [/ belangrijkste] baan? Tel hier onbetaalde pauzes, zoals de lunch niet in mee <i>Answer type: Integer</i> <i>Min: 0</i> <i>Max: 168</i> <i>Label-right: uur per week</i>

Question 13 was initially adopted from the EWCS, but was revised in the SQ after consultation with ILO. The categories were adapted to the contractual arrangements present in the national context, following advice from experts in the national probability panels. In France, the question was asked only to the employees.

Q13	SQ	13. Is your contract or agreement...? <i>Select all that applies</i> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. For a specified period of time 2. Until the date a task is completed 3. Permanent or until retirement 4. Ongoing, until further notice 5. Don't know
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	UK	13. What kind of employment contract do you have in your main job? 1. Contract of unlimited duration 2. Contract of limited duration 3. A temporary employment agency contract 4. An apprenticeship or other training scheme 5. Zero hours contract (without agreed minimum working hours) 6. On-call, on-demand jobs (with agreed minimum working hours) 7. Other (write:)
	FR	<i>Si QX04 = {2,3}</i> QX13 Votre contrat ou accord dure-t-il... ? 1. Pour une durée déterminée 2. Jusqu'à l'accomplissement d'une tâche 3. En permanence ou jusqu'à la retraite 4. De façon continue, jusqu'à nouvel ordre 5. Je ne sais pas [Exclusif]
	SE	q29 Vilken eller vilka av följande former stämmer för din anställning? Välj allt som stämmer. 1. Tillsvidareanställning 2. Tidsbegränsad anställning 3. Projektanställning 4. Behovsanställning 5. Vet ej
	NL	Q12 Wat voor een type contract hebt u? Meerdere antwoorden mogelijk <i>Answer type: Checkboxes</i> <i>Categories:</i> 1. Een contract voor bepaalde tijd (tijdelijk) 2. Een contract tot dat een bepaalde taak voltooid is 3. Een contract voor onbepaalde tijd (vast) 4. Oproepcontract (bijv. nuluren of min-max) 5. Uitzendovereenkomst 6. Detacheringscontract (interim) 7. Leerwerkovereenkomst (bijv. BBL) 8. Payroll contract -1. Ik weet het niet

Question 14 is meant to differentiate between those who have minimum guaranteed working hours and those who don't (so-called the on-call or on-demand workers). This would be an equivalent of answer categories 5 and 6 for Q13 in the pilot survey. In France and the Netherlands, it is asked to those who have a contract/agreement; and in Sweden, it is asked to those who have answered "Behovsanställning" from the previous question.

Q14	SQ	14. Does the contract guarantee a minimum amount of hours or work for you? 1. Yes 2. No
	UK	No question for this
	FR	<i>Si QX09 = {1}</i> QX14 Le contrat vous garantit-il un minimum d'heures ou de travail ? 1. Oui 2. Non

SE	<p><i>Display This Question: If Vilken eller vilka av följande former stämmer för din anställning? Välj allt som stämmer. = Behovsanställning</i></p> <p>q39 Garanterar ditt kontrakt ett minsta antal timmar eller arbete för dig?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ja 2. Nej
NL	<p><i>if (Q8 = 2 or -1 not in Q12)</i></p> <p>Q13 Is in uw contract een minimaal aantal uren of opdrachten gegarandeerd?</p> <p><i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i></p> <p><i>Categories:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nee 2. Ja

Question 15 asks for the number of workers working within the respondents' company or organisation, using the same categories across the surveys in the different countries.

Q15	SQ	<p><i>IF Q4=2 "business" instead of "company or organization"</i></p> <p>15. How many workers in total work in your company or organization?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I work alone 2. 2-9 3. 10-24 4. 25-99 5. 100-249 6. 250-499 7. 500 or more
	UK	<p>14. How many employees in total work in your company/organization/business?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. (works alone) 2. 2-9 3. 10-24 4. 25-99 5. 100-249 6. 250-499 7. 500 or more
	FR	<p><i>Si QX04 = {1}</i></p> <p>QX15 Au total, combien de salariés travaillent au sein de votre entreprise ou structure?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Je travaille seul(e) 2. 2 – 9 3. 10 – 24 4. 25 – 99 5. 100 – 249 6. 250 – 499 7. 500 ou plus
	SE	<p>q17 Hur många arbetar totalt i {e://Field/arbetsituation}?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Jag jobbar ensam 2. 2-9 3. 10-24 4. 25-99 5. 100-249 6. 250-499 7. 500 eller fler

	NL	Hoeveel werknemers werken er in totaal in uw [zaak / bedrijf of organisatie]? <i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i> <i>Categories:</i> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ik werk alleen 2. 2-9 3. 10-24 4. 25-99 5. 100-249 6. 250-499 7. 500 of meer
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Question 16 was adopted from the EWCS. In France, it is not asked as the panel already has the data on this (unless participants have changed their job within the last 12 months), and QX04 (question 4) is used as an alternative question to identify working for the public/private sector. In Sweden, we have used the question already contained in the panel already, which has different categories: 1) government, 2) regional, 3) municipal, 4) private, and 5) non-profit organization/foundation.

Q16	SQ	16. Are you working in...? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The private sector 2. The public sector 3. A joint private-public organization or company 4. The not-for-profit sector or an NGO 5. Other (write:)
	UK	15. Are you working in...? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The private sector 2. The public sector 3. A joint private-public organization or company 4. The not-for-profit sector or an NGO 5. Other (write:) OE CHA
	FR	Deleted for ELIPSS
	SE	q19 Inom vilken sektor arbetar du? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Statlig 2. Kommunal 3. Landstings- / regional 4. Privat 5. Icke vinstdrivande organisation/stiftelse
	NL	Q15 In welke sector werkt u? <i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i> <i>Categories:</i> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. De private sector (commercieel) 2. De publieke sector (overheid) 3. Een gezamenlijke privaat-publieke organisatie of onderneming 4. De non-profitsector of een ngo 5. Anders, namelijk:

Q17	SQ	17. In your main job, do you have any responsibility for supervising the work of other people? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No
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	UK	16. In your main job, do you have any responsibility for supervising the work of other employees? (EWCS) 1. Yes 2. No
	FR	<i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i> QX17 Avez-vous des personnes qui travaillent sous votre direction et pour lesquelles les augmentations de salaire, les primes ou les promotions dépendent étroitement de vous? 1. Oui 2. Non
	SE	q31 Arbetsleder du andra i ditt arbete? 1. Ja 2. Nej
	NL	Q16 Geeft u in uw belangrijkste baan leiding aan andere mensen? <i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i> <i>Categories:</i> 1. Nee 2. Ja

Questions 18 and 19 are about overtime work and whether or not it is paid by the employer/contractor. Note that in the SQ, we have included a script explaining what unpaid working hours mean, as well as the definition of overtime work from the ILO. Moreover, the question is divided into two, with one asking whether or not one has engaged in overtime work and how frequently they've done it, and the other one asking to what extent it is paid for. Question 19 is only asked to those who have done overtime work. Note that for Sweden, we have revised question 18 to match question 19 in the time period from "in the past months" to "in the past 12 months".

Q18	SQ	People work to get paid, but sometimes people do tasks that are not paid, which is called 'unpaid working hours'. The next questions are about your paid and unpaid working hours in your main job. 18. Have you ever done overtime work in the past months? If so, how frequently do you do it? *overtime is the working hours that are done in addition to normal (contractual) working hours during a day or a week (ILO definition) 1. no, I haven't done any overtime work 2. yes, once a month or less 3. yes, several times per month 4. yes, several times a week 5. yes, daily
	UK	20. Do you get paid or compensations for your overtime work? 1. I do not work overtime 2. I work overtime, and it is fully compensated 3. I work overtime, and it is partially compensated 4. I work overtime, but is not compensated
	FR	<i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i> De manière générale, les gens travaillent pour être payés. Mais il arrive à des gens d'effectuer des tâches qui ne sont pas rémunérées, ce que l'on appelle des « heures de travail non rémunérées ». Les questions suivantes portent sur vos heures de travail rémunérées et non rémunérées dans votre emploi principal.

		<p><i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i></p> <p>QX18 Avez-vous effectué des heures supplémentaires au cours des mois écoulés, et si oui, à quelle fréquence ?</p> <p><i>Les heures supplémentaire désignent les heures de travail effectuées au-delà de la durée contractuelle quotidienne ou hebdomadaire.</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Non, je n'ai pas effectué d'heures supplémentaires 2. Oui, une fois par mois ou moins 3. Oui, plusieurs fois par mois 4. Oui, plusieurs fois par semaine 5. Oui, tous les jours
	SE	<p>q50 Folk får betalt när de arbetar, men ibland utför folk obetalda uppgifter, vilket kallas "obetald arbetstid". Nästa frågor handlar om din betalda och obetalda arbetstid på ditt arbete.</p> <p>q52 Hur ofta har du arbetat övertid de senaste 12 månaderna? Övertid är den arbetstid som sker utöver normal (avtalad) arbetstid under en dag, en vecka eller en månad.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. En gång i månaden eller mindre 2. Flera gånger i månaden 3. Flera gånger i veckan 4. Dagligen 5. Jag har inte arbetat övertid
	NL	<p>Mensen werken om geld te verdienen, maar soms doen mensen ook taken waar ze niet betaald voor worden. Dat zijn dan 'onbetaalde werkuren'. De volgende vragen gaan over de betaalde en onbetaalde werkuren in uw [/ belangrijkste]baan.</p> <p><i>if (1 in p_belbezig or 2 in p_belbezig or 3 in p_belbezig)</i></p> <p>Q17 Hebt u de afgelopen maanden wel eens overuren gemaakt? Overuren zijn werkuren die bovenop de normale (contractuele) uren worden gemaakt. <i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i> <i>Categories:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nee, ik heb de afgelopen maanden geen overuren gemaakt 2. Ja, één keer per maand of minder 3. Ja, meerdere keren per maand 4. Ja, meerdere keren per week 5. Ja, dagelijks

Q19	SQ	<p>19. Have you received any pay or compensation for your overtime work in the past 12 months?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No 2. Yes, but mostly not paid and part of it paid 3. Yes, and mostly paid but part of it not paid 4. Yes, fully paid
	UK	<p>20. Do you get paid or compensations for your overtime work?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I do not work overtime 2. I work overtime, and it is fully compensated 3. I work overtime, and it is partially compensated 4. I work overtime, but is not compensated
	FR	<p><i>Si QX18 = {2,3,4,5}</i></p>

		<p>QX19 Avez-vous reçu une rémunération (ou une compensation) pour les heures supplémentaires que vous avez effectuées au cours des 12 derniers mois?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Non 2. Oui, mais seulement une partie des heures ont été payées 3. Oui, et la plupart des heures ont été payées 4. Oui, toutes les heures supplémentaires sont payées
	SE	<p><i>Display This Question:</i></p> <p><i>If Hur ofta har du arbetat övertid de senaste 12 månaderna? Övertid är den arbetstid som sker utöver... = En gång i månaden eller mindre</i></p> <p><i>Or Hur ofta har du arbetat övertid de senaste 12 månaderna? Övertid är den arbetstid som sker utöver... = Flera gånger i månaden</i></p> <p><i>Or Hur ofta har du arbetat övertid de senaste 12 månaderna? Övertid är den arbetstid som sker utöver... = Flera gånger i veckan</i></p> <p><i>Or Hur ofta har du arbetat övertid de senaste 12 månaderna? Övertid är den arbetstid som sker utöver... = Dagligen</i></p> <p>q54 Har du fått någon lön eller ersättning för ditt övertidsarbete under de senaste 12 månaderna?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nej 2. Ja, men majoriteten obetalt och en del betalt 3. Ja, majoriteten betalt men en del obetalt 4. Ja, jag får full ersättning
	NL	<p><i>if (Q17 > 1)</i></p> <p>Q18 Hebt u de afgelopen 12 maanden een vergoeding of loon ontvangen voor de gemaakte overuren?</p> <p><i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i></p> <p><i>Categories:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nee 2. Ja, maar grotendeels niet betaald en deels betaald 3. Ja, en grotendeels betaald, maar deels niet betaald 4. Ja, volledig betaald

Question 20 asks those respondents who have more than one job how many hours they work in their other job, providing a more complete picture of the total hours worked for this group of respondents.

Q20	SQ	20. How many hours do you usually work per week for your job(s) other than your main paid job?
	UK	<p><i>ASK Q19 ONLY IF Q3=1</i></p> <p><i>OE NUM – 0-100</i></p> <p>19. How many hours a week on average do you work in job(s) other than your main paid job?</p>
	FR	<p><i>Si QA03 = {1}</i></p> <p>QA20 Habituellement, combien d'heures par semaine effectuez-vous dans votre (vos) autre(s) emploi(s) (autre que votre emploi principal) ? (Veuillez saisir un nombre entier sans décimale et sans autre caractère - lettre, espace, ponctuation) <i>[Champ numérique] heure(s)/semaine</i></p>

SE	<i>Display This Question: If Har du under den senaste månaden arbetat på mer än ett jobb? Observera att detta inte gäller vid... = Ja</i> q46 Hur många timmar arbetar du vanligtvis per vecka för ditt/dina andra jobb utöver ditt huvudsakliga arbete?
NL	<i>If (Q2 = 2)</i> Q19 Hoeveel uren werkt u gewoonlijk per week bij uw andere baan/banen, naast uw betaalde belangrijkste baan? <i>Answer type: Integer</i> <i>Min: 0</i> <i>Max: 168</i> <i>Label-right: uren per week</i>

Questions 21 and 22 are about the unpaid work approached from time perspective. In the pilot survey, we first asked if the respondents have engaged in specific tasks then asked how frequently they do it IF they do it. The answer category “never” for the UK survey is therefore an error as only those who answered to do the task answered the frequency question. In the SQ, we have changed it to merge the two questions and changed the wordings of the tasks and added examples to enhance comprehensibility of the questions.

Q21	SQ	Now follows a set of questions regarding different work tasks and if they are paid by your employer or client. 21. Is the following task included as part of your main job? If so, how frequently do you do it?																																																
		<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Yes, daily</th> <th>Yes, several times a week</th> <th>Yes, several times a month</th> <th>Yes, but less often</th> <th>Never</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>A. Waiting between tasks/clients</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>B. Communication with clients/employers (e.g., negotiating, email exchanges, meetings)</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>C. Administrative/paper work (e.g., dealing with HR, physical paper work, writing reports)</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>D. Traveling between jobs and tasks (excluding commuting time between home and work)</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>E. Maintaining work equipment or tools</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>F. Networking (e.g., any efforts made to get more clients/orders/business in the current job or maintain them over time, such as contacting or meeting people, attending events)</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>G. Preparing for the main task agreed by contract (e.g., getting</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Yes, daily	Yes, several times a week	Yes, several times a month	Yes, but less often	Never	A. Waiting between tasks/clients	1	2	3	4	5	B. Communication with clients/employers (e.g., negotiating, email exchanges, meetings)	1	2	3	4	5	C. Administrative/paper work (e.g., dealing with HR, physical paper work, writing reports)	1	2	3	4	5	D. Traveling between jobs and tasks (excluding commuting time between home and work)	1	2	3	4	5	E. Maintaining work equipment or tools	1	2	3	4	5	F. Networking (e.g., any efforts made to get more clients/orders/business in the current job or maintain them over time, such as contacting or meeting people, attending events)	1	2	3	4	5	G. Preparing for the main task agreed by contract (e.g., getting	1	2	3	4	5
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	ready or practicing or gathering materials for the main tasks, drawing up schedule or plan of the day)					
	H. Training for the main job (including workshops, conference)	1	2	3	4	5
UK	21. In your main paid job: has this occurred to you?					
		No	Yes			
	A. Waiting time between jobs/tasks	1	2			
	B. Preparation time	1	2			
	C. Communication with clients/employers	1	2			
	D. Administrative/paper work	1	2			
	E. Travel time between jobs and tasks (excluding commuting time between home and work)	1	2			
	F. Maintenance time (e.g., time spent on maintaining work equipment)	1	2			
	G. Networking time (contacting or meeting people related to the job to build relationships or maintain them overtime; attending events in order to meet new people)	1	2			
	H. 'Volunteer work' as part of the job	1	2			
	I. Training	1	2			
	<i>SHOW ONLY ITEMS WITH CODE 2 IN Q21</i>					
	23. On average, how frequently do you do the following work unpaid?					
		Daily	Several times a week	Several times a month	Less often	Never
	A. Waiting time between jobs/tasks	1	2	3	4	5
	B. Preparation time	1	2	3	4	5
	C. Communication with clients/employers	1	2	3	4	5
	D. Administrative/paper work	1	2	3	4	5
	E. Travel time between jobs and tasks (excluding commuting time between home and work)	1	2	3	4	5
	F. Maintenance time (e.g., time spent on maintaining work equipment)	1	2	3	4	5
	G. Networking time (contacting or meeting people related to the job to build relationships or maintain them overtime; attending events in order to meet new people)	1	2	3	4	5
	H. 'Volunteer work' as part of the job	1	2	3	4	5
	I. Training	1	2	3	4	5
FR	<i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i>					

	<p>Les questions suivantes porteront sur les différentes tâches effectuées dans le cadre de votre travail, et leurs rémunérations.</p> <p><i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i></p> <p>QX21 Les tâches suivantes font-elles partie de votre emploi principal, et si oui à quelle fréquence?</p> <p>QX21_A Attente entre des tâches/clients</p> <p>QX21_B Communication avec les clients/employeurs (par exemple négociation, échanges de courriers, réunions, etc.)</p> <p>QX21_C Travail administratif/de bureau (par exemple gestion RH, paperasse, rédaction de rapports, etc.)</p> <p>QX21_D Déplacements professionnels (par exemple entre différents sites, hors temps de trajets entre le domicile et le lieu de travail, etc.)</p> <p>QX21_E Entretien d'équipements ou d'outils de travail</p> <p>QX21_F Faire du réseau (par exemple tous les efforts déployés pour obtenir plus de clients/commandes, contacter ou rencontrer des gens, assister à des événements, etc.)</p> <p>QX21_G Préparation de la tâche principale contractuelle (par exemple élaboration du calendrier et des plannings, préparations des documents, etc.)</p> <p>QX21_H Formation (y compris ateliers, conférences, etc.)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Oui, chaque jour 2. Oui, plusieurs fois par semaine 3. Oui, plusieurs fois par mois 4. Oui, mais moins souvent 5. Jamais
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SE	<p>q56 Nu följer några frågor som handlar om olika arbetsuppgifter och om du får betalt för dem av din arbetsgivare eller uppdragsgivare/klient.</p> <p>q58 Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det?</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="349 371 1388 1527"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="349 371 735 479"></th> <th data-bbox="735 371 863 479">Ja, dagligen</th> <th data-bbox="863 371 991 479">Ja, flera gånger i veckan</th> <th data-bbox="991 371 1131 479">Ja, flera gånger i månaden</th> <th data-bbox="1131 371 1260 479">Ja, men mer sällan</th> <th data-bbox="1260 371 1388 479">Aldrig</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="349 479 735 555">1. Vänta mellan uppgifter/kunder</td> <td data-bbox="735 479 863 555">1</td> <td data-bbox="863 479 991 555">2</td> <td data-bbox="991 479 1131 555">3</td> <td data-bbox="1131 479 1260 555">4</td> <td data-bbox="1260 479 1388 555">5</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="349 555 735 663">2. Kommunikation med kunder/arbetsgivare (t.ex. förhandlingar, e-post, möten)</td> <td data-bbox="735 555 863 663">1</td> <td data-bbox="863 555 991 663">2</td> <td data-bbox="991 555 1131 663">3</td> <td data-bbox="1131 555 1260 663">4</td> <td data-bbox="1260 555 1388 663">5</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="349 663 735 770">3. Administration/ pappersarbete (t.ex. att hantera HR, skriva rapporter)</td> <td data-bbox="735 663 863 770">1</td> <td data-bbox="863 663 991 770">2</td> <td data-bbox="991 663 1131 770">3</td> <td data-bbox="1131 663 1260 770">4</td> <td data-bbox="1260 663 1388 770">5</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="349 770 735 913">4. Resa mellan arbete och uppgifter (exklusive pendlingstid mellan hem och arbete)</td> <td data-bbox="735 770 863 913">1</td> <td data-bbox="863 770 991 913">2</td> <td data-bbox="991 770 1131 913">3</td> <td data-bbox="1131 770 1260 913">4</td> <td data-bbox="1260 770 1388 913">5</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="349 913 735 990">5. Underhållning av arbetsutrustning eller verktyg</td> <td data-bbox="735 913 863 990">1</td> <td data-bbox="863 913 991 990">2</td> <td data-bbox="991 913 1131 990">3</td> <td data-bbox="1131 913 1260 990">4</td> <td data-bbox="1260 913 1388 990">5</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="349 990 735 1236">6. Nätverkande (t.ex. allt arbete för att få fler kunder/order/företag eller behålla dem över tid, som att kontakta eller träffa människor, delta i evenemang)</td> <td data-bbox="735 990 863 1236">1</td> <td data-bbox="863 990 991 1236">2</td> <td data-bbox="991 990 1131 1236">3</td> <td data-bbox="1131 990 1260 1236">4</td> <td data-bbox="1260 990 1388 1236">5</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="349 1236 735 1420">7. Förberedelser inför huvuduppgiften (t.ex. förbereda sig eller öva eller samla material, upprätta schema eller plan för dagen)</td> <td data-bbox="735 1236 863 1420">1</td> <td data-bbox="863 1236 991 1420">2</td> <td data-bbox="991 1236 1131 1420">3</td> <td data-bbox="1131 1236 1260 1420">4</td> <td data-bbox="1260 1236 1388 1420">5</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="349 1420 735 1527">8. Utbildning/träning för sitt arbete (inklusive workshops, konferens)</td> <td data-bbox="735 1420 863 1527">1</td> <td data-bbox="863 1420 991 1527">2</td> <td data-bbox="991 1420 1131 1527">3</td> <td data-bbox="1131 1420 1260 1527">4</td> <td data-bbox="1260 1420 1388 1527">5</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Ja, dagligen	Ja, flera gånger i veckan	Ja, flera gånger i månaden	Ja, men mer sällan	Aldrig	1. Vänta mellan uppgifter/kunder	1	2	3	4	5	2. Kommunikation med kunder/arbetsgivare (t.ex. förhandlingar, e-post, möten)	1	2	3	4	5	3. Administration/ pappersarbete (t.ex. att hantera HR, skriva rapporter)	1	2	3	4	5	4. Resa mellan arbete och uppgifter (exklusive pendlingstid mellan hem och arbete)	1	2	3	4	5	5. Underhållning av arbetsutrustning eller verktyg	1	2	3	4	5	6. Nätverkande (t.ex. allt arbete för att få fler kunder/order/företag eller behålla dem över tid, som att kontakta eller träffa människor, delta i evenemang)	1	2	3	4	5	7. Förberedelser inför huvuduppgiften (t.ex. förbereda sig eller öva eller samla material, upprätta schema eller plan för dagen)	1	2	3	4	5	8. Utbildning/träning för sitt arbete (inklusive workshops, konferens)	1	2	3	4	5
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NL	<p>Er volgen nu een aantal vragen over verschillende taken op werk, en of deze wel of niet betaald worden.</p> <p>Q20_table Zijn de volgende taken onderdeel van uw [/ belangrijkste]baan? <i>Question type: Table</i> <i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i> <i>Sub-questions:</i> Q20A Wachten tussen taken/klanten door Q20B Communicatie met klanten/werkgevers (bijv. onderhandelingen, e-mailverkeer, vergaderingen)</p>																																																						

	<p>Q20C Administratief werk/bureauwerk (bijv. contacten met HR, fysiek bureauwerk, opstellen van rapporten)</p> <p>Q20D Verplaatsingen tussen werk en taken (exclusief woon-werkverkeer)</p> <p>Q20E Onderhoud van werkapparatuur of instrumenten</p> <p>Q20F Netwerken (bijv. inspanningen om meer klanten/bestellingen/zaken in de huidige job binnen te halen of te behouden, zoals contact opnemen met mensen of mensen ontmoeten, evenementen bijwonen)</p> <p>Q20G Voorbereiding van de hoofdwerkzaamheden (bijv. voorbereiden, oefenen of materiaal verzamelen voor de hoofdtaken, roosters of dagplanning opstellen)</p> <p>Q20H Opleidingen volgen (inclusief workshops, conferenties)</p> <p><i>Categories:</i></p> <p>4. Ja, dagelijks</p> <p>3. Ja, meerdere keren per week</p> <p>2. Ja, meerdere keren per maand</p> <p>1. Ja, maar minder vaak</p> <p>0. Nooit</p>
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For question 22, we asked to what extent they are paid/unpaid among those who answered the categories other than “never”. Note that in the SQ, there are two answer categories for partially paid (i.e., mostly paid, part of it not paid; mostly not paid, part of it paid). Moreover, in the pilot survey, we asked for specific examples of tasks that are not paid, which have been deleted in the SQ due to the limited space and limited usefulness.

Q22	SQ	<i>SHOW ONLY ITEMS WITH CODE 1-4 IN Q21</i>				
		22. In your main paid job: are they paid by your employer/client?				
			Fully paid	Mostly paid, part of it not paid	Mostly not paid, part of it paid	Not paid at all
		A. Waiting between tasks/clients	1	2	3	4
		B. Communication with clients/employers (e.g., negotiating, email exchanges, meetings)	1	2	3	4
		C. Administrative/paper work (e.g., dealing with HR, physical paper work, writing reports)	1	2	3	4
		D. Traveling between jobs and tasks (excluding commuting time between home and work)	1	2	3	4
		E. Maintaining work equipment or tools	1	2	3	4
		F. Networking (e.g., any efforts made to get more clients/orders/business in the current job or maintain them over time, such as contacting or meeting people, attending events)	1	2	3	4
		G. Preparing for the main task agreed by contract (e.g., getting ready or practicing	1	2	3	4

	or gathering materials for the main tasks, drawing up schedule or plan of the day)																																												
	H. Training for the main job (including workshops, conference)	1	2	3	4																																								
UK	<p><i>SHOW ONLY ITEMS WITH CODE 2 IN Q21</i></p> <p>22. In your main paid job: are they paid by your employer/contractor?</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Fully paid</th> <th>Partially paid</th> <th>Fully unpaid</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>I. Waiting time between jobs/tasks</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>J. Preparation time</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>K. Communication with clients/employers</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>L. Administrative/paper work</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>M. Travel time between jobs and tasks (excluding commuting time between home and work)</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>N. Maintenance time (e.g., time spent on maintaining work equipment)</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>O. Networking time (contacting or meeting people related to the job to build relationships or maintain them overtime; attending events in order to meet new people)</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>P. 'Volunteer work' as part of the job</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Q. Training</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>24. Are there other types of work you do as part of your main job that are unpaid? If so, what are they?</p> <p>99. There is no other type of work I do as part of my main job that is unpaid. <i>EXCLUSIVE</i></p>						Fully paid	Partially paid	Fully unpaid	I. Waiting time between jobs/tasks	1	2	3	J. Preparation time	1	2	3	K. Communication with clients/employers	1	2	3	L. Administrative/paper work	1	2	3	M. Travel time between jobs and tasks (excluding commuting time between home and work)	1	2	3	N. Maintenance time (e.g., time spent on maintaining work equipment)	1	2	3	O. Networking time (contacting or meeting people related to the job to build relationships or maintain them overtime; attending events in order to meet new people)	1	2	3	P. 'Volunteer work' as part of the job	1	2	3	Q. Training	1	2	3
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FR	<p><i>Si QX21_x <> 5</i></p> <p>QX22 Dans votre emploi principal, les tâches suivantes sont-elles rémunérées par votre employeur ou client?</p> <p><i>[Items si QX21_x <> {5}]</i></p> <p>QX22_A Attente entre des tâches/clients</p> <p>QX22_B Communication avec les clients/employeurs (par exemple négociation, échanges de courriers, réunions, etc.)</p> <p>QX22_C Travail administratif/de bureau (par exemple gestion RH, paperasse, rédaction de rapports, etc.)</p> <p>QX22_D Déplacements professionnels (par exemple entre différents sites, hors temps de trajets entre le domicile et le lieu de travail, etc.)</p> <p>QX22_E Entretien d'équipements ou d'outils de travail</p> <p>QX22_F Faire du réseau (par exemple tous les efforts déployés pour obtenir plus de clients/commandes, contacter ou rencontrer des gens, assister à des événements, etc.)</p> <p>QX22_G Préparation de la tâche principale contractuelle (par exemple élaboration du calendrier et des plannings, préparations des documents, etc.)</p> <p>QX22_H Formation (y compris ateliers, conférences, etc.)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Entièrement rémunérées 2. En grande partie rémunérées, une partie non rémunérée 3. En grande partie non rémunérées, une partie rémunérée 4. Pas du tout rémunérées 																																												

SE	<p><i>Display This Question: If Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Ja, dagligen</i></p> <p><i>Or = Ja, flera gånger i veckan</i></p> <p><i>Or = Ja, flera gånger i månaden</i></p> <p><i>Or = Ja, men mer sällan</i></p> <p>q60 I vilken utsträckning betalas följande uppgifter av din arbetsgivare eller uppdragsgivare?</p> <p><i>Display Choices: If Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Ja, dagligen</i></p> <p><i>Or = Ja, flera gånger i veckan</i></p> <p><i>Or = Ja, flera gånger i månaden</i></p> <p><i>Or = Ja, men mer sällan</i></p> <table border="1" data-bbox="316 696 1402 1312"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Betalas helt</th> <th>Majoriteten betalt, en del obetalt</th> <th>Majoriteten obetalt, en del betalt</th> <th>Betalas inte alls</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1. Vänta mellan uppgifter/kunder</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2. Kommunikation med kunder/arbetsgivare</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3. Administration/ pappersarbete</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4. Resa mellan arbete och uppgifter (exklusive pendlingstid mellan hem och arbete)</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5. Underhållning av arbetsutrustning eller verktyg</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6. Nätverkande</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7. Förberedelser inför huvuduppgiften</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8. Utbildning/träning för sitt arbete</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Betalas helt	Majoriteten betalt, en del obetalt	Majoriteten obetalt, en del betalt	Betalas inte alls	1. Vänta mellan uppgifter/kunder	1	2	3	4	2. Kommunikation med kunder/arbetsgivare	1	2	3	4	3. Administration/ pappersarbete	1	2	3	4	4. Resa mellan arbete och uppgifter (exklusive pendlingstid mellan hem och arbete)	1	2	3	4	5. Underhållning av arbetsutrustning eller verktyg	1	2	3	4	6. Nätverkande	1	2	3	4	7. Förberedelser inför huvuduppgiften	1	2	3	4	8. Utbildning/träning för sitt arbete	1	2	3	4
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NL	<p>Krijgt u betaald voor de onderstaande taken bij uw [/ belangrijkste] baan?</p> <p><i>Question type: Table</i></p> <p><i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i></p> <p><i>Sub-questions:</i></p> <p>Q21A [Q20A>0] Wachten tussen taken/klanten door</p> <p>Q21B [Q20B>0] Communicatie met klanten/werkgevers (bijv. onderhandelingen, e-mailverkeer, vergaderingen)</p> <p>Q21C [Q20C>0] Administratief werk/bureauwerk (bijv. contacten met HR, fysiek bureauwerk, opstellen van rapporten)</p> <p>Q21D [Q20D>0] Verplaatsingen tussen werk en taken (exclusief woon-werkverkeer)</p> <p>Q21E [Q20E>0] Onderhoud van werkapparatuur of instrumenten</p> <p>Q21F [Q20F>0] Netwerken (bijv. inspanningen om meer klanten/bestellingen/zaken in de huidige job binnen te halen of te behouden, zoals contact opnemen met mensen of mensen ontmoeten, evenementen bijwonen)</p> <p>Q21G [Q20G>0] Voorbereiding van de hoofdwerkzaamheden (bijv. voorbereiden, oefenen of materiaal verzamelen voor de hoofdtaken, roosters of dagplanning opstellen)</p> <p>Q21H [Q20H>0] Opleidingen volgen (inclusief workshops, conferenties)</p>																																													

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Questions 23-25 are about unpaid labour, but approached from the perspective of material assets. Similar to the previous questions on unpaid time, we have changed the wordings of the questions and added some examples to make it easier for the respondents to understand the questions for the SQ. Communication tools have been separated into three categories – computer, phone and internet, and, after the pilot survey, a new category was added to the SQ: working space. Questions 24-25 are only asked to those who use the tools (i.e., answered ‘yes’ to Q23). The answer categories for Q24 is increased to 4 instead of 3 to have two answers for partially paid, as mentioned for the previous question. Q25 about ownership and expenses for use was added after the pilot survey. Note that those who answered ‘other’ to Q25 only were asked to specify which one in France but not in Sweden and the Netherlands as suggested by the country panels.

Q23	SQ	The following questions are about the expenses you have to make for your main job.		
		23. Do you need the following for your main job?		
			No	Yes
		A. Transportation means used during the working hours (e.g., car, bike, truck, etc.) excluding commuting between home and work	1	2
		B. Safety equipment (e.g., personal protective equipment (PPE), gloves, etc.)	1	2
		C. Specific clothing or accessories (including uniform)	1	2
		D. Computer (e.g., PC, laptop, tablet, and other connected device)	1	2
		E. Phone	1	2
		F. Internet	1	2
		G. Gifts/rewards for clients (including business dinners)	1	2
	H. Working space	1	2	
UK		The following questions are about the tools and equipment you need in your main job (that takes up most hours per week, or the one with higher pay if several jobs have the same hour)		
		25. Are the following equipment/tools/materials necessary for your main job?		
			No	Yes
		I. Transportation means (car, bike, truck, etc.)	1	2
		J. Related to safety (PPE(personal protective equipment), gloves, etc.)	1	2
		K. Related to appearance (certain clothes, accessories, make-up, etc.)	1	2
		L. Related to communication (mobile data, internet, etc.)	1	2
	M. Gifts/rewards for clients	1	2	
FR		<i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i> Les questions suivantes portent sur les frais que vous devez engager pour votre emploi principal.		

	<p><i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i></p> <p>QX23 Avez-vous besoin des éléments suivants dans votre emploi principal ?</p> <p>QX23_A De moyens de transport utilisés pendant les heures de travail (par exemple voiture, vélo, camion, etc.) hors trajets entre le domicile et le lieu de travail</p> <p>QX23_B D'équipements de sécurité (par exemple équipements de protection individuelle – EPI, gants, etc.)</p> <p>QX23_C De vêtements ou accessoires spécifiques (y compris uniforme)</p> <p>QX23_D D'ordinateur (par exemple PC, ordinateur portable, tablette et autre appareil connecté)</p> <p>QX23_E D'un téléphone</p> <p>QX23_F D'Internet</p> <p>QX23_G De cadeaux/récompenses pour les clients (y compris dîners d'affaires)</p> <p>QX23_H D'un espace de travail</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Oui 2. Non 																											
SE	<p>q62 Följande frågor handlar om vilka utgifter du behöver göra i ditt arbete.</p> <p>q64 Behöver du följande för ditt arbete?</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="336 837 1394 1245"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Ja</th> <th>Nej</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1. Transportmedel som används under arbetstiden (t.ex. bil, cykel, lastbil, osv.) exklusive pendling mellan hem och arbete</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2. Säkerhetsutrustning (t.ex. personlig skyddsutrustning, handskar, osv.)</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3. Specifika kläder eller tillbehör/uniform</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4. Dator/surfplatta</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5. Telefon</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6. Internet</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7. Gåvor/belöningar till kunder (inklusive affärsmiddagar)</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8. Arbetsyta</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Ja	Nej	1. Transportmedel som används under arbetstiden (t.ex. bil, cykel, lastbil, osv.) exklusive pendling mellan hem och arbete	1	2	2. Säkerhetsutrustning (t.ex. personlig skyddsutrustning, handskar, osv.)	1	2	3. Specifika kläder eller tillbehör/uniform	1	2	4. Dator/surfplatta	1	2	5. Telefon	1	2	6. Internet	1	2	7. Gåvor/belöningar till kunder (inklusive affärsmiddagar)	1	2	8. Arbetsyta	1	2
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NL	<p>De volgende vragen gaan over de kosten die u maakt voor uw [/ belangrijkste]baan.</p> <p>Q22_table</p> <p>Kunt u aangeven welke van de onderstaande zaken u nodig hebt in uw [/ belangrijkste] baan?</p> <p><i>Question type: Table</i></p> <p><i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i></p> <p><i>Sub-questions:</i></p> <p>Q22A Vervoer tijdens werkuren (bijv. auto, fiets, vrachtwagen enz.), met uitzondering van woon-werkverkeer</p> <p>Q22B Veiligheidsuitrusting (bijv. persoonlijke beschermingsmiddelen (PBM), handschoenen enz.)</p> <p>Q22C Specifieke kleding of accessoires (inclusief uniform)</p> <p>Q22D Computer (bijv. pc, laptop, tablet en andere toestellen die verbonden zijn met het internet)</p> <p>Q22E Telefoon</p> <p>Q22F Internet</p> <p>Q22G Geschenken/beloningen voor klanten (inclusief zakendiners)</p> <p>Q22H Werkplek (bijv. bureaustoel, kantoor of gehuurde werkplek)</p> <p><i>Categories:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nee 2. Ja 																											

Q24	SQ	<p><i>SHOW ONLY ITEMS WITH CODE 2 IN Q20</i></p> <p>24. Are the expenses for buying or maintaining the following paid by your employer/client?</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="347 360 1385 1093"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="347 360 938 539"></th> <th data-bbox="943 360 1038 539">Fully paid</th> <th data-bbox="1043 360 1155 539">Mostly paid, part of it unpaid</th> <th data-bbox="1160 360 1272 539">Mostly unpaid, part of it paid</th> <th data-bbox="1276 360 1385 539">Fully unpaid</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="347 546 938 680">A. Transportation means used during the working hours (e.g., car, bike, truck, etc.) excluding commuting between home and work</td> <td data-bbox="943 546 1038 680">1</td> <td data-bbox="1043 546 1155 680">2</td> <td data-bbox="1160 546 1272 680">3</td> <td data-bbox="1276 546 1385 680">4</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="347 687 938 754">B. Safety equipment (e.g., PPE (personal protective equipment), gloves, etc.)</td> <td data-bbox="943 687 1038 754">1</td> <td data-bbox="1043 687 1155 754">2</td> <td data-bbox="1160 687 1272 754">3</td> <td data-bbox="1276 687 1385 754">4</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="347 761 938 828">C. Specific clothing or accessories (including uniform)</td> <td data-bbox="943 761 1038 828">1</td> <td data-bbox="1043 761 1155 828">2</td> <td data-bbox="1160 761 1272 828">3</td> <td data-bbox="1276 761 1385 828">4</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="347 835 938 902">D. Computer (e.g., PC, laptop, tablet, and other connected device)</td> <td data-bbox="943 835 1038 902">1</td> <td data-bbox="1043 835 1155 902">2</td> <td data-bbox="1160 835 1272 902">3</td> <td data-bbox="1276 835 1385 902">4</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="347 909 938 943">E. Phone</td> <td data-bbox="943 909 1038 943">1</td> <td data-bbox="1043 909 1155 943">2</td> <td data-bbox="1160 909 1272 943">3</td> <td data-bbox="1276 909 1385 943">4</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="347 949 938 983">F. Internet</td> <td data-bbox="943 949 1038 983">1</td> <td data-bbox="1043 949 1155 983">2</td> <td data-bbox="1160 949 1272 983">3</td> <td data-bbox="1276 949 1385 983">4</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="347 990 938 1057">G. Gifts/rewards for clients (including business dinners)</td> <td data-bbox="943 990 1038 1057">1</td> <td data-bbox="1043 990 1155 1057">2</td> <td data-bbox="1160 990 1272 1057">3</td> <td data-bbox="1276 990 1385 1057">4</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="347 1064 938 1093">H. Working space</td> <td data-bbox="943 1064 1038 1093">1</td> <td data-bbox="1043 1064 1155 1093">2</td> <td data-bbox="1160 1064 1272 1093">3</td> <td data-bbox="1276 1064 1385 1093">4</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Fully paid	Mostly paid, part of it unpaid	Mostly unpaid, part of it paid	Fully unpaid	A. Transportation means used during the working hours (e.g., car, bike, truck, etc.) excluding commuting between home and work	1	2	3	4	B. Safety equipment (e.g., PPE (personal protective equipment), gloves, etc.)	1	2	3	4	C. Specific clothing or accessories (including uniform)	1	2	3	4	D. Computer (e.g., PC, laptop, tablet, and other connected device)	1	2	3	4	E. Phone	1	2	3	4	F. Internet	1	2	3	4	G. Gifts/rewards for clients (including business dinners)	1	2	3	4	H. Working space	1	2	3	4
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	<p>QX24_G De cadeaux/récompenses pour les clients (y compris dîners d'affaires)</p> <p>QX24_H D'un espace de travail</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Entièrement rémunérées 2. En grande partie pris en charge, une partie non prise 3. En grande partie pris en charge, une partie prise en charge 4. Pas du tout pris en charge 																																													
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		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Volledig betaald 2. Grotendeels betaald, maar deels onbetaald 3. Grotendeels onbetaald, maar deels betaald 4. Volledig onbetaald
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Q25	SQ	25. Who owns the following and who covers the expenses for using it?																																									
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	<p>Qui est propriétaire des éléments suivants et qui prend en charge les frais liés à leur utilisation?</p> <p>QX25_A De moyens de transport utilisés pendant les heures de travail (par exemple voiture, vélo, camion, etc.) hors trajets entre le domicile et le lieu de travail</p> <p>QX25_B D'équipements de sécurité (par exemple équipements de protection individuelle – EPI, gants, etc.)</p> <p>QX25_C De vêtements ou accessoires spécifiques (y compris uniforme)</p> <p>QX25_D D'ordinateur (par exemple PC, ordinateur portable, tablette et autre appareil connecté)</p> <p>QX25_E D'un téléphone</p> <p>QX25_F D'Internet</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. J'en suis propriétaire et je prends en charge les frais liés 2. J'en suis propriétaire, mais mon entreprise prend en charge les frais liés 3. Mon entreprise en est propriétaire, mais je prends en charge les frais liés 4. Mon entreprise en est propriétaire et prend en charge les frais liés 5. Autre (préciser) <p><i>Si QX25_A = {5}</i> QX25_A_TXT Veuillez préciser qui est propriétaire des éléments suivants et qui prend en charge les frais liés à leur utilisation: - De moyens de transport utilisés pendant les heures de travail (par exemple voiture, vélo, camion, etc.) hors trajets entre le domicile et le lieu de travail <i>[Champ texte]</i></p> <p><i>Si QX25_B = {5}</i> QX25_B_TXT Veuillez préciser qui est propriétaire des éléments suivants et qui prend en charge les frais liés à leur utilisation: - D'équipements de sécurité (par exemple équipements de protection individuelle – EPI, gants, etc.) <i>[Champ texte]</i></p> <p><i>Si QX25_C = {5}</i> QX25_C_TXT Veuillez préciser qui est propriétaire des éléments suivants et qui prend en charge les frais liés à leur utilisation: - De vêtements ou accessoires spécifiques (y compris uniforme) <i>[Champ texte]</i></p> <p><i>Si QX25_D = {5}</i> QX25_D_TXT Veuillez préciser qui est propriétaire des éléments suivants et qui prend en charge les frais liés à leur utilisation: - D'ordinateur (par exemple PC, ordinateur portable, tablette et autre appareil connecté) <i>[Champ texte]</i></p> <p><i>Si QX25_E = {5}</i> QX25_E_TXT Veuillez préciser qui est propriétaire des éléments suivants et qui prend en charge les frais liés à leur utilisation: - D'un téléphone <i>[Champ texte]</i></p> <p><i>Si QX25_F = {5}</i> QX25_F_TXT Veuillez préciser qui est propriétaire des éléments suivants et qui prend en charge les frais liés à leur utilisation: - D'Internet <i>[Champ texte]</i></p>
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SE	<p><i>Display This Question: If Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Transportmedel som används under arbetstiden (t.ex. bil, cykel, lastbil, osv.) exklusive pendling mellan hem och arbete [Ja]</i></p> <p><i>Or = Säkerhetsutrustning (t.ex. personlig skyddsutrustning, handskar, osv.) [Ja]</i></p> <p><i>Or = Specifika kläder eller tillbehör/uniform [Ja]</i></p> <p><i>Or = Dator/surfplatta [Ja]</i></p> <p><i>Or = Telefon [Ja]</i></p> <p><i>Or = Internet [Ja]</i></p> <p>q68 Vem äger följande och vem står för utgifterna förknippade med dess användning?</p> <p><i>Display Choices: If Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Ja</i></p> <table border="1" data-bbox="347 622 1391 1238"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Jag äger det och står för utgifterna</th> <th>Jag äger det men mitt arbete står för utgifterna</th> <th>Mitt arbete äger det men jag står för utgifterna</th> <th>Mitt arbete äger det och står för utgifterna</th> <th>Annat</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1. Transportmedel som används under arbetstiden</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>2. Säkerhetsutrustning</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>3. Specifika kläder eller tillbehör/ uniform</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>4. Dator/surfplatta</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>5. Telefon</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>6. Internet</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Jag äger det och står för utgifterna	Jag äger det men mitt arbete står för utgifterna	Mitt arbete äger det men jag står för utgifterna	Mitt arbete äger det och står för utgifterna	Annat	1. Transportmedel som används under arbetstiden	1	2	3	4		2. Säkerhetsutrustning	1	2	3	4		3. Specifika kläder eller tillbehör/ uniform	1	2	3	4		4. Dator/surfplatta	1	2	3	4		5. Telefon	1	2	3	4		6. Internet	1	2	3	4	
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NL	<p><i>If (Q22A > 1 or Q22B > 1 or Q22C > 1 or Q22D > 1 or Q22E > 1 or Q22F > 1)</i></p> <p>Q24_table Wie is de eigenaar van het volgende en wie neemt de kosten voor het gebruik ervan voor zijn rekening?</p> <p><i>Question type: Table</i></p> <p><i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i></p> <p><i>Sub-questions:</i></p> <p>Q24A [Q22A=2] Vervoer tijdens werkuren (bijv. auto, fiets, vrachtwagen enz.), met uitzondering van woon-werkverkeer</p> <p>Q24B [Q22B=2] Veiligheidsuitrusting (bijv. persoonlijke beschermingsmiddelen (PBM), handschoenen enz.)</p> <p>Q24C [Q22C=2] Specifieke kleding of accessoires (inclusief uniform)</p> <p>Q24D [Q22D=2] Computer (bijv. pc, laptop, tablet en andere toestellen die verbonden zijn met het internet)</p> <p>Q24E [Q22E=2] Telefoon</p> <p>Q24F [Q22F=2] Internet</p> <p>Categories:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Ik ben de eigenaar en ik betaal de kosten Ik ben de eigenaar, maar mijn bedrijf betaalt de kosten Mijn bedrijf is de eigenaar, maar ik betaal de kosten Mijn bedrijf is de eigenaar en betaalt de kosten Anders 																																										

Question 26 is asked to examine the reasons behind doing unpaid labour, based on the theory built from the qualitative interviews. Three categories of items are included. A-B indicate the inevitability of the unpaid work, C-E refers to doing unpaid work for reward, and F-H for doing unpaid work to avoid penalty. Note that some wordings have changed after the pilot survey to enhance readability of the questions.

Q26	SQ	<p>In this survey, we define unpaid work as any kind of tasks that are carried out as part of the main job but which are not paid or are carried out outside of the paid working time. For the self-employed, this can be all the tasks/hours that are not included as part of the contract of your work or products and therefore not paid.</p> <p>26. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?</p> <p>A. Unpaid work is part of my job B. There is no one to perform the tasks for my job instead of me C. Doing unpaid work can help with my career (e.g., promotion, increase in wage, bonus, finding a better job, etc.) D. Doing unpaid work is seen favourably by colleagues/clients/employers E. Doing unpaid work is an act of care or kindness towards people I work with (e.g., colleagues, clients) F. Not doing unpaid work would make me feel guilty G. Not doing unpaid work is seen badly by colleagues/clients/employers H. Not doing unpaid work might harm my career (e.g., promotion, finding better job in the future, wage, losing clients)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly disagree 2. Tend to disagree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. Tend to agree 5. Strongly agree
	UK	<p>In this survey, we define unpaid work as any kind of work that we do in our daily lives that is not paid. For the following questions, the unpaid work is strictly limited to the work that you do as part of your paid job that are unpaid. For the self-employed, this may refer to all the tasks/hours you that are not included as part of the price of your work or products. The 'work' here does not include any activities that can be considered a 'leisure'.</p> <p><i>ASK Q29 ONLY IF AT LEAST ONE CODE 2 OR 3 SELECTED IN Q22 OR IF AT LEAST ONE CODE 2 OR 3 SELECTED IN Q26</i></p> <p>29. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?</p> <p>A. Unpaid work is part of my job B. I do unpaid work, because there is no one to replace me C. I do unpaid work with because it might help my career (e.g., promotion, increase in wage, bonus, finding a better job, etc.) D. I do unpaid work because it is seen good by colleagues/clients/employers E. I do unpaid work out of care or kindness F. If I don't do unpaid work, I feel guilty G. Not doing unpaid work is seen badly by colleagues/clients/employers H. If I don't do unpaid work, it might harm on my career (e.g., promotion, finding better job in the future, wage, losing clients)</p>

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FR	<p><i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i></p> <p>Nous considérerons le travail non rémunéré comme tout type de tâches effectuées dans le cadre de l'emploi principal, mais qui sont non rémunérées ou bien qui sont effectuées en dehors du temps de travail rémunéré. Si vous êtes indépendant, il peut s'agir de tout ce qui n'est pas spécifié dans le contrat comme les tâches réalisées, les heures supplémentaires ou encore vos produits utilisés, et qui ne sont donc pas rémunérés.</p> <p><i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i></p> <p>QX26 Dans quelle mesure êtes-vous d'accord ou non avec les affirmations suivantes ?</p> <p>QX26_A Le travail non rémunéré fait partie de mon travail</p> <p>QX26_B Il n'y a personne pour effectuer les tâches de mon travail à ma place</p> <p>QX26_C Effectuer du travail non rémunéré peut être utile à ma carrière (par exemple promotion, augmentation de salaire, prime, trouver un meilleur emploi, etc.)</p> <p>QX26_D Effectuer du travail non rémunéré est perçu favorablement par les collègues/clients/employeurs</p> <p>QX26_E Effectuer du travail non rémunéré est une attention ou une faveur envers les personnes avec lesquelles je travaille (par exemple collègues, clients)</p> <p>QX26_F Ne pas effectuer de travail non rémunéré me donnerait un sentiment de culpabilité</p> <p>QX26_G Ne pas effectuer de travail non rémunéré est perçu défavorablement par les collègues/clients/employeurs</p> <p>QX26_H Ne pas effectuer de travail non rémunéré pourrait nuire à ma carrière (par exemple promotion, trouver un meilleur emploi à l'avenir, salaire, perte de clients)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pas du tout d'accord 2. Plutôt pas d'accord 3. Ni d'accord, ni pas d'accord 4. Plutôt d'accord 5. Tout à fait d'accord 															
SE	<p>q70 I denna undersökning definieras oavlönat arbete som alla slags uppgifter som utförs som en del av arbetet men utan att betalas, eller som utförs vid sidan av den betalda arbetstiden. För egenföretagare innebär det uppgifter eller tid som inte omfattas av kontraktet och därför inte är betalda.</p> <p>q72 I vilken utsträckning instämmer du med följande påståenden?</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Instämmer till fullo</th> <th>Instämmer till viss del</th> <th>Varken eller</th> <th>Instämmer inte</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1. Oavlönat arbete är en del av mitt jobb</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2. Det finns ingen som kan utföra mina arbetsuppgifter istället för mig</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Instämmer till fullo	Instämmer till viss del	Varken eller	Instämmer inte	1. Oavlönat arbete är en del av mitt jobb	1	2	3	4	2. Det finns ingen som kan utföra mina arbetsuppgifter istället för mig	1	2	3	4
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	3. Oavlönat arbete kan hjälpa mig i min karriär	1	2	3	4
	4. Oavlönat arbete ses positivt av kollegor/klienter/arbetsgivare	1	2	3	4
	5. Jag visar vänlighet och omsorg om människor jag arbetar med (t.ex. kollegor, klienter) genom oavlönat arbete	1	2	3	4
	6. Att avstå från oavlönat arbete skulle få mig att känna skuld	1	2	3	4
	7. Kollegor/klienter/arbetsgivare ser negativt på att man avstår oavlönat arbete	1	2	3	4
	8. Det kan skada min karriär om jag avstår oavlönat arbete	1	2	3	4
NL	<p>Q25_table</p> <p>Onbetaald werk zijn alle mogelijke taken die je uitvoert voor je werk, maar die niet betaald worden of buiten werktijd gedaan worden. Voor zelfstandigen zijn dit bijvoorbeeld alle taken of uren die niet zijn opgenomen in het contract met opdrachtgevers. In hoeverre bent u het eens of oneens met de volgende uitspraken?</p> <p><i>Question type: Table</i></p> <p><i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i></p> <p><i>Sub-questions:</i></p> <p>Q25A Onbetaald werk maakt deel uit van mijn baan</p> <p>Q25B Niemand anders kan de taken voor mijn baan uitvoeren behalve ik</p> <p>Q25C Onbetaald werk kan mijn carrière vooruithelpen (bijv. promotie, loonsverhoging, bonus, een betere baan vinden enz.)</p> <p>Q25D Onbetaald werk wordt positief ontvangen door collega's/klanten/werkgevers</p>				

	<p>Q25E Onbetaald werk is een teken van zorg of vriendelijkheid tegenover mensen met wie ik werk (bijv. collega's, klanten)</p> <p>Q25F Als ik geen onbetaald werk zou doen, zou ik me schuldig voelen</p> <p>Q25G Wie geen onbetaald werk doet, wordt negatief beoordeeld door collega's/klanten/werkgevers</p> <p>Q25H Als ik geen onbetaald werk zou doen, kan dat mijn carrière schaden (bijv. promotie, een betere baan vinden in de toekomst, loon, verlies van klanten)</p> <p><i>Categories:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Helemaal niet mee eens 2. Niet mee eens 3. Niet mee eens of oneens 4. Mee eens 5. Helemaal mee eens
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The questions below are different indices for variables that we hypothesise to be related to different types of unpaid work, either as a predictor or a consequence.

Q27	SQ	<p>Following questions are about how you feel about your job.</p> <p>27. For each of the following statements, please select the response which best describes your work situation.</p> <p>A. My job gives me the feeling of work well done</p> <p>B. I have the feeling of doing useful work</p> <p>C. I feel like my job is being recognized</p> <p>D. I feel appreciated in the society because of my job</p> <p>E. Considering all my efforts and achievements in my job, I feel I get paid appropriately</p> <p>F. My job offers good prospects for career advancement</p> <p>G. I might lose my job in the next 6 months</p> <p>H. If I were to lose or quit my current job, it would be easy for me to find a job of similar salary</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly disagree 2. Tend to disagree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. Tend to agree 5. Strongly agree
	UK	<p>Following questions are about how you feel about your job</p> <p>31. For each of the following statements, please select the response which best describes your work situation.</p> <p>A. My job gives me the feeling of work well done</p> <p>B. I have the feeling of doing useful work</p> <p>C. I feel like my job is being recognized</p> <p>D. I feel appreciated in the society because of my job</p> <p>E. Considering all my efforts and achievements in my job, I feel I get paid appropriately</p> <p>F. My job offers good prospects for career advancement</p> <p>G. I might lose my job in the next 6 months</p> <p>H. If I were to lose or quit my current job, it would be easy for me to find a job of similar salary</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly disagree 2. Tend to disagree

	<p>3. Neither agree nor disagree</p> <p>4. Tend to agree</p> <p>5. Strongly agree</p>																																				
FR	<p><i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i></p> <p>Les questions suivantes portent sur les émotions que vous procure votre travail.</p> <p><i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i></p> <p>QX27 Pour chacune des affirmations suivantes, veuillez sélectionner la réponse qui décrit le mieux votre situation professionnelle.</p> <p>QX27_A Mon travail me donne le sentiment du travail bien fait</p> <p>QX27_B J'ai le sentiment de faire un travail utile</p> <p>QX27_C J'ai le sentiment que mon travail est reconnu</p> <p>QX27_D Je me sens apprécié(e) dans la société grâce à mon travail</p> <p>QX27_E Je trouve que je suis bien payé(e) pour les efforts que je fournis et le travail que je fais</p> <p>QX27_F Mon travail offre de bonnes perspectives d'évolution de carrière</p> <p>QX27_G Je risque de perdre mon travail au cours des 6 prochains mois</p> <p>QX27_H Si je devais perdre ou quitter mon emploi actuel, il serait facile pour moi de trouver un emploi avec un salaire similaire</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pas du tout d'accord 2. Plutôt pas d'accord 3. Ni d'accord, ni pas d'accord 4. Plutôt d'accord 5. Tout à fait d'accord 																																				
SE	<p>q74 Följande frågor handlar om hur du känner för ditt arbete.</p> <p>q76 Välj det svar som bäst beskriver din arbetssituation för varje påstående.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Instämmer till fullo</th> <th>Instämmer till viss del</th> <th>Varken eller</th> <th>Instämmer inte</th> <th>Instämmer inte alls</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1. Mitt jobb ger mig känslan av ett väl utfört arbete</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2. Jag känner att jag utför ett viktigt arbete</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3. Jag känner att mitt arbete erkänns</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4. Jag känner mig uppskattad i samhället på grund av mitt arbete</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5. Jag känner att jag får rätt betalt med tanke på mina ansträngningar</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Instämmer till fullo	Instämmer till viss del	Varken eller	Instämmer inte	Instämmer inte alls	1. Mitt jobb ger mig känslan av ett väl utfört arbete	1	2	3	4	5	2. Jag känner att jag utför ett viktigt arbete	1	2	3	4	5	3. Jag känner att mitt arbete erkänns	1	2	3	4	5	4. Jag känner mig uppskattad i samhället på grund av mitt arbete	1	2	3	4	5	5. Jag känner att jag får rätt betalt med tanke på mina ansträngningar	1	2	3	4	5
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		och arbetsprestationer					
		6. Mitt arbete ger goda möjligheter till karriärutveckling	1	2	3	4	5
		7. Jag skulle kunna förlora mitt arbete inom de närmaste sex månaderna	1	2	3	4	5
		8. Om jag skulle förlora eller sluta på mitt nuvarande arbete skulle det vara lätt för mig att hitta ett arbete med liknande lön	1	2	3	4	5
NL	<p>We stellen u nu een aantal vragen over hoe u zich voelt bij uw [/ belangrijkste] baan. Q26_table Kies voor elk van de volgende uitspraken het antwoord dat het beste bij uw Werksituatie past. <i>Question type: Table</i> <i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i> <i>Sub-questions:</i> Q26A Mijn baan geeft me het gevoel dat ik goed werk heb verricht Q26B Ik heb het gevoel dat ik nuttig werk doe Q26C Ik heb het gevoel dat mijn baan gewaardeerd wordt Q26D Ik voel me gewaardeerd in de samenleving dankzij mijn baan Q26E Ik heb het gevoel dat ik goed betaald word voor al mijn inspanningen en prestaties in mijn baan Q26F Mijn baan biedt goede vooruitzichten voor mijn toekomstige carrière Q26G Het is mogelijk dat ik mijn baan in de komende 6 maanden verlies Q26H Als ik mijn huidige baan zou verliezen of ontslag zou nemen, kan ik gemakkelijk een baan met een vergelijkbaar salaris vinden <i>Categories:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Helemaal niet mee eens 2. Niet mee eens 3. Niet mee eens of oneens 4. Mee eens 5. Helemaal mee eens 						

Note that the Q28 originally comes from EWCS, and had to be cut down to fewer indicators due to limited space for France, Sweden and the Netherlands. For France, all four questions from the SQ are presented, and for Sweden and the Netherlands we further deleted A. We deleted the indicators from the original survey based on the results from the factor loadings from factor analysis and the repetitiveness of the indicators.

Q28	SQ	28. The following statements are about how you feel about your job. For each statement, please tell me how often you feel this way...
-----	----	---

	<p>A. At my work I feel full of energy</p> <p>B. I am enthusiastic about my job</p> <p>C. I feel physically exhausted at the end of the working day</p> <p>D. I feel emotionally drained by my work</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Always 2. Most of the time 3. Sometimes 4. Rarely 5. Never
UK	<p>32. The following statements are about how you feel about your job. For each statement, please tell me how often you feel this way...</p> <p>A. At my work I feel full of energy</p> <p>B. I am enthusiastic about my job</p> <p>C. Time flies when I am working</p> <p>D. I feel exhausted at the end of the working day</p> <p>E. I doubt the importance of my work</p> <p>F. I feel that I am good at my job</p> <p>G. I experience stress in my job</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Always 2. Most of the time 3. Sometimes 4. Rarely 5. Never
FR	<p>QX28 Les affirmations suivantes portent sur le sentiment que vous procure votre travail. Pour chaque affirmation, veuillez préciser à quelle fréquence vous avez eu ce sentiment...</p> <p>QX28_A Au travail, je me sens plein d'énergie</p> <p>QX28_B Je suis enthousiaste vis-à-vis de mon travail</p> <p>QX28_C Je me sens épuisé(e) physiquement à la fin de ma journée de travail</p> <p>QX28_D Je me sens épuisé(e) émotionnellement par mon travail</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tout le temps 2. La plupart du temps 3. Parfois 4. Rarement 5. Jamais

SE	q78 Hur ofta känner du följande för ditt arbete?					
		Alltid	Oftast	Ibland	Sällan	Aldrig
	1. Jag är entusiastisk över mitt arbete	1	2	3	4	5
	2. Jag känner mig fysiskt utmattad i slutet av arbetsdagen	1	2	3	4	5
	3. Jag känner mig känslomässigt dränerad av mitt arbete	1	2	3	4	5
NL	<p>Q27_table Kunt u aangeven hoe vaak u zich als volgt voelt in uw huidige baan?</p> <p><i>Question type: Table</i></p> <p><i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i></p> <p><i>Sub-questions:</i></p> <p>Q27A Ik ben enthousiast over mijn baan</p> <p>Q27B Ik voel me fysiek uitgeput aan het einde van de werkdag</p> <p>Q27C Ik voel me emotioneel uitgeput door mijn werk</p> <p><i>Categories:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nooit 2. Zelden 3. Soms 4. Meestal 5. Altijd 					

For Q29-31, several indicators are deleted for the SQ after factor analysis and repetitiveness of the indicators due to the limited space in the panel surveys. Note that Q30 was created for this survey based on the existing scales for stigma as mentioned in the previous section.

Q29	SQ	<p>We would like to ask you about the emotional side of your job.</p> <p>29. In your main job, how frequently do you...?</p> <p>A. Feel like you have to resist expressing your true feelings</p> <p>B. Pretend to have emotions that you don't really have</p> <p>C. Hide your true feelings about a situation</p> <p>D. Make an effort to actually feel the emotions that you need to display to others (customers/employers/colleagues)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Always 2. Most of the time 3. Sometimes 4. Rarely 5. Never
	UK	We would like to ask you about the emotional side of your job.

	<p>33. In your main job, how frequently do you...?</p> <p>A. Listen to customer/employer/colleagues' complaints</p> <p>B. Feel like you have to resist expressing your true feelings</p> <p>C. Pretend to have emotions that you don't really have</p> <p>D. Hide your true feelings about a situation</p> <p>E. Make an effort to actually feel the emotions that you need to display to others (customers/employers/colleagues)</p> <p>F. Try to actually experience the emotions that you must show</p> <p>G. Really try to feel the emotions you have to show as part of my job</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Always 2. Most of the time 3. Sometimes 4. Rarely 5. Never 																														
FR	<p><i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i></p> <p>Nous aimerions vous poser des questions sur l'aspect émotionnel de votre emploi principal.</p> <p><i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i></p> <p>QX29 Dans votre emploi principal, à quelle fréquence... ?</p> <p>QX29_A Avez-vous l'impression de devoir garder vos sentiments pour vous</p> <p>QX29_B Faites-vous semblant d'éprouver des émotions que vous n'éprouvez pas en réalité</p> <p>QX29_C Cachez-vous vos réels sentiments à propos d'une situation</p> <p>QX29_D Vous efforcez-vous de ressentir les émotions que vous pensez devoir éprouver (face aux clients/employeurs/collègues)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tout le temps 2. La plupart du temps 3. Parfois 4. Rarement 5. Jamais 																														
SE	<p>q80 Hur ofta sker följande i ditt arbete?</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Alltid</th> <th>Oftast</th> <th>Ibland</th> <th>Sällan</th> <th>Aldrig</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1. Det känns som att du måste motstå att uttrycka dina sanna känslor</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2. Du låtsas som att du har känslor som du egentligen inte har</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3. Du döljer dina sanna känslor om en situation</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4. Du försöker faktiskt känna de känslor som du behöver visa för andra (kunder/arbetsgivare/kollegor)</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Alltid	Oftast	Ibland	Sällan	Aldrig	1. Det känns som att du måste motstå att uttrycka dina sanna känslor	1	2	3	4	5	2. Du låtsas som att du har känslor som du egentligen inte har	1	2	3	4	5	3. Du döljer dina sanna känslor om en situation	1	2	3	4	5	4. Du försöker faktiskt känna de känslor som du behöver visa för andra (kunder/arbetsgivare/kollegor)	1	2	3	4	5
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NL	<p>Q28_table</p> <p>Hoe vaak komen de volgende dingen voor in uw [/ belangrijkste]baan?</p> <p><i>Question type: Table</i></p> <p><i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i></p>																														

		<p><i>Sub-questions:</i> Q28A Het gevoel hebben dat u uw ware gevoelens niet kan uiten Q28B Emoties tonen die u niet echt hebt Q28C Uw ware gevoelens over een situatie verbergen Q28D Moeite doen om de emoties te voelen die u aan anderen moet tonen (klanten/werkgevers/collega's)</p> <p><i>Categories:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nooit 2. Zelden 3. Soms 4. Meestal 5. Altijd
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Q30	SQ	<p>Following questions are about how the people who do your job feel in the society.</p> <p>30. To what extent do you agree with the following statements about how you and the people with a similar job to yours feel in the society?</p> <p>A. Other people think less of people in a similar job to mine B. People who work in a similar job to mine feel we're not as good as others C. Other people discriminate against me because of my job</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly disagree 2. Tend to disagree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. Tend to agree 5. Strongly agree
	UK	<p>Following questions are about how the people who do your job feel in the society</p> <p>34. To what extent do you agree with the following statements about how you feel in the society?</p> <p>A. People who do my job feel belong to the society B. People who do my job feel set apart, isolated from the rest of the world C. Sometimes I feel that people who do my job are being talked down to D. Other people think less of people who do my job E. People who do my job feel we're not as good as others F. I avoid telling people about my job G. I worry about people discriminating against me because of my job</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly disagree 2. Tend to disagree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. Tend to agree 5. Strongly agree
	FR	<p>Les questions suivantes portent sur le ressenti des personnes occupant un emploi similaire au vôtre, dans votre entreprise ou ailleurs.</p> <p><i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i></p> <p>QX30 Dans quelle mesure êtes-vous d'accord avec les affirmations suivantes concernant la façon dont vous vous sentez dans la société? On entend par "vous" les personnes occupant un emploi similaire au vôtre, y compris vous-même. Les "autres personnes" sont les personnes qui n'occupent pas un emploi similaire au vôtre.</p>

	<p>QX30_A Les autres personnes dénigrent les personnes occupant un emploi comme le mien.</p> <p>QX30_B Les personnes qui exercent un travail similaire au mien ont le sentiment de valoir moins que les autres personnes</p> <p>QX30_C Je subis de la discrimination à cause de mon emploi.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pas du tout d'accord 2. Plutôt pas d'accord 3. Ni d'accord, ni pas d'accord 4. Plutôt d'accord 5. Tout à fait d'accord 																								
SE	<p>q82 I vilken utsträckning instämmer du med följande påståenden?</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Instämmer till fullo</th> <th>Instämmer till viss del</th> <th>Varken eller</th> <th>Instämmer inte</th> <th>Instämmer inte alls</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1. Andra ser ner på människor med mitt typ av arbete</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2. Människor med samma typ av arbete som jag tycker generellt att vi inte är lika bra som andra</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3. Andra människor diskriminerar mig på grund av mitt arbete</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Instämmer till fullo	Instämmer till viss del	Varken eller	Instämmer inte	Instämmer inte alls	1. Andra ser ner på människor med mitt typ av arbete	1	2	3	4	5	2. Människor med samma typ av arbete som jag tycker generellt att vi inte är lika bra som andra	1	2	3	4	5	3. Andra människor diskriminerar mig på grund av mitt arbete	1	2	3	4	5
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NL	<p>Q29_table</p> <p>In hoeverre bent u het eens met de volgende uitspraken?</p> <p><i>Question type: Table</i></p> <p><i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i></p> <p><i>Sub-questions:</i></p> <p>Q29A Andere mensen kijken neer op mensen met een soortgelijke baan als de mijne</p> <p>Q29B Mensen met een soortgelijke baan als ik vinden dat we niet zo goed zijn als anderen</p> <p>Q29C Andere mensen discrimineren mij vanwege mijn baan</p> <p><i>Categories:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Helemaal niet mee eens 2. Niet mee eens 3. Niet mee eens of oneens 4. Mee eens 5. Helemaal mee eens 																								

Q31	SQ	Following questions are about how you've felt during the past week.				
		31. How much of the time during the past week...				
			None or almost none of the time	Some of the time	Most of the time	All or almost all of the time
	A	...you felt that everything you did was an effort?	1	2	3	4
	B	...you felt lonely?	1	2	3	4
	C	...you felt sad?	1	2	3	4
	D	...you could not get going?	1	2	3	4
UK		Following questions are about how you've felt during the past week.				
		35. How much of the time during the past week...				
			None or almost none of the time	Some of the time	Most of the time	All or almost all of the time
	A	...you felt depressed?	1	2	3	4
	B	...you felt that everything you did was an effort?	1	2	3	4
	C	...your sleep was restless?	1	2	3	4
	D	...you were happy?	1	2	3	4
	E	...you felt lonely?	1	2	3	4
	F	...you enjoyed life?	1	2	3	4
	G	...you felt sad?	1	2	3	4
	H	...you could not get going?	1	2	3	4
FR		Les questions suivantes portent sur ce que vous avez ressenti au cours de la semaine écoulée.				
		Q31 Vous est-il arrivé la semaine dernière...				
		Q31_A ...d'avoir l'impression que tout vous demandait un effort ?				
		Q31_B ...de vous sentir seul(e) ?				
		Q31_C ...de vous sentir triste ?				
	Q31_D ...de ne rien être capable de faire ?					
		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. À aucun moment ou presque 2. De temps en temps 3. La plupart du temps 4. Tout le temps ou presque 				
SE		q84 Hur stor del av tiden under den senaste veckan ...?				
			Hela eller nästan hela tiden	För det mesta av tiden	En del av tiden	Ingen eller nästan ingen del av tiden
		1. ... kände du att allt du gjorde var en ansträngning	1	2	3	4
		2. ... kände du dig ensam	1	2	3	4
	3. ... kände du dig ledsen	1	2	3	4	

		4. ... kunde du inte sätta igång med arbetet	1	2	3	4
NL	<p>Q30_table Hoe vaak hebt u de afgelopen week... <i>Question type: Table</i> <i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i> <i>Sub-questions:</i> Q30A ...het gevoel gehad dat alles veel moeite kost? Q30B ...zich eenzaam gevoeld? Q30C ...zich verdrietig gevoeld? Q30D ...het gevoel gehad dat u maar niet op gang kwam? <i>Categories:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Niet of bijna niet 2. Soms 3. Meestal 4. Altijd of bijna altijd 					

Questions 32-34 are about the unpaid labour outside of paid jobs. Although the focus of the survey is on the unpaid labour within paid job, we have incorporated these questions to have a full grasp of different types of unpaid labour, and to examine how the two are related. Due to limited space for the Swedish panel, we have deleted the questions 32-34.

Q32	SQ	<p>Following questions are about the hours you work outside of your paid job.</p> <p><i>OE NUM – 0-100</i></p> <p>32. On average, how many hours per week do you spend on Job searching/application for the next job?</p>
	UK	<p>Following questions are about the hours you work outside of your paid job.</p> <p><i>OE NUM – 0-100</i></p> <p>36. On average, how many hours per week do you spend on Job searching/application outside of your paid job?</p>
	FR	<p>Les questions suivantes portent sur vos heures en dehors de votre emploi rémunéré.</p> <p>Q32 En moyenne, combien d’heures par semaine consacrez-vous à la recherche d’un emploi/à postuler à un futur emploi ? (Veuillez saisir un chiffre entier sans décimale et sans autre caractère - lettre, espace, ponctuation) Répondre 0 si vous n’y consacrer pas d’heure ou n’êtes pas concerné(e).</p> <p><i>[Champ numérique] heure(s)/semaine</i></p>
	SE	Deleted for LORE
	NL	<p>De volgende vragen gaan over de uren die u buiten uw betaalde baan besteed.</p> <p>Q31 Hoeveel uren per week besteedt u gemiddeld aan het zoeken naar werk/solliciteren voor de volgende baan? Als u niet op zoek bent naar werk/solliciteert, vul dan 0 in. <i>Answer type: Integer</i> <i>Min: 0</i></p>

		<i>Max: 168</i> <i>Label-right: uren per week</i>
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Q33	SQ	33. On average, how many hours per week do you spend on job preparation/practice/training outside of your main paid job or to get a paid job?
	UK	<i>OE NUM – 0-100</i> 37. On average, how many hours per week do you spend on job preparation/practice/training outside of your main paid job or to get a paid job?
	FR	Q33 En moyenne, combien d’heures par semaine consacrez-vous à la préparation/à l’entraînement/à la formation à l’emploi en dehors de votre emploi principal rémunéré ou pour décrocher un emploi rémunéré ? (Veuillez saisir un chiffre entier sans décimale et sans autre caractère - lettre, espace, ponctuation) Répondre 0 si vous n’y consacrer pas d’heure ou n’êtes pas concerné(e). <i>[Champ numérique] heure(s)/semaine</i>
	SE	Deleted for LORE
	NL	Q32 Hoeveel uur besteedt u gemiddeld per week aan voorbereiding, oefening of training naast uw betaalde [/ belangrijkste]baan of om een betaalde baan te krijgen? <i>Answer type: Integer</i> <i>Min: 0</i> <i>Max: 168</i> <i>Label-right: uren per week</i>

Q34	SQ	34. On average, how many hours per week do you spend on Volunteer or charitable activity (such as union activities or community engagement) outside of your paid job?
	UK	<i>OE NUM – 0-100</i> 38. On average, how many hours per week do you spend on Volunteer or charitable activity (such as union activities or community engagement) outside of your paid job?
	FR	Q34 En moyenne, combien d’heures par semaine consacrez-vous à des activités bénévoles ou caritatives (comme des activités syndicales ou un engagement communautaire) en dehors de votre emploi rémunéré ? (Veuillez saisir un chiffre entier sans décimale et sans autre caractère - lettre, espace, ponctuation) Répondre 0 si vous n’y consacrer pas d’heure ou n’êtes pas concerné(e). <i>[Champ numérique] heure(s)/semaine</i>
	SE	Deleted for LORE
	NL	Q33 Hoeveel uren per week besteedt u gemiddeld aan vrijwilligerswerk of liefdadigheidsactiviteiten (zoals vakbondsactiviteiten of gemeenschapswerk) naast uw betaalde baan? <i>Answer type: Integer</i> <i>Min: 0</i> <i>Max: 168</i> <i>Label-right: uren per week</i>

Questions 35-36 are about working at asocial hours. Q35 is from EWCS, and was reduced by merging ‘Sundays’ and ‘Saturdays’ to ‘Weekends’ to reduce the number of questions. Due to limited space, we deleted Q36 for both France and Sweden.

Q35	SQ	<p>Now we would like to go back to your main job and ask you about your working hours.</p> <p>35. Normally in your main job, how many times a month do you work...? Answer in numbers</p> <p>At night, for at least 2 hours between 10pm-5am <i>OE NUM – 0-31</i> On Weekends? <i>OE NUM – 0-5</i> More than 10 hours a day? <i>OE NUM – 0-31</i></p>								
	UK	<p>Now we would like to go back to your main job and ask you about your working hours</p> <p>39. Normally in your main job, how many times a month do you work...?</p> <p>A. At night, for at least 2 hours between 10pm-5am <i>OE NUM – 0-31</i> B. On Sundays? <i>OE NUM – 0-5</i> C. On Saturdays? <i>OE NUM – 0-5</i> D. More than 10 hours a day? <i>OE NUM – 0-31</i></p>								
	FR	<p>Nous aimerions à présent revenir sur votre emploi principal et vous poser des questions sur vos heures de travail.</p> <p><i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i></p> <p>QX35A Habituellement, dans votre emploi principal, combien de fois par mois travaillez-vous... ? (Veuillez saisir un chiffre entier sans décimale et sans autre caractère - lettre, espace, ponctuation) - De nuit, pendant au moins 2 heures entre 22 h et 5 h du matin <i>[Champ numérique] nuit(s)/mois</i></p> <p><i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i></p> <p>QX35B Habituellement, dans votre emploi principal, combien de fois par mois travaillez-vous... ? (Veuillez saisir un chiffre entier sans décimale et sans autre caractère - lettre, espace, ponctuation) - Le week-end <i>[Champ numérique] week-end(s)/mois</i></p> <p><i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i></p> <p>QX35C Habituellement, dans votre emploi principal, combien de fois par mois travaillez-vous... ? (Veuillez saisir un chiffre entier sans décimale et sans autre caractère - lettre, espace, ponctuation) - Plus de 10 heures par jour <i>[Champ numérique] jour(s)/mois</i></p>								
	SE	<p>q48 Hur många gånger i månaden arbetar du följande arbetstider? Svara i siffror.</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="347 1731 1388 1917"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="347 1731 868 1771"></th> <th data-bbox="873 1731 1388 1771">Antal gånger</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="347 1778 868 1843">1. På natten, i minst 2 timmar mellan 22.00–05.00</td> <td data-bbox="873 1778 1388 1843"></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="347 1850 868 1883">2. På helgen</td> <td data-bbox="873 1850 1388 1883"></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="347 1890 868 1917">3. Mer än 10 timmar om dagen</td> <td data-bbox="873 1890 1388 1917"></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Antal gånger	1. På natten, i minst 2 timmar mellan 22.00–05.00		2. På helgen		3. Mer än 10 timmar om dagen	
	Antal gånger									
1. På natten, i minst 2 timmar mellan 22.00–05.00										
2. På helgen										
3. Mer än 10 timmar om dagen										
	NL	<p>We stellen u nu een aantal vragen over uw werkuren in uw [/ belangrijkste] baan.</p>								

		<p>Q34_table</p> <p>Hoeveel keer per maand werkt u bij uw belangrijkste baan...</p> <p>Vul hier een geheel getal in. Als iets nooit voorkomt, vul dan 0 in.</p> <p><i>Question type: Table</i></p> <p><i>Answer type: Integer</i></p> <p><i>Min: 0</i></p> <p><i>Max: 31</i></p> <p><i>Label-right: keer</i></p> <p><i>Sub-questions:</i></p> <p>Q34A ...minstens 2 uur 's nachts tussen 22 uur en 5 uur?</p> <p>Q34B ...in het weekend?</p> <p>Q34C ...meer dan 10 uur per dag?</p>
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Q36	SQ	<p>36. In the last month in your main job, has it happened at least once that you had less than 11 hours between the end of one working day and the start of the next working day?</p> <p>1. Yes</p> <p>2. No</p>
	UK	<p>40. In the last month in your main job, has it happened at least once that you had less than 11 hours between the end of one working day and the start of the next working day?</p> <p>1. Yes</p> <p>2. No</p>
	FR	Deleted for ELIPSS
	SE	Deleted for LORE
	NL	<p>Q35 Is het in de afgelopen maand voorgekomen dat u minder dan 11 uur rust hebt gehad tussen het einde van de werkdag en het begin van de volgende?</p> <p><i>Categories:</i></p> <p>1. Nee</p> <p>2. Ja</p>

Questions 37 and 38 regularity of work. Q37 was reduced to have one question "C" for limited space in France and Sweden. For Sweden, and Q38 was deleted for the same reason.

Q37	SQ	37. In your main job, do you work...?		
			Yes	No
		A. The same number of hours every day	1	2
		B. The same number of days every week	1	2
		C. The same number of hours every week	1	2
		D. Fixed starting and finishing times	1	2
		E. Shifts	1	2
	UK	41. In your main job, do you work...?		
			Yes	No
		A. The same number of hours every day	1	2
		B. The same number of days every week	1	2
C. The same number of hours every week		1	2	
	D. Fixed starting and finishing times	1	2	
	E. Shifts	1	2	
FR	<i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i>			

		<p>QX37 Dans votre emploi principal, travaillez-vous le même nombre d'heures chaque semaine ?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Oui 2. Non
	SE	<p>q41 Arbetar du samma antal timmar varje vecka?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ja 2. Nej
	NL	<p>Q36_table Werkt u in uw [/ belangrijkste]baan... <i>Question type: Table</i> <i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i> <i>Sub-questions:</i> Q36A elke dag evenveel uren? Q36B elke week evenveel dagen? Q36C elke week evenveel uren? Q36D met vaste begin- en eindtijden? Q36E in ploegen(dienst)? <i>Categories:</i> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nee 2. Ja </p>

Q38	SQ	<p>38. In your main job, do changes to your working time arrangements occur regularly? (if yes,) how long before are you informed about these changes?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No 2. Yes, the same day 3. Yes, the day before 4. Yes, several days in advance 5. Yes, several weeks in advance
	UK	<p>42. In your main job, do changes to your working time arrangements occur regularly? (if yes,) how long before are you informed about these changes?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No 2. Yes, the same day 3. Yes, the day before 4. Yes, several days in advance 5. Yes, several weeks in advance
	FR	<p><i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i> QX38 Dans votre emploi principal, y a-t-il régulièrement des changements dans vos horaires? Si oui, combien de temps à l'avance êtes-vous informé(e) de ces changements?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Non, il n'y a pas de changement 2. Oui, et je suis informé(e) le jour même 3. Oui, et je suis informé(e) la veille 4. Oui, et je suis informé(e) plusieurs jours à l'avance 5. Oui, et je suis informé(e) plusieurs semaines à l'avance
	SE	Deleted for LORE
	NL	<p>Q37 Worden uw werktijden in uw [/ belangrijkste]baan regelmatig gewijzigd? Zo ja, hoelang van tevoren wordt u daarvan op de hoogte gebracht?</p>

		<p><i>Categories:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nee 2. Ja, dezelfde dag 3. Ja, een dag van tevoren 4. Ja, meerdere dagen van tevoren 5. Ja, enkele weken van tevoren
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Q39 and Q41 have to do with control or autonomy over one's work. Q39 is related to temporal and spatial autonomy and Q41 is related to the autonomy over how work is done. Due to the limited space in the survey, we have merged the two questions and kept the core questions.

Q39	SQ	<p><i>Following questions are about the flexibility and control you have in your main job.</i></p> <p>In your main job, can you decide...</p> <p>A. The number of working hours?</p> <p>B. Where you work?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not at all 2. Rarely 3. Some of the time 4. Most of the time 5. All the time
	UK	<p><i>Following questions are about the flexibility and control you have in your main job</i></p> <p>43. In your main job, can you decide the starting time of work?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No <p>44. In your main job, can you decide the working hours?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No <p>46. In your main job, can you decide where you work?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No
	FR	<p><i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i></p> <p>Les questions suivantes portent sur la flexibilité et le contrôle dont vous disposez dans votre emploi principal.</p> <p><i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i></p> <p>QX39 Dans votre emploi principal, pouvez-vous décider... ?</p> <p>QX39_A Du nombre d'heures de travail</p> <p>QX39_B Du lieu où vous travaillez</p> <p>QX39_C De l'ordre de vos tâches</p> <p>QX39_D De vos méthodes de travail</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Jamais 2. Rarement 3. Parfois 4. La plupart du temps 5. Tout le temps

SE	<p>q86 Följande frågor handlar om den flexibilitet och kontroll du har i ditt arbete.</p> <p>q88 I vilken utsträckning kan du bestämma följande i ditt arbete?</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Alltid</th> <th>Ofta</th> <th>Ibland</th> <th>Sällan</th> <th>Inte alls</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1. Antalet arbetstimmar</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2. Var du arbetar</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3. Den ordning i vilken du utför arbetsuppgifter</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4. Dina arbetsmetoder</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Alltid	Ofta	Ibland	Sällan	Inte alls	1. Antalet arbetstimmar	1	2	3	4	5	2. Var du arbetar	1	2	3	4	5	3. Den ordning i vilken du utför arbetsuppgifter	1	2	3	4	5	4. Dina arbetsmetoder	1	2	3	4	5
	Alltid	Ofta	Ibland	Sällan	Inte alls																										
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NL	<p>De volgende vragen gaan over de flexibiliteit en controle die u hebt in uw [/ belangrijkste] baan.</p> <p>Q38_table Kunt u in uw [/ belangrijkste] baan het onderstaande zelf bepalen? <i>Question type: Table</i> <i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i> <i>Sub-questions:</i> Q38A De volgorde van uw taken Q38B Uw werkwijze Q38C Het aantal werkuren Q38D Op welke plek u werkt <i>Categories:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Helemaal niet 2. Zelden 3. Soms 4. Meestal 5. Altijd 																														

Q41	SQ	41. In your main job, are you able to choose or change...	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Not at all</th> <th>Rarely</th> <th>Some of the time</th> <th>Most of the time</th> <th>All the time</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>A. Your order of tasks</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>B. Your methods of work</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>C. Your speed or rate of work</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>						Not at all	Rarely	Some of the time	Most of the time	All the time	A. Your order of tasks	1	2	3	4	5	B. Your methods of work	1	2	3	4	5	C. Your speed or rate of work	1	2	3	4	5
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	C. Your speed or rate of work	1	2	3	4	5																									
UK	47. In your main job, are you able to choose or change...	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Yes</th> <th>No</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>D. Your order of tasks</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>E. Your methods of work</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>F. Your speed or rate of work</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>					Yes	No	D. Your order of tasks	1	2	E. Your methods of work	1	2	F. Your speed or rate of work	1	2														
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FR	See number QX39																														
SE	See number q88																														
NL	See number Q38																														

Question 40 is derived from the Eurobarometer survey. We have adapted the question for the SQ after consulting with the ILO and Eurofound.

Q40	SQ	<p>40. Flexible work arrangement includes flexible working, flexitime (adapted beginning and finishing working times), working from home (telework). To your knowledge, are there flexible work arrangements in the company or organisation in your main job?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes, and I currently use or have used such arrangements personally 2. Yes, but I have never used such arrangements personally 3. No, there are no flexible work arrangements available in the company or organization where I currently work
	UK	<p>45. To your knowledge, are there flexible work arrangements in the company or organisation in your main job? (flexible work arrangement include part-time, flexitime (adapted beginning and finishing working times), working from home (telework) or being able to take some time off for private emergencies (medical issues, a sick child, etc.))</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes, and I currently use or have used such arrangements personally 2. Yes, but I have never used such arrangements personally 3. No, there are no flexible work arrangements available in the company or organization where I currently work
	FR	<p>QX40</p> <p>Les formules de travail flexibles incluent le temps partiel, le flexitime (horaire de début et de fin de journée de travail adaptés), le travail à domicile (télétravail) ou le fait de pouvoir prendre des congés pour les urgences privées (problèmes médicaux, enfant malade, etc.).</p> <p>Parlons à présent de votre situation professionnelle personnelle.</p> <p>À votre connaissance, existe-t-il des formules de travail flexibles dans l'entreprise ou la structure dans laquelle vous travaillez actuellement ?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Oui, et vous utilisez actuellement ou avez utilisé personnellement de telles formules 2. Non, il n'existe aucune formule de travail flexible dans l'entreprise ou la structure 3. dans laquelle vous travaillez actuellement
	SE	<p>q90 Finns det, såvitt du vet, flexibla arbetsformer i det företag eller den organisation där du arbetar?</p> <p>Flexibla arbetsformer omfattar flexibelt arbete, flexitid (anpassade tider för när arbetet börjar och slutar) och arbete hemifrån (distansarbete).</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ja, och jag använder/har använt flexibla arbetsformer personligen 2. Ja, men jag har aldrig använt flexibla arbetsformer personligen 3. Nej, flexibla arbetsformer finns inte tillgängligt där jag arbetar
	NL	<p>Q39 Sommige banen hebben flexibele werkregelingen. Voorbeelden van flexibele werkregelingen zijn flexibel werk, het aanpassen van begin- en eindtijden en/of thuiswerken. Heeft het bedrijf of de organisatie van uw [/ belangrijkste] baan flexibele werkregelingen naar u weten?</p> <p><i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i></p> <p><i>Categories:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ja, en ik gebruik zo'n regeling op dit moment zelf of heb ze zelf gebruikt 2. Ja, maar ik heb zo'n regeling nog nooit zelf gebruikt

		3. Nee, er zijn geen flexibele werkregelingen beschikbaar in het bedrijf of de organisatie waar ik momenteel werk
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Q42 is about the existence of trade unions or equivalent works council. We have deleted the questions on the name and the membership after the pilot survey due to ethical regulations in the panels. The items was deleted in French panel.

Q42	SQ	Following questions are about trade unions at your workplace. 42. Is there a trade union, works council or a similar committee representing the employees at your workplace? 1. Yes 2. No
	UK	Following questions are about trade unions at your workplace 48. Is there a trade union, works council or a similar committee representing the employees at your workplace? 1. Yes 2. No <i>ASK ONLY IF Q48=1</i> 49. What is the name of the trade union at your workplace? <i>ASK ONLY IF Q48=1</i> 50. Are you a member of the trade union? 1. Yes 2. No
	FR	Deleted for ELIPSS
	SE	q92 Finns det ett fackförbund, företagsråd eller liknande kommitté som representerar de anställda på din arbetsplats? 1. Ja 2. Nej 3. Vet ej
	NL	We stellen u nu nog een paar algemene vragen over uw [/ belangrijkste] baan, en het evenwicht tussen uw werk en privé. Q40 Is er een vakbond, ondernemingsraad of een vergelijkbare organisatie of orgaan dat de werknemers op uw werkplek vertegenwoordigt? <i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i> <i>Categories:</i> 1. Nee 2. Ja

Q43-45 was again about the unpaid labour outside of paid job but specifically focusing on the household and care labour. Due to the limited space and the fact that there is a question on work-life balance Q45, both Q43 and 44 were deleted for the panel surveys in France, Sweden and the Netherlands.

Q43	SQ	Now we would like to ask you about how you balance between your work and family.
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		<p><i>OE NUM PER ROW – 0-100</i></p> <p>43. On average, how many hours per week do you spend for the following activities outside work? <i>Answer in numbers</i></p> <p>A. household tasks B. caring for children/grandchildren C. caring for elderly/disabled relatives</p>
	UK	<p>Now we would like to ask you about how you balance between your work and family</p> <p><i>OE NUM PER ROW – 0-100</i></p> <p>51. On average, how many hours per week do you spend for the following activities outside work?</p> <p>A. household chores B. caring for children/grandchildren C. caring for elderly/disabled relatives</p>
	FR	Deleted
	SE	Deleted
	NL	Deleted

Q44	SQ	<p>44. In general, how do your working hours fit in with your family or social commitments outside work?</p> <p>1. Very well 2. Well 3. Not very well 4. Not at all well</p>
	UK	<p>52. In general, how do your working hours fit in with your family or social commitments outside work?</p> <p>1. Very well 2. Well 3. Not very well 4. Not at all well</p>
	FR	Deleted
	SE	Deleted
	NL	Deleted

Q45	SQ	<p>45. How often in the last 12 months (or since you started working), have you...?</p> <p>A. Kept worrying about work when you were not working B. Felt too tired after work to do some of the household jobs which need to be done C. Found that your job prevented you from giving the time you wanted to your family D. Found it difficult to concentrate on your job because of your family responsibilities E. Found that your family responsibilities prevented you from giving the time you should to your job</p> <p>1. Always 2. Most of the time 3. Sometimes 4. Rarely 5. Never</p>
	UK	<p>53. How often in the last 12 months (or since you started working), have you...?</p> <p>A. Kept worrying about work when you were not working B. Felt too tired after work to do some of the household jobs which need to be done C. Found that your job prevented you from giving the time you wanted to your family D. Found it difficult to concentrate on your job because of your family responsibilities</p>

	<p>E. Found that your family responsibilities prevented you from giving the time you should to your job</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Always 2. Most of the time 3. Sometimes 4. Rarely 5. Never 																																			
FR	<p><i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i> Nous aimerions à présent vous demander comment vous conciliez vie professionnelle et vie privée. <i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i> QX45 Au cours des 12 derniers mois, à quelle fréquence... ? QX45_A Vous vous êtes préoccupé(e) des questions liées au travail alors que vous ne travailliez pas QX45_B Vous vous êtes senti(e) fatigué(e) après le travail pour accomplir certaines tâches ménagères nécessaires QX45_C Vous avez trouvé que votre travail vous empêchait de consacrer le temps voulu à votre famille QX45_D Vous avez trouvé difficile de vous concentrer sur votre travail à cause de vos responsabilités familiales QX45_E Vous avez trouvé que vos responsabilités familiales vous empêchaient de consacrer du temps à votre travail</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tout le temps 2. La plupart du temps 3. Parfois 4. Rarement 5. Jamais 																																			
SE	<p>q94 Hur ofta under de senaste 12 månaderna (eller sedan du började arbeta) har du upplevt följande?</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Alltid</th> <th>Ofta</th> <th>Ibland</th> <th>Sällan</th> <th>Aldrig</th> <th><i>Ej tillämpligt</i></th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1. Fortsatt att oroa dig för arbetet utanför arbetstid</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> <td>6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2. Känt dig för trött efter arbetet för att göra några av de hushållssysslor som måste göras</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> <td>6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3. Känt att ditt arbete hindrar dig från att ge den tid du vill till din familj</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> <td>6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4. Haft svårt att</td> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> <td>6</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Alltid	Ofta	Ibland	Sällan	Aldrig	<i>Ej tillämpligt</i>	1. Fortsatt att oroa dig för arbetet utanför arbetstid	1	2	3	4	5	6	2. Känt dig för trött efter arbetet för att göra några av de hushållssysslor som måste göras	1	2	3	4	5	6	3. Känt att ditt arbete hindrar dig från att ge den tid du vill till din familj	1	2	3	4	5	6	4. Haft svårt att	1	2	3	4	5	6
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		koncentrera dig på arbetet på grund av ansvar för familjen						
		5. Kämt att ditt ansvar för familj hindrat dig från att ge ditt arbete den tid du borde	1	2	3	4	5	6
NL	<p>Q41_table</p> <p>Hoe vaak is in de afgelopen 12 maanden het volgende voorgekomen? Als u minder dan 12 maanden geleden bent begonnen met werken, vul dan de vraag in over de periode sinds dat u gestart bent met werken</p> <p><i>Question type: Table</i></p> <p><i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i></p> <p><i>Sub-questions:</i></p> <p>Q41A U blijft piekeren over het werk terwijl u niet aan het werken bent</p> <p>Q41B U voelt zich te moe na het werk om een aantal van de huishoudelijke taken te doen die gedaan moesten worden</p> <p>Q41C U hebt gevoel dat u door uw werk niet genoeg tijd kan besteden aan uw gezin zoals u zou willen</p> <p>Q41D U vindt het moeilijk om u op uw werk te concentreren door familieverplichtingen</p> <p>Q41E U komt tot de conclusie dat uw familieverplichtingen u verhinderden om genoeg tijd te maken voor uw werk</p> <p>Categories:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nooit 2. Zelden 3. Soms 4. Meestal 5. Altijd -1. Niet van toepassing 							

Q46-50 are on social protection. Few questions were on actual social protection and some on their perception with regards to the possibility of making ends meet in case of risks, such as unemployment, retirement, child birth, and sickness. Some questions were deleted as they can be inferred from their employment status, or were deleted due to limited space.

Q46-50	SQ	<p>Following questions are about social protection.</p> <p>46. Over the past 12 months (or since you started working), did you work when you were sick?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No <p>47. In case of your illness or injury, do you think you can keep your main job?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No
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	<p>3. Don't know</p> <p>48. In case of your illness, do you think your household can make ends meet?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No 3. Don't know <p>49. If you lost your job, do you think your household can make ends meet?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No 3. Don't know <p>50. In case of having a child now, do you think you can continue working for your main job after the child is born?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No 3. Don't know
UK	<p>Following questions are about social protection.</p> <p>54. In case of illness or injury, do you think you can keep your main job?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No <p>55. In case of illness, do you think your household can make ends meet?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No <p>56. Over the past 12 months (or since you started working), did you work when you were sick?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No <p>57. In case of unemployment, do you think your household can make ends meet?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No <p>58. When you retire, do you think your household can make ends meet?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No <p>59. From your main job, are you entitled to maternity/paternity leave?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No <p>60. In case of having a child now, do you think you can keep your main job?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No <p>61. In case of having a child now, do you think your household can make ends meet?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes

		2. No
	FR	<p>Q49 En cas de maladie, pensez-vous que votre ménage puisse joindre les deux bouts ?</p> <p>1. Oui 2. Non</p> <p><i>Si Groupe A</i></p> <p>QA50 En cas de perte d'emploi, pensez-vous que votre ménage puisse joindre les deux bouts ?</p> <p>1. Oui 2. Non</p>
	SE	Deleted for LORE
	NL	Deleted for LISS

Question 51 is on health or safety risk from work, which is adopted from the EWCS. We have deleted the question on the positive/negative affect (Q63 for UK) after the pilot survey to reduce the survey length.

Q51	SQ	<p><i>Now going back to your main job, we would like to ask you about the safety at your workplace.</i></p> <p>51. In your main job, do you think your health or safety is at risk because of your work?</p> <p>1. Yes 2. No</p>
	UK	<p>Now going back to your main job, we would like to ask you about the safety at your workplace</p> <p>62. In your main job, do you think your health or safety is at risk because of your work?</p> <p>1. Yes 2. No</p> <p>63. In your main job, does your work affect your health?</p> <p>1. Yes, mainly positively 2. Yes, mainly negatively 3. No</p>
	FR	<p><i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i></p> <p>QX52 Dans votre emploi principal, pensez-vous courir un risque pour votre santé ou votre sécurité à cause de votre travail?</p> <p>1. Oui 2. Non</p>
	SE	<p>q96 Tror du att din hälsa eller säkerhet är i fara på grund av ditt arbete?</p> <p>1. Ja 2. Nej</p>
	NL	<p>Q42 Denkt u dat er in uw [/ belangrijkste]baan een risico is voor uw gezondheid of veiligheid?</p> <p><i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i></p>

		<p><i>Categories:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nee 2. Ja
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Questions 52-53 are asking the individual net income from the respondents' main job. We have first drafted the questionnaire to have the income scale for weekly, monthly and annual so that the respondents can select the one that they can remember the best. However, due to its complexity, we have decided to delete Q52 and adjust Q53 to meet the standards of each country after consulting with the panels. The income scale used in Q65 for the pilot survey was in combination of EWCS and ESS. However, due to its limited comparability, we have used the deciles from the ESS for France and Sweden. Monthly income is used for both after consulting with the experts from the panel. In the Netherlands, the LISS already contains a measure of individual monthly income. To this we added a measure of yearly income from the respondent's main job based on consultation with the panel experts in each country.

Q52-53	SQ	<p>Now we would like to ask you about your income.</p> <p>52. Thinking about your usual pay in your main job, which one do you know best?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Weekly pay 2. Monthly pay 3. Annual pay <p>53. Please can you tell us what is your average weekly/monthly/annual net pay after tax and compulsory deductions from your main job? If you don't know the exact figure, please give an estimate.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Weekly <i>SHOW IF Q52=1</i></th> <th>Monthly <i>SHOW IF Q52=2</i></th> <th>Yearly <i>SHOW IF Q52=3</i></th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1)</td> <td>Less than £100</td> <td>Less than £400</td> <td>Less than £4800</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2)</td> <td>£101-£150</td> <td>£401-£600</td> <td>£4801-£7200</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3)</td> <td>£151-£200</td> <td>£601-£800</td> <td>£7201-£9600</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4)</td> <td>£201-£250</td> <td>£801-£1000</td> <td>£9601-£12000</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5)</td> <td>£251-£300</td> <td>£1001-£1200</td> <td>£12001-£14400</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6)</td> <td>£301-£375</td> <td>£1201-£1500</td> <td>£14401-£18000</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7)</td> <td>£376-£450</td> <td>£1501-£1800</td> <td>£18001-£21600</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8)</td> <td>£451-£525</td> <td>£1801-£2100</td> <td>£21601-£25200</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9)</td> <td>£526-£625</td> <td>£2101-£2500</td> <td>£25201-£30000</td> </tr> <tr> <td>10)</td> <td>£626-£750</td> <td>£2501-£3000</td> <td>£30001-£36000</td> </tr> <tr> <td>11)</td> <td>£751-£875</td> <td>£3001-£3500</td> <td>£36001-£42000</td> </tr> <tr> <td>12)</td> <td>More than £876</td> <td>More than £3501</td> <td>More than £42001</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Weekly <i>SHOW IF Q52=1</i>	Monthly <i>SHOW IF Q52=2</i>	Yearly <i>SHOW IF Q52=3</i>	1)	Less than £100	Less than £400	Less than £4800	2)	£101-£150	£401-£600	£4801-£7200	3)	£151-£200	£601-£800	£7201-£9600	4)	£201-£250	£801-£1000	£9601-£12000	5)	£251-£300	£1001-£1200	£12001-£14400	6)	£301-£375	£1201-£1500	£14401-£18000	7)	£376-£450	£1501-£1800	£18001-£21600	8)	£451-£525	£1801-£2100	£21601-£25200	9)	£526-£625	£2101-£2500	£25201-£30000	10)	£626-£750	£2501-£3000	£30001-£36000	11)	£751-£875	£3001-£3500	£36001-£42000	12)	More than £876	More than £3501	More than £42001
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FR	<p>Enfin, nous aimerions vous poser quelques questions sur vos revenus.</p> <p><i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i></p> <p>QX54 Pourriez-vous nous donner votre salaire mensuel net de votre emploi principal avant prélèvement à la source ?</p> <p>Si vous ne connaissez pas le chiffre exact, veuillez donner une estimation.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Moins de 1 150 € 2. De 1 150 € à 1 600 € 3. De 1 601 € à 1 900 € 4. De 1 901 € à 2 250 € 5. De 2 251 € à 2 650 € 6. De 2 651 € à 3 150 € 7. De 3 151 € à 3 750 € 8. De 3 751 € à 4 500 € 9. De 4 501 € à 5 750 € 10. Plus de 5 750 € 																																																				
SE	<p>q98 Nu följer några avslutande bakgrundsfrågor om bland annat din inkomst.</p> <p>q100 Vad är din <i>egen</i> genomsnittliga lön per månad <i>efter</i> skatt och obligatoriska avdrag från ditt arbete?</p> <p>Om du inte vet den exakta siffran, ge en uppskattning.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Upp till 12 999 2. 13 000 - 15 999 3. 16 000 - 21 999 4. 22 000 - 25 999 5. 26 000 - 30 999 6. 31 000 - 38 999 7. 39 000 - 46 999 8. 47 000 - 56 999 9. 57 000 - 71 999 10. 72 000 eller mer 11. Vet ej /vill ej ange 																																																				
NL	<p>Q43 Kunt u ons vertellen wat u per jaar verdient, na aftrek van belastingen en andere inhoudingen met uw [/ belangrijkste] baan?</p>																																																				

		<p>Als u het niet precies weet, mag u een schatting maken.</p> <p><i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i></p> <p><i>Categories:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Minder dan €15.000 2. €15.001 tot €20.000 3. €20.001 tot €25.000 4. €25.001 tot €29.000 5. €29.001 tot €35.000 6. €35.001 tot €42.000 7. €42.001 tot €50.000 8. €50.001 tot €59.000 9. €59.001 tot €74.000 10. €74.001 of meer <ol style="list-style-type: none"> -1. Weet ik niet -2. Wil ik niet zeggen
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Q54 asks about the stability of the income. The question was revised after the pilot survey to enhance comprehensibility for the respondents. For France, “tell” has been translated to “predict”.

Q54	SQ	<p>54. Can you tell in advance how much you are going to earn (in your main job) in the next 3 months?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes, quite accurately 2. Yes, but approximately 3. No
	UK	<p>66. Would you say your income from your main job is stable?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Stable 2. Relatively stable 3. Relatively unstable 4. Unstable
	FR	<p>Q55 Pouvez-vous prévoir à l’avance combien vous allez gagner (dans votre emploi principal) au cours des 3 prochains mois ?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Oui, assez précisément 2. Oui, mais approximativement 3. Non
	SE	<p>q102 Kan du i förväg förutsäga hur mycket du kommer att tjäna i ditt arbete under de kommande 3 månaderna?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ja, ganska exakt 2. Ja, ungefär 3. Nej
	NL	<p>Q44 Weet u van tevoren hoeveel u gaat verdienen de komende 3 maanden [/ met uw belangrijkste baan] ?</p> <p><i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i></p> <p><i>Categories:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nee 2. Ja, maar niet precies 3. Ja, redelijk precies

Q55-57 ask about the household income. Q55 asks if the respondents are the breadwinner of the household based on the old EWCS survey. Q56 asks about the net household income which is based

on ESS. They are the same figures as the individual pay for France and Sweden, which needs to be taken into account. In the Netherlands, the LISS survey already provides a measure of the household income. Q57 asks about the subjective perception of their household income – whether or not they think they are able to make ends meet.

Q55	SQ	55. Are you, in your household, the person who contributes the most to the household income? 1. Yes 2. No
	UK	67. Are you, in your household, the person who contributes the most to the household income? 1. Yes 2. No
	FR	Q56 Êtes-vous, dans votre foyer, la personne qui contribue le plus au revenu du ménage? 1. Oui 2. Non
	SE	q106 Är du den person i ditt hushåll som bidrar mest till hushållets inkomster? 1. Ja 2. Nej
	NL	Q45 Bent u degene die het meeste bijdraagt aan het inkomen van uw huishouden? Als u een eenpersoonshuishouden hebt, kies dan "Ja" <i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i> <i>Categories:</i> 1. Nee 2. Ja

Q56	SQ	56. Taking into account all source of income in your household (e.g., partner income, social benefit, non-labour income from properties, etc), what is your total net household income per week? If you don't know the exact figure, please give an estimate. (following are weekly values) 1. less than £229 2. £229 to under £308 3. £308 to under £385 4. £385 to under £469 5. £469 to under £562 6. £562 to under £667 7. £667 to under £795 8. £795 to under £982 9. £982 to under £1,267 10. £1,267 or more
	UK	68. Taking into account all source of income in your household (e.g., partner income, social benefit, non-labour income from properties, etc), what is your total net household income per week? If you don't know the exact figure, please give an estimate. (following are weekly values) 1. less than £229 2. £229 to under £308 3. £308 to under £385 4. £385 to under £469 5. £469 to under £562

		6. £562 to under £667 7. £667 to under £795 8. £795 to under £982 9. £982 to under £1,267 10. £1,267 or more
	FR	Q57 En tenant compte de toutes les sources de revenu de votre ménage (par exemple revenu du partenaire, avantage social, revenu hors travail issu de propriétés, etc.), pourriez-vous nous donner le revenu mensuel net de votre ménage après impôts et déductions obligatoires? Si vous ne connaissez pas le chiffre exact, veuillez donner une estimation. 1. Moins de 1 150 € 2. De 1 150 € à 1 600 € 3. De 1 601 € à 1 900 € 4. De 1 901 € à 2 250 € 5. De 2 251 € à 2 650 € 6. De 2 651 € à 3 150 € 7. De 3 151 € à 3 750 € 8. De 3 751 € à 4 500 € 9. De 4 501 € à 5 750 € 10. Plus de 5 750 €
	SE	q108 Med hänsyn till alla inkomstkällor i ditt hushåll (t.ex. partners inkomst, ekonomiskt bistånd, intäkter från fastigheter), vad är din totala <i>hushållsinkomst efter skatt</i> per månad? Om du inte vet den exakta siffran, ge en uppskattning. 1. Upp till 12 999 2. 13 000 - 15 999 3. 16 000 - 21 999 4. 22 000 - 25 999 5. 26 000 - 30 999 6. 31 000 - 38 999 7. 39 000 - 46 999 8. 47 000 - 56 999 9. 57 000 - 71 999 10. 72 000 eller mer 11. Vet ej/ vill ej ange
	NL	omitted

Q57	SQ	57. A household may have different sources of income and more than one household member may contribute to it. Thinking of your household's total monthly income, is your household able to make ends meet...? 1. Very easily 2. Easily 3. Fairly easily 4. With some difficulty 5. With difficulty 6. With great difficulty
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	UK	69. A household may have different sources of income and more than one household member may contribute to it. Thinking of your household's total monthly income, is your household able to make ends meet...? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very easily 2. Easily 3. Fairly easily 4. With some difficulty 5. With difficulty 6. With great difficulty
	FR	Q58 Un ménage peut avoir différentes sources de revenus et plusieurs membres du ménage peuvent apporter leur contribution. En pensant au revenu mensuel total de votre ménage, votre foyer est-il en mesure de joindre les deux bouts : <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Très facilement 2. Facilement 3. Assez facilement 4. Avec quelques difficultés 5. Avec difficultés 6. Avec de grandes difficultés
	SE	q110 Ett hushåll kan ha olika inkomstkällor och mer än en hushållsmedlem kan bidra till det. Om du tänker på ditt hushålls totala månadsinkomst, hur klarar sig ditt hushåll? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mycket bra 2. Bra 3. Ganska bra 4. Med viss svårighet 5. Med svårighet 6. Med stor svårighet
	NL	Q47 Een gezin kan verschillende bronnen van inkomsten hebben en meer dan één gezinslid kan daaraan bijdragen. Hoe goed kan uw gezin rondkomen van het totale maandinkomen? <i>Answer type: Radio buttons</i> <i>Categories:</i> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Heel makkelijk 2. Makkelijk 3. Vrij makkelijk 4. Met enige moeite 5. Met moeite 6. Met veel moeite

From Q58, the survey asks questions on socio-demographic characteristics. Many questions are omitted for France, Sweden and the Netherlands as the data were already available in the national panels. Our datasets therefore include the full socio-demographic data from the respondents, but the questions were not included in the survey.

Q58	SQ	Before we end the survey, we would like to ask you some information about you. 58. Would you describe yourself as... <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Female 2. Male 3. Non-binary 4. Other
	UK	70. With which gender do you identify yourself? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Female

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Male 3. Non-binary 4. Other
	FR	omitted
	SE	omitted
	NL	omitted

Q59	SQ	How old are you?
	UK	<p><i>OE NUM – 0-99</i> <i>SCREENOUT IF <18</i> 71. How old are you?</p> <p><i>HIDDEN – AGE RECODE</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 18-34 2. 35-49 3. 50+
	FR	omitted
	SE	omitted
	NL	omitted

Q60	SQ	<p>60. What is the highest level of education or training that you have successfully completed?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No qualification, left school before age 11 2. No qualification, left school between age 11 and 14 3. No qualification, left school after age 14 4. One or more of the following: Key Skills, Skills for Life Level 1, Functional Skills Level 1, NVQ Level 1, GNVQ or GSVQ Foundation Level, BTEC or SCOTVEC Introductory, First or General Certificate, RSA Levels 1-3, City & Guilds Part 1, YT or YTP Certificate 5. One or more of the following: Functional Skills Level 2, NVQ Level 2, GNVQ Intermediate Level, BTEC or SCOTVEC First or General Diploma, RSA Diploma, City & Guilds Part 2 6. One or more of the following: One or more CSEs below Grade 1, one or more GCSEs or O Levels 7. One or more A Levels or AS Levels, One or more SCE Higher Grade, Scottish Certificate of Sixth Year Studies, International Baccalaureate 8. NVQ Level 3, GNVQ or GSVQ Advanced Level 9. Higher Education Access Course 10. NVQ Level 4, HNC or HND, BTEC higher, Diploma in Higher Education, Teaching qualification, e.g. Teaching Certificate, PGCE, Nursing qualification, RSA Higher Diploma 11. NVQ Level 5 12. First degree: BA or BSc 13. Higher degree, e.g. MA, MBA, MSc, Mphil 14. Doctorate: PhD or Dphil
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	UK	<p>72. What is the highest level of education or training that you have successfully completed?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No qualification, left school before age 11 2. No qualification, left school between age 11 and 14 3. No qualification, left school after age 14 4. One or more of the following: Key Skills, Skills for Life Level 1, Functional Skills Level 1, NVQ Level 1, GNVQ or GSVQ Foundation Level, BTEC or SCOTVEC Introductory, First or General Certificate, RSA Levels 1-3, City & Guilds Part 1, YT or YTP Certificate 5. One or more of the following: Functional Skills Level 2, NVQ Level 2, GNVQ Intermediate Level, BTEC or SCOTVEC First or General Diploma, RSA Diploma, City & Guilds Part 2 6. One or more of the following: One or more CSEs below Grade 1, one or more GCSEs or O Levels 7. One or more A Levels or AS Levels, One or more SCE Higher Grade, Scottish Certificate of Sixth Year Studies, International Baccalaureate 8. NVQ Level 3, GNVQ or GSVQ Advanced Level 9. Higher Education Access Course 10. NVQ Level 4, HNC or HND, BTEC higher, Diploma in Higher Education, Teaching qualification, e.g. Teaching Certificate, PGCE, Nursing qualification, RSA Higher Diploma 11. NVQ Level 5 12. First degree: BA or BSc 13. Higher degree, e.g. MA, MBA, MSc, Mphil 14. Doctorate: PhD or Dphil
	FR	omitted
	SE	omitted
	NL	omitted

Note that Swedish panel included the question on the place of residence but used the question they already had in their panel instead of using the question from SQ.

Q61	SQ	<p>61. Which of the following best describes the area you live?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A big city 2. The suburbs or outskirts of a big city 3. A town or a small city 4. A country village 5. A farm or home in the countryside
	UK	<p>73. Which of the following best describes the area you live?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A big city 2. The suburbs or outskirts of a big city 3. A town or a small city 4. A country village 5. A farm or home in the countryside
	FR	omitted

	SE	<p>q114 I vilken typ av område bor du?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Storstad: centralt 2. Storstad: ytterområde/förort 3. Stad: centralt 4. Stad: ytterområde 5. Större tätort 6. Mindre tätort 7. Ren landsbygd
	NL	omitted

Q62-65 have been changed to simplify the questions while getting the core data we need. We merged the three questions and ask "Including yourself, how many people live with you regularly as members of your household? A. Adults (including yourself): ____, B. Children, 0-13 years old: _____, C. Children, 14-17 years old: _____." This was not adjusted in the SQ but was incorporated in Sweden. Questions about the number of household members and children were already contained in the standard questionnaire in the Netherlands.

Q62-64	SQ	<p>62. Do you live together with your partner, spouse or a significant other?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No <p>63. Do you have (a) child(ren)?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No <p><i>OE NUM – 0-10</i></p> <p>64. How many child(ren) do you have?</p>
	UK	<p>74. Do you live together with your partner, spouse or a significant other?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No <p>75. Do you have (a) child(ren)?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No <p><i>ASK ONLY IF Q75=1</i></p> <p><i>OE NUM – 1-10</i></p> <p>76. How many child(ren) do you have?</p>
	FR	omitted
	SE	<p>q104 Hur många personer bor regelbundet med dig i ditt hushåll, inklusive dig själv? Svara i siffror.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Vuxna (inklusive dig själv) 2. Barn 0-3 år 3. Barn 4-13 år 4. Barn 14-17 år
	NL	omitted

Q65	SQ	<p>ASK ONLY IF Q64>0 OE NUM IF AGE > 18: LIMITS = 0-3 IF AGE = 18: LIMITS = 1-3 ANSWER CAN'T BE SUPERIOR TO RESPONSE FROM Q64 65. How many child(ren) below the age of 3 do you have?</p>
	UK	<p>ASK ONLY IF Q75=1 OE NUM IF AGE > 18: LIMITS = 0-3 IF AGE = 18: LIMITS = 1-3 ANSWER CAN'T BE SUPERIOR TO RESPONSE FROM Q76 77. How many child(ren) below the age of 3 do you have?</p> <p>ASK ONLY IF Q75=1 OE NUM IF Q77=0: MIN = 3 – MAX = ([RESPONDENT AGE] – 16) IF Q77>0: MIN = 0 – MAX = 3 78. What is the age of the youngest child?</p>
	FR	omitted
	SE	See q104
	NL	omitted

Note that for Sweden, the question on citizenship Q66 is asked in the survey, as it didn't feature in the LORE database.

Q66-67	SQ	<p>66. Are you a citizen of the United Kingdom? 1. Yes 2. No</p> <p>67. Were you born in the United Kingdom? 1. Yes 2. No</p>
	UK	<p>79. Are you a citizen of the United Kingdom? 1. Yes 2. No</p> <p>ASK ONLY IF Q79=1 80. Were you born in the United Kingdom? 1. Yes 2. No</p>
	FR	omitted
	SE	<p>q112 Är du svensk medborgare? 1. Ja 2. Nej</p>
	NL	omitted

Q67 was deleted due to different ethical regulations across countries.

Q67	SQ	deleted
	UK	81. With which ethnic group do you most identify? 1. Other ethnic group (please specify) 2. Black or African or Caribbean or Black British 3. Asian or Asian British 4. Mixed or Multiple Ethnic groups 5. White 6. Middle Eastern or Arabic
	FR	Deleted for ethical reason
	SE	Deleted for ethical reason
	NL	Deleted for ethical reason

Note that for Sweden and the Netherlands, this question was deleted due to ethical reasons.

Q68	SQ	68. Do you have chronic illness or disability? 1. Yes 2. No
	UK	82. Do you have chronic illness or disability? 1. Yes 2. No
	FR	<i>Si Groupe A ou Groupe B</i> Les questions suivantes portent sur la protection sociale. Q46 Avez-vous une maladie ou un problème de santé chronique ou de caractère durable? Une maladie chronique est une maladie qui dure depuis au moins 6 mois (ou durera longtemps) ou qui revient (reviendra) régulièrement. 1. Oui 2. Non
	SE	Deleted for ethical reason
	NL	Deleted for ethical reason

Vignette experiment

One set of questions that were deleted in the SQ was an vignette experiment to examine how people perceive workers doing unpaid labour differently based on different socio-demographic and economic backgrounds. Four indicators were made to vary randomly in the survey, which are name, occupation, age, and salary. Name is used to indicate both the gender and migrant status (Paul, Sarah, Marek and Katarzyna), and the occupations represent different sectors (gig, care, creative and general). Age was simplified to two types – 20s and 50s – which represent the young and older workers. Salary was calculated based on the wage range for each occupations published in WageIndicator Foundation website, represent low and high earnings. We have given them a script to give the profile of the worker and mentioned that they ‘always end up working longer due to work that is not finished’ and that ‘the work he/she undertakes outside of 9-5 are not paid.’ We then ask to what extent respondents see them inefficient/efficient, disinterested/passionate, lazy/hardworking.

UK

INFO SCREEN

Following questions are based on a description of a person. Please read the description below and answer the following questions.

[NAME] is a **[JOB]** in his/her **[AGE]**. He/she tries to work between 9-5, but always ends up working longer due to work that is not finished. The work he/she undertakes outside of 9-5 are, however, not paid. He/she earns per month, **[SALARY]** pounds.

Randomly select a combination of values for each respondent

Values for NAME

1. Paul
2. Sarah
3. Marek
4. Katarzyna

Values for JOB

1. delivery worker who delivers parcels that people order online
2. care worker working in a care home
3. freelance graphic designer who designs posters for events and activities outsourced by different companies and organisations
4. administrative worker at a small firm

Values for AGE

1. 20s
2. 50s

Values for SALARY

IF JOB=1

1. 1277
2. 2039

IF JOB=2

3. 1244
4. 1955

IF JOB=3

5. 1484
6. 3064

IF JOB=4

7. 1343
8. 2851

There can be following possible combinations for Paul and same for the other three names – so total $16 \times 4 = 64$ possible combinations.

	Name	Job	Age	Income
1	Paul	Delivery worker ...	20s	1277 pounds
2	Paul	Delivery worker ...	20s	2039 pounds
3	Paul	Delivery worker ...	50s	1277 pounds

4	Paul	Delivery worker ...	50s	2039 pounds
5	Paul	Care worker ...	20s	1244 pounds
6	Paul	Care worker ...	20s	1955 pounds
7	Paul	Care worker ...	50s	1244 pounds
8	Paul	Care worker ...	50s	1955 pounds
9	Paul	Freelance graphic designer ...	20s	1484 pounds
10	Paul	Freelance graphic designer ...	20s	3064 pounds
11	Paul	Freelance graphic designer ...	50s	1484 pounds
12	Paul	Freelance graphic designer ...	50s	3064 pounds
13	Paul	Administrative worker ...	20s	1343 pounds
14	Paul	Administrative worker ...	20s	2851 pounds
15	Paul	Administrative worker ...	50s	1343 pounds
16	Paul	Administrative worker ...	50s	2851 pounds

30. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

A. He/she is inefficient - efficient

Inefficient

Efficient

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

B. He/she is disinterested – passionate

Disinterested

Passionate

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

C. He/she is opposite - hardworking

Lazy

Hardworking

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

Appendix – Complete Questionnaire per country

Appendix 1. UK Questionnaire

SC

SD1. With which gender do you identify yourself?

- 1) Female
- 2) Male
- 3) Non-binary
- 4) Other

OE NUM – 0-99

SCREENOUT IF <18

SD2. How old are you?

HIDDEN – AGE RECODE

1. 18-34
2. 35-49
3. 50+

INFO SCREEN

To start with, we would like to ask you some questions about your current job(s).

MC

1. Which of these descriptions applies to what you have been doing for the last 7 days?
Select all that apply
(from ESS)
 11. In paid work (or away temporarily, on leave or furlough) (employee, self-employed, working for your family business)
 12. Paid internship
 13. Unpaid internship
 14. In education, (not paid for by employer) even if on vacation
 15. Unemployed and actively looking for a job
 16. Unemployed, wanting a job but not actively looking for a job
 17. Permanently sick or disabled
 18. Retired
 19. In community or military service
 20. Doing housework, looking after children or other persons
 21. Other (write:) **OE CHA**

ASK Q2 ONLY IF CODE 1 or 2 NOT SELECTED IN Q1

SC

2. Did you do any paid work of an hour or more in the last 7 days?
(ESS)
 1. Yes

2. No

SCREENOUT IF CODE 2 SELECTED

ASK Q3 ONLY IF Q1=1 OR Q1=2 OR Q2=1

SC

3. In the last month did you work in more than 1 job?
(note that this does not apply to changing the job but doing several jobs at the same time – namely, multi-jobs)
- 1) yes
 - 2) no

INFO SCREEN – SHOW IF Q3=1

If you have more than one job, please answer about the one that takes up the most hours per week. If you have two jobs that are exactly equal, please answer about the more highly paid of the two. That job will be defined as the 'main job' for this survey.

ASK ONLY IF Q1=1 OR Q1=2 OR Q2=1

SC

4. Are you working as an employee or are you self-employed? (or working for your own family's business)
- (EWCS & ESS)**
- 1) Employee (paid a salary or wage by an employer)
 - 2) Self-employed
 - 3) Working for your own family's business
 - 4) Working under government scheme (**LFS**)
 - 5) Other (write:) **OE CHA**

ASK ONLY IF Q1=1 OR Q1=2 OR Q2=1

OE CHA

5. What is the title of your main paid job? By main paid job, we mean the one where you spend most hours.
- (EWCS)**

ASK ONLY IF Q1=1 OR Q1=2 OR Q2=1

OE CHA

6. What do you mainly do in your job?
- (EWCS)**

ASK ONLY IF Q3=1

SC

7. Other than your main job, how many jobs do you have?
- 1) 1
 - 2) 2
 - 3) 3
 - 4) 4

- 5) 5
- 6) More than 5

ASK ONLY IF Q3=1

OE CHA

8. What is the title of your second job?

ASK ONLY IF Q7=2 TO 6

OE CHA

9. What is the title of your third job?

ASK ONLY IF Q4=2

MC

10. Looking at this card, please select the category or categories which apply to your main paid job?

(EWCS)

- 1) Sole director of own business
- 2) A partner in a business or professional practice
- 3) Working for yourself
- 4) Working as a sub-contractor
- 5) Doing freelance work
- 6) Paid a salary or a wage by an agency
- 7) Other (write:) **OE CHA**

ASK ONLY IF Q4=2

SC PER ROW

11. Regarding your business, do you

(EWCS)

	Yes	No
I. Have the authority to hire or dismiss employees?	1	2
J. Get paid an agreed fee on a weekly or monthly basis?	1	2
K. Have employees (working for you)?	1	2
L. Generally, have more than one client or customer?	1	2

ASK ONLY IF Q4=1

SC

12. Do you have a contract? If so, does it specify the agreed working hours?

- 1) No
- 2) Yes, specified
- 3) Yes, not specified

SC

13. What kind of employment contract do you have in your main job?

(EWCS)

- 1) Contract of unlimited duration
- 2) Contract of limited duration
- 3) A temporary employment agency contract
- 4) An apprenticeship or other training scheme
- 5) Zero hours contract (without agreed minimum working hours)
- 6) On-call, on-demand jobs (with agreed minimum working hours)
- 7) Other (write:) **OE CHA**

SC

14. How many employees in total work in your company/organization/business?

(mix of EWCS & ESS)

- 1) 1 (works alone)
- 2) 2-9
- 3) 10-24
- 4) 25-99
- 5) 100-249
- 6) 250-499
- 7) 500 or more

SC

15. Are you working in...?

(EWCS)

- 1) The private sector
- 2) The public sector
- 3) A joint private-public organization or company
- 4) The not-for-profit sector or an NGO
- 5) Other (write:) **OE CHA**

SC

16. In your main job, do you have any responsibility for supervising the work of other employees? (EWCS)

- 1) Yes
- 2) no

INFO SCREEN

The next questions are about your paid and unpaid working hours in your main job (that takes up most hours per week, or the one with higher pay if several jobs have the same hour)

ASK Q17 ONLY IF Q12=2

OE NUM – 0-100

17. In a typical work week, what is the agreed working hours according to the contract?

OE NUM – 0-100

18. How many hours per week do you usually actually work in your main job/business – please exclude meal breaks?

(LFS)

ASK Q19 ONLY IF Q3=1

OE NUM – 0-100

19. How many hours a week on average do you work in job(s) other than your main paid job?
(EWCS)

SC

20. Do you get paid or compensations for your overtime work?

- 1) I do not work overtime
- 2) I work overtime, and it is fully compensated
- 3) I work overtime, and it is partially compensated
- 4) I work overtime, but is not compensated

SPECIFIC INSTRUCTION FOR Q21 - Q22 - Q23: We would like this to be followed by the 22A 23A... instead of presenting all 21A-I then 22A-I...

SC PER ROW

21. In your main paid job: has this occurred to you?

	No	Yes
I. Waiting time between jobs/tasks	1	2
J. Preparation time	1	2
K. Communication with clients/employers	1	2
L. Administrative/paper work	1	2
M. Travel time between jobs and tasks (excluding commuting time between home and work)	1	2
N. Maintenance time (e.g., time spent on maintaining work equipment)	1	2
O. Networking time (contacting or meeting people related to the job to build relationships or maintain them overtime; attending events in order to meet new people)	1	2
P. 'Volunteer work' as part of the job	1	2
Q. Training	1	2

SHOW ONLY ITEMS WITH CODE 2 IN Q21**SC PER ROW**

22. In your main paid job: are they paid by your employer/contractor?

	Fully paid	Partially paid	Fully unpaid
R. Waiting time between jobs/tasks	1	2	3
S. Preparation time	1	2	3
T. Communication with clients/employers	1	2	3
U. Administrative/paper work	1	2	3
V. Travel time between jobs and tasks (excluding commuting time between home and work)	1	2	3
W. Maintenance time (e.g., time spent on maintaining work equipment)	1	2	3
X. Networking time (contacting or meeting people related to the job to build relationships or maintain them overtime; attending events in order to meet new people)	1	2	3
Y. 'Volunteer work' as part of the job	1	2	3
Z. Training	1	2	3

SHOW ONLY ITEMS WITH CODE 2 OR 3 IN Q22

SC PER ROW

23. On average, how frequently do you do the following work unpaid?

	Daily	Several times a week	Several times a month	Less often	Never
J. Waiting time between jobs/tasks	1	2	3	4	5
K. Preparation time	1	2	3	4	5
L. Communication with clients/employers	1	2	3	4	5
M. Administrative/paper work	1	2	3	4	5
N. Travel time between jobs and tasks (excluding commuting time between home and work)	1	2	3	4	5
O. Maintenance time (e.g., time spent on maintaining work equipment)	1	2	3	4	5
P. Networking time (contacting or meeting people related to the job to build relationships or maintain them overtime; attending events in order to meet new people)	1	2	3	4	5
Q. 'Volunteer work' as part of the job	1	2	3	4	5
R. Training	1	2	3	4	5

OE CHA

24. Are there other types of work you do as part of your main job that are unpaid? If so, what are they?

99. There is no other type of work I do as part of my main job that is unpaid. **EXCLUSIVE**

INFO SCREEN

The following questions are about the tools and equipment you need in your main job (that takes up most hours per week, or the one with higher pay if several jobs have the same hour)

SC PER ROW

25. Are the following equipment/tools/materials necessary for your main job?

	No	Yes
N. Transportation means (car, bike, truck, etc.)	1	2
O. Related to safety (PPE(personal protective equipment), gloves, etc.)	1	2
P. Related to appearance (certain clothes, accessories, make-up, etc.)	1	2
Q. Related to communication (mobile data, internet, etc.)	1	2
R. Gifts/rewards for clients	1	2

SHOW ONLY ITEMS WITH CODE 2 IN Q25

SC PER ROW

26. Is it paid by your employer/contractor?

	Fully paid	Partially paid	Fully unpaid
N. Transportation means (car, bike, truck, etc.)	1	2	3
O. Related to safety (PPE(personal protective equipment), gloves, etc.)	1	2	3

P. Related to appearance (certain clothes, accessories, make-up, etc.)	1	2	3
Q. Related to communication (mobile data, internet, etc.)	1	2	3
R. Gifts/rewards for clients	1	2	3

OE CHA

27. Are there any other types of materials to assist with your main job that you pay on your own? If so, what are they?

99. There is no other type of materials to assist with my main job that I pay on my own. **EXCLUSIVE**

**ASK ONLY IF AT LEAST ONE CODE 2 OR 3 SELECTED IN Q26 OR IF CODE 99 NOT SELECTED IN Q27
OE NUM – 0-300**

28. Taking all into account, how much do you approximately spend on these equipment/tools/materials (including maintenance) per month for your main job? (in pounds)

INFO SCREEN

In this survey, we define unpaid work as any kind of work that we do in our daily lives that is not paid. For the following questions, the unpaid work is strictly limited to the work that you do as part of your paid job that are unpaid. For the self-employed, this may refer to all the tasks/hours you that are not included as part of the price of your work or products. The ‘work’ here does not include any activities that can be considered a ‘leisure’.

ASK Q29 ONLY IF AT LEAST ONE CODE 2 OR 3 SELECTED IN Q22 OR IF AT LEAST ONE CODE 2 OR 3 SELECTED IN Q26

29. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

COLUMNS

1) Strongly disagree 2) Tend to disagree 3) Neither agree nor disagree 4) Tend to agree 5) Strongly agree

ITEMS

- I. Unpaid work is part of my job
- J. I do unpaid work, because there is no one to replace me
- K. I do unpaid work with because it might help my career (e.g., promotion, increase in wage, bonus, finding a better job, etc.)
- L. I do unpaid work because it is seen good by colleagues/clients/employers
- M. I do unpaid work out of care or kindness
- N. If I don't do unpaid work, I feel guilty
- O. Not doing unpaid work is seen badly by colleagues/clients/employers
- P. If I don't do unpaid work, it might harm on my career (e.g., promotion, finding better job in the future, wage, losing clients)

INFO SCREEN

Following questions are based on a description of a person. Please read the description below and answer the following questions.

[NAME] is a [JOB] in his/her [AGE]. He/she tries to work between 9-5, but always ends up working longer due to work that is not finished. The work he/she undertakes outside of 9-5 are, however, not paid. He/she earns per month, [SALARY] pounds.

Randomly select a combination of values for each respondent

Values for NAME

5. Paul
6. Sarah
7. Marek
8. Katarzyna

Values for JOB

5. delivery worker who delivers parcels that people order online
6. care worker working in a care home
7. freelance graphic designer who designs posters for events and activities outsourced by different companies and organisations
8. administrative worker at a small firm

Values for AGE

3. 20s
4. 50s

Values for SALARY

IF JOB=1

9. 1277
10. 2039

IF JOB=2

11. 1244
12. 1955

IF JOB=3

13. 1484
14. 3064

IF JOB=4

15. 1343
16. 2851

There can be following possible combinations for Paul and same for the other three names – so total $16 \times 4 = 64$ possible combinations.

	Name	Job	Age	Income
1	Paul	Delivery worker ...	20s	1277 pounds
2	Paul	Delivery worker ...	20s	2039 pounds
3	Paul	Delivery worker ...	50s	1277 pounds
4	Paul	Delivery worker ...	50s	2039 pounds
5	Paul	Care worker ...	20s	1244 pounds
6	Paul	Care worker ...	20s	1955 pounds
7	Paul	Care worker ...	50s	1244 pounds
8	Paul	Care worker ...	50s	1955 pounds
9	Paul	Freelance graphic designer ...	20s	1484 pounds
10	Paul	Freelance graphic designer ...	20s	3064 pounds
11	Paul	Freelance graphic designer ...	50s	1484 pounds
12	Paul	Freelance graphic designer ...	50s	3064 pounds
13	Paul	Administrative worker ...	20s	1343 pounds
14	Paul	Administrative worker ...	20s	2851 pounds
15	Paul	Administrative worker ...	50s	1343 pounds
16	Paul	Administrative worker ...	50s	2851 pounds

SC PER ROW

30. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

D. He/she is inefficient - efficient

Inefficient

Efficient

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

E. He/she is disinterested – passionate

Disinterested

Passionate

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

F. He/she is opposite - hardworking

Lazy

Hardworking

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

INFO SCREEN

Following questions are about how you feel about your job

SC PER ROW

31. For each of the following statements, please select the response which best describes your work situation.

(Based on EWCS)

1) Strongly disagree 2) Tend to disagree 3) Neither agree nor disagree 4) Tend to agree 5) Strongly agree

- A. My job gives me the feeling of work well done
- B. I have the feeling of doing useful work
- C. I feel like my job is being recognized
- D. I feel appreciated in the society because of my job
- E. Considering all my efforts and achievements in my job, I feel I get paid appropriately
- F. My job offers good prospects for career advancement
- G. I might lose my job in the next 6 months
- H. If I were to lose or quit my current job, it would be easy for me to find a job of similar salary

SC PER ROW

32. The following statements are about how you feel about your job. For each statement, please tell me how often you feel this way...

(EWCS)

1) Always 2) Most of the time 3) Sometimes 4) Rarely 5) Never

- A. At my work I feel full of energy
- B. I am enthusiastic about my job

- C. Time flies when I am working
- D. I feel exhausted at the end of the working day
- E. I doubt the importance of my work
- F. I feel that I am good at my job
- G. I experience stress in my job

INFO SCREEN

We would like to ask you about the emotional side of your job

SC PER ROW

33. In your main job, how frequently do you...?

1) Always 2) Most of the time 3) Sometimes 4) Rarely 5) Never

- A. Listen to customer/employer/colleagues' complaints
- B. Feel like you have to resist expressing your true feelings
- C. Pretend to have emotions that you don't really have
- D. Hide your true feelings about a situation
- E. Make an effort to actually feel the emotions that you need to display to others (customers/employers/colleagues)
- F. Try to actually experience the emotions that you must show
- G. Really try to feel the emotions you have to show as part of my job

INFO SCREEN

Following questions are about how the people who do your job feel in the society

SC PER ROW

34. To what extent do you agree with the following statements about how you feel in the society?

1) Strongly disagree 2) Tend to disagree 3) Neither agree nor disagree 4) Tend to agree 5) Strongly agree

- A. People who do my job feel belong to the society
- B. People who do my job feel set apart, isolated from the rest of the world
- C. Sometimes I feel that people who do my job are being talked down to
- D. Other people think less of people who do my job
- E. People who do my job feel we're not as good as others
- F. I avoid telling people about my job
- G. I worry about people discriminating against me because of my job

INFO SCREEN

Following questions are about how you've felt during the past week

SC PER ROW

35. How much of the time during the past week...

(ESS)

		None or almost none of the time	Some of the time	Most of the time	All or almost all of the time
A	...you felt depressed?	1	2	3	4
B	...you felt that everything you did was an effort?	1	2	3	4
C	...your sleep was restless?	1	2	3	4
D	...you were happy?	1	2	3	4
E	...you felt lonely?	1	2	3	4
F	...you enjoyed life?	1	2	3	4
G	...you felt sad?	1	2	3	4
H	...you could not get going?	1	2	3	4

INFO SCREEN

Following questions are about the hours you work outside of your paid job

OE NUM – 0-100

36. On average, how many hours per week do you spend on Job searching/application outside of your paid job?

OE NUM – 0-100

37. On average, how many hours per week do you spend on job preparation/practice/training outside of your main paid job or to get a paid job?

OE NUM – 0-100

38. On average, how many hours per week do you spend on Volunteer or charitable activity (such as union activities or community engagement) outside of your paid job?

INFO SCREEN

Now we would like to go back to your main job and ask you about your working hours

OE NUM PER ROW

39. Normally in your main job, how many times a month do you work...?

(EWCS)

- A. At night, for at least 2 hours between 10pm-5am **OE NUM – 0-31**
- B. On Sundays? **OE NUM – 0-5**
- C. On Saturdays? **OE NUM – 0-5**
- D. More than 10 hours a day? **OE NUM – 0-31**

SC

40. In the last month in your main job, has it happened at least once that you had less than 11 hours between the end of one working day and the start of the next working day?

- 1) Yes
- 2) No

SC PER ROW

41. In your main job, do you work...?

(EWCS)

	Yes	No
F. The same number of hours every day	1	2
G. The same number of days every week	1	2
H. The same number of hours every week	1	2
I. Fixed starting and finishing times	1	2
J. Shifts	1	2

SC

42. In your main job, do changes to your working time arrangements occur regularly? (if yes,) how long before are you informed about these changes?

(EWCS)

- 1) No
- 2) Yes, the same day
- 3) Yes, the day before
- 4) Yes, several days in advance
- 5) Yes, several weeks in advance

INFO SCREEN

Following questions are about the flexibility and control you have in your main job

SC

43. In your main job, can you decide the starting time of work?

- 1) Yes
- 2) No

SC

44. In your main job, can you decide the working hours?

- 1) Yes
- 2) No

SC

45. To your knowledge, are there flexible work arrangements in the company or organisation in your main job? (flexible work arrangement include part-time, flexitime (adapted beginning and finishing working times), working from home (telework) or being able to take some time off for private emergencies (medical issues, a sick child, etc.))

(Eurobarometer)

- 1) Yes, and I currently use or have used such arrangements personally
- 2) Yes, but I have never used such arrangements personally
- 3) No, there are no flexible work arrangements available in the company or organization where I currently work

SC

46. In your main job, can you decide where you work?

- 1) Yes
- 2) No

SC PER ROW

47. In your main job, are you able to choose or change...
(EWCS)

	Yes	No
A. Your order of tasks	1	2
B. Your methods of work	1	2
C. Your speed or rate of work	1	2

INFO SCREEN

Following questions are about trade unions at your workplace

SC

48. Is there a trade union, works council or a similar committee representing the employees at your workplace?
(EWCS)

- 1) Yes
- 2) No

ASK ONLY IF Q48=1

OE CHA

49. What is the name of the trade union at your workplace?

ASK ONLY IF Q48=1

SC

50. Are you a member of the trade union?
1) Yes
2) No

INFO SCREEN

Now we would like to ask you about how you balance between your work and family

OE NUM PER ROW – 0-100

51. On average, how many hours per week do you spend for the following activities outside work?
A. household chores
B. caring for children/grandchildren
C. caring for elderly/disabled relatives

SC

52. In general, how do your working hours fit in with your family or social commitments outside work?
(EWCS)
1) Very well
2) Well
3) Not very well
4) Not at all well

SC PER ROW

53. How often in the last 12 months (or since you started working), have you...?

(EWCS)

1) Always 2) Most of the time 3) Sometimes 4) Rarely 5) Never

- A. Kept worrying about work when you were not working
- B. Felt too tired after work to do some of the household jobs which need to be done
- C. Found that your job prevented you from giving the time you wanted to your family
- D. Found it difficult to concentrate on your job because of your family responsibilities
- E. Found that your family responsibilities prevented you from giving the time you should to your job

INFO SCREEN

Following questions are about social protection

SC

54. In case of illness or injury, do you think you can keep your main job?

- 1) Yes
- 2) No

SC

55. In case of illness, do you think your household can make ends meet?

- 1) Yes
- 2) No

SC

56. Over the past 12 months (or since you started working), did you work when you were sick?

(EWCS)

- 1) Yes
- 2) No

SC

57. In case of unemployment, do you think your household can make ends meet?

- 1) Yes
- 2) No

SC

58. When you retire, do you think your household can make ends meet?

- 1) Yes
- 2) No

SC

59. From your main job, are you entitled to maternity/paternity leave?

- 1) Yes
- 2) No

SC

60. In case of having a child now, do you think you can keep your main job?

- 1) Yes
- 2) No

SC

61. In case of having a child now, do you think your household can make ends meet?

- 1) Yes
- 2) No

INFO SCREEN

Now going back to your main job, we would like to ask you about the safety at your workplace

SC

62. In your main job, do you think your health or safety is at risk because of your work?

(EWCS)

- 1) Yes
- 2) No

SC

63. In your main job, does your work affect your health?

(EWCS)

- 1) Yes, mainly positively
- 2) Yes, mainly negatively
- 3) No

INFO SCREEN

Now we would like to ask you about your income

SC

64. Thinking about your usual pay in your main job, which one do you know best?

(ESS)

- 1) Weekly pay
- 2) Monthly pay
- 3) Annual pay

SC

65. Please can you tell us what is your average weekly/monthly/annual net pay after tax and compulsory deductions from your main job? If you don't know the exact figure, please give an estimate.

(EWCS, ESS)

	Weekly SHOW IF Q61=1	Monthly SHOW IF Q61=2	Yearly SHOW IF Q61=3
1)	Less than £100	Less than £400	Less than £4800
2)	£101-£150	£401-£600	£4801-£7200
3)	£151-£200	£601-£800	£7201-£9600
4)	£201-£250	£801-£1000	£9601-£1200
5)	£251-£300	£1001-£1200	£12001-£14400

6)	£301-£375	£1201-£1500	£14401-£18000
7)	£376-£450	£1501-£1800	£18001-£21600
8)	£451-£525	£1801-£2100	£21601-£25200
9)	£526-£625	£2101-£2500	£25201-£30000
10)	£626-£750	£2501-£3000	£30001-£36000
11)	£751-£875	£3001-£3500	£36001-£42000
12)	More than £876	More than £3501	More than £42001

SC

66. Would you say your income from your main job is stable?

- 1) Stable
- 2) Relatively stable
- 3) Relatively unstable
- 4) Unstable

SC

67. Are you, in your household, the person who contributes the most to the household income?

(EWCS)

- 1) Yes
- 2) No

SC

68. Taking into account all source of income in your household (e.g., partner income, social benefit, non-labour income from properties, etc), what is your total net household income per week? If you don't know the exact figure, please give an estimate. (following are weekly values)

- 1) less than £229
- 2) £229 to under £308
- 3) £308 to under £385
- 4) £385 to under £469
- 5) £469 to under £562
- 6) £562 to under £667
- 7) £667 to under £795
- 8) £795 to under £982
- 9) £982 to under £1,267
- 10) £1,267 or more

SC

69. A household may have different sources of income and more than one household member may contribute to it. Thinking of your household's total monthly income, is your household able to make ends meet...?

(EWCS)

- 1) Very easily
- 2) Easily
- 3) Fairly easily
- 4) With some difficulty

- 5) With difficulty
- 6) With great difficulty

INFO SCREEN

Before we end the survey, we would like to ask you some information about you

~~70. With which gender do you identify yourself?~~

- ~~1) Female~~
- ~~2) Male~~
- ~~3) Non-binary~~
- ~~4) Other~~

~~71. How old are you?~~

SC

72. What is the highest level of education or training that you have successfully completed?

(EWCS)

- 1) No qualification, left school before age 11
- 2) No qualification, left school between age 11 and 14
- 3) No qualification, left school after age 14
- 4) One or more of the following: Key Skills, Skills for Life Level 1, Functional Skills Level 1, NVQ Level 1, GNVQ or GSVQ Foundation Level, BTEC or SCOTVEC Introductory, First or General Certificate, RSA Levels 1-3, City & Guilds Part 1, YT or YTP Certificate
- 5) One or more of the following: Functional Skills Level 2, NVQ Level 2, GNVQ Intermediate Level, BTEC or SCOTVEC First or General Diploma, RSA Diploma, City & Guilds Part 2
- 6) One or more of the following: One or more CSEs below Grade 1, one or more GCSEs or O Levels
- 7) One or more A Levels or AS Levels, One or more SCE Higher Grade, Scottish Certificate of Sixth Year Studies, International Baccalaureate
- 8) NVQ Level 3, GNVQ or GSVQ Advanced Level
- 9) Higher Education Access Course
- 10) NVQ Level 4, HNC or HND, BTEC higher, Diploma in Higher Education, Teaching qualification, e.g. Teaching Certificate, PGCE, Nursing qualification, RSA Higher Diploma
- 11) NVQ Level 5
- 12) First degree: BA or BSc
- 13) Higher degree, e.g. MA, MBA, MSc, Mphil
- 14) Doctorate: PhD or Dphil

SC

73. Which of the following best describes the area you live?

- 1) A big city
- 2) The suburbs or outskirts of a big city
- 3) A town or a small city
- 4) A country village
- 5) A farm or home in the countryside

SC

74. Do you live together with your partner, spouse or a significant other?
- 1) Yes
 - 2) No

SC

75. Do you have (a) child(ren)?
- 1) Yes
 - 2) No

ASK ONLY IF Q75=1

OE NUM – 1-10

76. How many child(ren) do you have?

ASK ONLY IF Q75=1

OE NUM

IF AGE > 18: LIMITS = 0-3

IF AGE = 18: LIMITS = 1-3

ANSWER CAN'T BE SUPERIOR TO RESPONSE FROM Q76

77. How many child(ren) below the age of 3 do you have?

ASK ONLY IF Q75=1

OE NUM

IF Q77=0: MIN = 3 – MAX = ([RESPONDENT AGE] – 16)

IF Q77>0: MIN = 0 – MAX = 3

78. What is the age of the youngest child?

SC

79. Are you a citizen of the United Kingdom?

(EWCS)

- 1) Yes
- 2) No

ASK ONLY IF Q79=1

SC

80. Were you born in the United Kingdom?

(EWCS)

- 1) Yes
- 2) No

SC

81. With which ethnic group do you most identify?

- 1) Other ethnic group (please specify) **OE CHA**
- 2) Black or African or Caribbean or Black British
- 3) Asian or Asian British
- 4) Mixed or Multiple Ethnic groups
- 5) White
- 6) Middle Eastern or Arabic

SC

82. Do you have chronic illness or disability?

- 1) Yes
- 2) No

Appendix 2. France Questionnaire

À TOUS

INTRO_GÉNÉRALE

Bonjour,

Nous aimerions vous inviter à prendre part à cette enquête sur la façon dont vous travaillez et effectuez parfois des tâches non rémunérées au travail. Ce questionnaire est élaboré dans le cadre du projet European Research Council (ERC) Advanced Grant ResPecTMe (convention de subvention n° 833577), en vertu du programme européen pour la recherche et l'innovation Horizon 2020. Il vous faudra, au maximum, environ 20 minutes pour répondre au questionnaire.

Nous vous rappelons que les réponses sont traitées de manière anonyme, et les informations transmises ne seront utilisées qu'à des fins de recherche et abordées avec des décideurs politiques.

Si vous n'êtes pas à l'aise pour répondre à certaines questions, vous aurez la plupart du temps la possibilité de passer ces questions.

Vous retrouverez en fin de questionnaire un lien vers le site Internet du projet pour plus de renseignements.

Nous vous remercions d'avance pour votre participation !

L'équipe ResPecTMe

Centre of Sociological Research

KU Leuven

À TOUS

Q01

Parmi ces situations, quelles sont celles qui s'appliquent à ce que vous avez fait au cours de ces 7 derniers jours ?

(Plusieurs réponses possibles)

1. Travail rémunéré (salarié, à son compte, travail dans l'entreprise familiale) même si absence ou congés temporaires
2. Études ou en formation (non payée par l'employeur) même si vous êtes actuellement en vacances
3. Sans emploi et recherchant activement un emploi
4. Sans emploi et voulant trouver un emploi mais sans le chercher activement pour le moment
5. Malade ou handicapé(e) de manière permanente
6. Retraité(e) ou pré-retraité(e)
7. Au foyer, s'occupant des enfants ou d'une autre personne
8. Autre (préciser)

[NOEMPTY]

Si Q01 = {2,3,4,5,6,7,8}

Q02

Avez-vous déjà occupé un travail rémunéré, même il y a longtemps ?

1. Oui
2. Non

[NOEMPTY]

RESPECTME_202310

-4-

[Groupe A : Si Q01 = {1},

Groupe B : Si Q01 \neq {1} Et Q02 = {1}

Groupe C : Si Q01 \in {1} Et Q02 = {2}

[QAnn : questions posées au groupe A

QXnn : questions posées au groupe A au présent, et au groupe B au passé

Qnn : questions posées au groupe A, au groupe B et au groupe C]

Si Groupe A

QA03

Au cours du dernier mois, avez-vous occupé plus d'un emploi ?

À noter que cela ne s'applique pas au changement d'emploi, mais à l'occupation de plusieurs emplois en même temps.

1. Oui

2. Non

[EMPTY]

Si QA03 = {2}

TRANSITION

Nous allons vous poser quelques questions sur votre emploi principal, c'est-à-dire sur l'emploi

rémunéré pour lequel vous réalisez le plus d'heures.

Si QA03 \in {2}

TRANSITION

Nous allons vous poser quelques questions sur votre emploi principal, c'est-à-dire sur l'emploi

rémunéré pour lequel vous réalisez le plus d'heures.

Si vous occupez plusieurs emplois parfaitement identiques, veuillez répondre en considérant l'emploi le mieux rémunéré.

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX04

Êtes-vous...

1. À votre compte (y compris gérant de société ou chef d'entreprise salarié)
2. Salarié(e) de la fonction publique (d'État, territoriale, hospitalière)
3. Salarié(e) d'un autre employeur (entreprise, association, de particulier, etc.)
4. Non rémunéré(e), mais vous travaillez avec un membre de votre famille
5. Autre (préciser)

[NOEMPTY]

Si Groupe A

QA04BIS

Avez-vous changé d'emploi au cours des douze derniers mois ?

1. Oui

2. Non

[EMPTY]

RESPECTME_202310

-5-

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX05

Quel est l'intitulé de votre emploi principal ?

Merci d'être le plus précis possible.

[Champ texte]

[EMPTY]

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX06

Dans votre emploi principal, quel type de travail faites-vous habituellement ?

Merci d'être le plus précis possible.

[Champ texte]

[EMPTY]

Si QX04 = {1}

QX07

Laquelle ou lesquelles de ces catégories décrit ou décrivent le mieux votre principal emploi rémunéré ?

(Plusieurs réponses possibles)

1. Unique dirigeant de sa propre entreprise
2. Associé au sein d'une entreprise ou d'un cabinet de profession libérale
3. À son compte
4. Sous-traitant
5. Free-lance
6. Salarié par une agence d'intérim
7. Autre (préciser)

[EMPTY+1]

Si QX04 = {1}

QX08

Dans votre entreprise ou votre structure...

1.

Oui

2.

Non

QX08_A Avez-vous le pouvoir d'embaucher ou de licencier des employés ?

QX08_B Recevez-vous des honoraires convenus, sur une base hebdomadaire ou mensuelle ?

QX08_C Avez-vous des employés (qui travaillent pour vous) ?

QX08_D Avez-vous plusieurs clients ?

[EMPTY+1]

Si QX04 = {2,3}

QX09

Avez-vous un contrat de travail ?

1. Oui

2. Non

[EMPTY]

RESPECTME_202310

-6-

Si QX09 = {1}

QX10

Le contrat de travail de votre emploi principal précise-t-il le nombre d'heures de travail que vous devez effectuer ?

1. Oui

2. Non

[EMPTY]

Si QX10 = {1}

QX11

Au cours d'une semaine de travail « normale », quel est le nombre d'heures hebdomadaire prévu dans votre contrat de travail ?

(Exclure les pauses repas non rémunérées)

Saisissez un nombre entier ou demi-entier (par exemple « 37.5 » pour 37 heures et demie)

[Champ numérique] heure(s)/semaine

[EMPTY]

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX12

Habituellement, combien d'heures par semaine travaillez-vous dans votre emploi principal ?

(Exclure les pauses repas non rémunérées)

Saisissez un nombre entier ou demi-entier (par exemple « 37.5 » pour 37 heures et demie)

[Champ numérique] heure(s)/semaine

[EMPTY]

Si QA03 = {1}

QA20

Habituellement, combien d'heures par semaine effectuez-vous dans votre (vos) autre(s) emploi(s) (autre que votre emploi principal) ?

(Veuillez saisir un nombre entier sans décimale et sans autre caractère - lettre, espace, ponctuation)

[Champ numérique] heure(s)/semaine

[EMPTY]

Si QX04 = {2,3}

QX13

Votre contrat ou accord dure-t-il... ?

1. Pour une durée déterminée
2. Jusqu'à l'accomplissement d'une tâche
3. En permanence ou jusqu'à la retraite
4. De façon continue, jusqu'à nouvel ordre
5. Je ne sais pas [Exclusif]

[EMPTY+1]

RESPECTME_202310

-7-

Si QX09 = {1}

QX14

Le contrat vous garantit-il un minimum d'heures ou de travail ?

1. Oui
2. Non

[EMPTY]

Si QX04 = {1}

QX15

Au total, combien de salariés travaillent au sein de votre entreprise ou structure ?

1. Je travaille seul(e)
2. 2 – 9
3. 10 – 24
4. 25 – 99
5. 100 – 249
6. 250 – 499
7. 500 ou plus

[EMPTY+1]

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX17

Avez-vous des personnes qui travaillent sous votre direction et pour lesquelles les augmentations de salaire, les primes ou les promotions dépendent étroitement de vous ?

1. Oui

2. Non

[EMPTY]

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

TRANSITION

De manière générale, les gens travaillent pour être payés. Mais il arrive à des gens d'effectuer des tâches qui ne sont pas rémunérées, ce que l'on appelle des « heures de travail non rémunérées ».

Les questions suivantes portent sur vos heures de travail rémunérées et non rémunérées dans votre emploi principal.

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX18

Avez-vous effectué des heures supplémentaires au cours des mois écoulés, et si oui, à quelle fréquence ?

Les heures supplémentaire désignent les heures de travail effectuées au-delà de la durée contractuelle quotidienne ou hebdomadaire.

1. Non, je n'ai pas effectué d'heures supplémentaires
2. Oui, une fois par mois ou moins
3. Oui, plusieurs fois par mois
4. Oui, plusieurs fois par semaine
5. Oui, tous les jours

[EMPTY]

RESPECTME_202310

-8-

Si QX18 = {2,3,4,5}

QX19

Avez-vous reçu une rémunération (ou une compensation) pour les heures supplémentaires que vous avez effectuées au cours des 12 derniers mois ?

1. Non
2. Oui, mais seulement une partie des heures ont été payées
3. Oui, et la plupart des heures ont été payées
4. Oui, toutes les heures supplémentaires sont payées

[EMPTY]

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

TRANSITION

Les questions suivantes porteront sur les différentes tâches effectuées dans le cadre de votre travail, et leurs rémunérations.

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX21

Les tâches suivantes font-elles partie de votre emploi principal, et si oui à quelle fréquence ?

1.
Oui,
chaque
jour
2.
Oui,
plusieurs
fois par
semaine
- 3.

Oui,
plusieurs
fois par
mois

4.

Oui,
mais
moins

souvent

5.

Jamais

QX21_A Attente entre des tâches/clients

QX21_B

Communication avec les clients/employeurs (par exemple négociation, échanges de courriers, réunions, etc.)

QX21_C Travail administratif/de bureau (par exemple gestion RH, paperasse, rédaction de rapports, etc.)

QX21_D

Déplacements professionnels (par exemple entre différents sites, hors temps de trajets entre le domicile et le lieu de travail, etc.)

QX21_E Entretien d'équipements ou d'outils de travail

QX21_F

Faire du réseau (par exemple tous les efforts déployés pour obtenir plus de clients/commandes, contacter ou rencontrer des gens, assister à des événements, etc.)

QX21_G

Préparation de la tâche principale contractuelle (par exemple élaboration du calendrier et des plannings, préparations des documents, etc.)

QX21_H Formation (y compris ateliers, conférences, etc.)

[EMPTY+1]

RESPECTME_202310

-9-

Si QX21_x <> 5

QX22

[Items si QX21_x <> {5}]

Dans votre emploi principal, les tâches suivantes sont-elles rémunérées par votre employeur ou client ?

1.

Entièrement
rémunérées

2.

En grande
partie
rémunérées,
une partie
non

rémunérée

3.

En grande
partie non
rémunérées,
une partie
rémunérée

4.

Pas du tout
rémunérées

QX22_A Attente entre des tâches/clients

QX22_B

Communication avec les clients/employeurs
(par exemple négociation, échanges de
courriers, réunions, etc.)

QX22_C

Travail administratif/de bureau (par exemple
gestion RH, paperasse, rédaction de rapports,
etc.)

QX22_D

Déplacements professionnels (par exemple
entre différents sites, hors temps de trajets entre
le domicile et le lieu de travail, etc.)

QX22_E Entretien d'équipements ou d'outils de travail

QX22_F

Faire du réseau (par exemple tous les efforts
déployés pour obtenir plus de
clients/commandes, contacter ou rencontrer des
gens, assister à des événements, etc.)

QX22_G

Préparation de la tâche principale contractuelle
(par exemple élaboration du calendrier et des
plannings, préparations des documents, etc.)

QX22_H Formation (y compris ateliers, conférences,
etc.)

[EMPTY+1]

RESPECTME_202310

-10-

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

TRANSITION

Les questions suivantes portent sur les frais que vous devez engager pour votre emploi principal.

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX23

Avez-vous besoin des éléments suivants dans votre emploi principal ?

1.

Oui

2.

Non

QX23_A De moyens de transport utilisés pendant les heures de travail (par exemple voiture, vélo, camion, etc.) hors trajets entre le domicile et le lieu de travail

QX23_B D'équipements de sécurité (par exemple équipements de protection individuelle – EPI, gants, etc.)

QX23_C De vêtements ou accessoires spécifiques (y compris uniforme)

QX23_D D'ordinateur (par exemple PC, ordinateur portable, tablette et autre appareil connecté)

QX23_E D'un téléphone

QX23_F D'Internet

QX23_G De cadeaux/récompenses pour les clients (y compris dîners d'affaires)

QX23_H D'un espace de travail

[EMPTY+1]

RESPECTME_202310

-11-

Si QX23_x = {1}

QX24

[Items si QX23_x = {1}]

Les frais d'achat ou d'entretien des éléments suivants sont-ils pris en charge par votre employeur/client ?

1.

Entièrement
rémunérées

2.

En grande
partie pris
en charge,
une partie
non prise

3.

En grande
partie pris en
charge, une
partie prise
en charge

4.

Pas du
tout pris
en charge

QX24_A

De moyens de transport utilisés pendant les heures de travail (par exemple voiture, vélo, camion, etc.) hors trajets entre le domicile et le lieu de travail

QX24_B

D'équipements de sécurité (par exemple équipements de protection individuelle – EPI, gants, etc.)

QX24_C De vêtements ou accessoires spécifiques (y

compris uniforme)

QX24_D D'ordinateur (par exemple PC, ordinateur portable, tablette et autre appareil connecté)

QX24_E D'un téléphone

QX24_F D'Internet

QX24_G De cadeaux/récompenses pour les clients (y compris dîners d'affaires)

QX24_H D'un espace de travail

[EMPTY+1]

RESPECTME_202310

-12-

Si QX23_x = {1}

QX25

[Items si QX23_x = {1}]

Qui est propriétaire des éléments suivants et qui prend en charge les frais liés à leur utilisation ?

1.

J'en suis
propriétaire
et je prends
en charge
les frais liés

2.

J'en suis
propriétaire,
mais mon
entreprise
prend en
charge les
frais liés

3.

Mon entreprise
en est
propriétaire,
mais je prends
en charge les
frais liés

4.

Mon
entreprise
en est
propriétaire
et prend en
charge les
frais liés

5.

Autre
(préciser)

QX25_A

De moyens de transport utilisés

pendant les heures de travail
(par exemple voiture, vélo,
camion, etc.) hors trajets entre
le domicile et le lieu de travail

QX25_B

D'équipements de sécurité (par
exemple équipements de
protection individuelle – EPI,
gants, etc.)

QX25_C

De vêtements ou accessoires
spécifiques (y compris
uniforme)

QX25_D

D'ordinateur (par exemple PC,
ordinateur portable, tablette et
autre appareil connecté)

QX25_E D'un téléphone

QX25_F D'Internet

[EMPTY+1]

Si QX25_A = {5}

QX25_A_TXT

Veillez préciser qui est propriétaire des éléments suivants et qui prend en charge les frais
liés

à leur utilisation :

- De moyens de transport utilisés pendant les heures de travail (par exemple voiture, vélo,
camion, etc.) hors trajets entre le domicile et le lieu de travail

[Champ texte]

[EMPTY]

RESPECTME_202310

-13-

Si QX25_B = {5}

QX25_B_TXT

Veillez préciser qui est propriétaire des éléments suivants et qui prend en charge les frais
liés

à leur utilisation :

- D'équipements de sécurité (par exemple équipements de protection individuelle – EPI,
gants, etc.)

[Champ texte]

[EMPTY]

Si QX25_C = {5}

QX25_C_TXT

Veillez préciser qui est propriétaire des éléments suivants et qui prend en charge les frais
liés

à leur utilisation :

- De vêtements ou accessoires spécifiques (y compris uniforme)

[Champ texte]

[EMPTY]

Si QX25_D = {5}

QX25_D_TXT

Veillez préciser qui est propriétaire des éléments suivants et qui prend en charge les frais liés

à leur utilisation :

- D'ordinateur (par exemple PC, ordinateur portable, tablette et autre appareil connecté)

[Champ texte]

[EMPTY]

Si QX25_E = {5}

QX25_E_TXT

Veillez préciser qui est propriétaire des éléments suivants et qui prend en charge les frais liés

à leur utilisation :

- D'un téléphone

[Champ texte]

[EMPTY]

Si QX25_F = {5}

QX25_F_TXT

Veillez préciser qui est propriétaire des éléments suivants et qui prend en charge les frais liés

à leur utilisation :

- D'Internet

[Champ texte]

[EMPTY]

RESPECTME_202310

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Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

TRANSITION

Nous considérerons le travail non rémunéré comme tout type de tâches effectuées dans le cadre de l'emploi principal, mais qui sont non rémunérées ou bien qui sont effectuées en dehors du temps de travail rémunéré.

Si vous êtes indépendant, il peut s'agir de tout ce qui n'est pas spécifié dans le contrat comme les tâches réalisées, les heures supplémentaires ou encore vos produits utilisés, et qui ne sont donc pas rémunérés.

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX26

Dans quelle mesure êtes-vous d'accord ou non avec les affirmations suivantes ?

1.

Pas du

tout

d'accord

2.

Plutôt

pas

d'accord

3.

Ni d'accord,

ni pas

d'accord

4.

Plutôt

d'accord

5.

Tout à
fait
d'accord

QX26_A Le travail non rémunéré fait partie de mon travail

QX26_B Il n'y a personne pour effectuer les tâches de mon travail à ma place

QX26_C Effectuer du travail non rémunéré peut être utile à ma carrière (par exemple promotion, augmentation de salaire, prime, trouver un meilleur emploi, etc.)

QX26_D Effectuer du travail non rémunéré est perçu favorablement par les collègues/clients/employeurs

QX26_E Effectuer du travail non rémunéré est une attention ou une faveur envers les personnes avec lesquelles je travaille (par exemple collègues, clients)

QX26_F Ne pas effectuer de travail non rémunéré me donnerait un sentiment de culpabilité

QX26_G Ne pas effectuer de travail non rémunéré est perçu défavorablement par les collègues/clients/employeurs

QX26_H Ne pas effectuer de travail non rémunéré pourrait nuire à ma carrière (par exemple promotion, trouver un meilleur emploi à l'avenir, salaire, perte de clients)

[EMPTY+1]

RESPECTME_202310

-15-

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

TRANSITION

Les questions suivantes portent sur les émotions que vous procure votre travail.

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX27

Pour chacune des affirmations suivantes, veuillez sélectionner la réponse qui décrit le mieux votre situation professionnelle.

1.

Pas du
tout
d'accord

2.

Plutôt
pas
d'accord

3.

Ni d'accord,
ni pas
d'accord

4.

Plutôt
d'accord

5.

Tout à
fait

d'accord

QX27_A Mon travail me donne le sentiment du
travail bien fait

QX27_B J'ai le sentiment de faire un travail utile

QX27_C J'ai le sentiment que mon travail est reconnu

QX27_D Je me sens apprécié(e) dans la société grâce
à mon travail

QX27_E Je trouve que je suis bien payé(e) pour les
efforts que je fournis et le travail que je fais

QX27_F Mon travail offre de bonnes perspectives
d'évolution de carrière

QX27_G Je risque de perdre mon travail au cours des
6 prochains mois

QX27_H Si je devais perdre ou quitter mon emploi
actuel, il serait facile pour moi de trouver un
emploi avec un salaire similaire

[EMPTY+1]

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX28

Les affirmations suivantes portent sur le sentiment que vous procure votre travail. Pour
chaque
affirmation, veuillez préciser à quelle fréquence vous avez eu ce sentiment...

1.

Tout le
temps

2.

La plupart
du temps

3.

Parfois

4.

Rarement

5.

Jamais

QX28_A Au travail, je me sens plein d'énergie

QX28_B Je suis enthousiaste vis-à-vis de mon travail

QX28_C Je me sens épuisé(e) physiquement à la fin de ma
journée de travail

QX28_D Je me sens épuisé(e) émotionnellement par mon
travail

[EMPTY+1]

RESPECTME_202310

-16-

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

TRANSITION

Nous aimerions vous poser des questions sur l'aspect émotionnel de votre emploi principal.

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX29

Dans votre emploi principal, à quelle fréquence... ?

1.

Tout le
temps

2.

La plupart
du temps

3.

Parfois

4.

Rarement

5.

Jamais

QX29_A Avez-vous l'impression de devoir garder vos
sentiments pour vous

QX29_B Faites-vous semblant d'éprouver des émotions
que vous n'éprouvez pas en réalité

QX29_C Cachez-vous vos réels sentiments à propos d'une
situation

QX29_D Vous efforcez-vous de ressentir les émotions que
vous pensez devoir éprouver (face aux
clients/employeurs/collègues)

[EMPTY+1]

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

TRANSITION

Les questions suivantes portent sur le ressenti des personnes occupant un emploi similaire au
vôtre, dans votre entreprise ou ailleurs.

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX30

Dans quelle mesure êtes-vous d'accord avec les affirmations suivantes concernant la façon
dont vous vous sentez dans la société ?

*On entend par "vous" les personnes occupant un emploi similaire au vôtre, y compris
vous-même.*

*Les "autres personnes" sont les personnes qui n'occupent pas un emploi similaire au
vôtre.*

1.

Pas du
tout
d'accord

2.

Plutôt
pas
d'accord

3.

Ni d'accord,
ni pas

d'accord

4.

Plutôt

d'accord

5.

Tout à

fait

d'accord

QX30_A Les autres personnes dénigrent les personnes occupant un emploi comme le mien.

QX30_B Les personnes qui exercent un travail similaire au mien ont le sentiment de valoir moins que les autres personnes

QX30_C Je subis de la discrimination à cause de mon emploi.

[EMPTY+1]

RESPECTME_202310

-17-

À TOUS

TRANSITION

Les questions suivantes portent sur ce que vous avez ressenti au cours de la semaine écoulée.

À TOUS

Q31

Vous est-il arrivé la semaine dernière...

1.

À aucun

moment

ou presque

2.

De temps

en temps

3.

La

plupart

du temps

4.

Tout le

temps ou

presque

Q31_A ...d'avoir l'impression que tout vous demandait un effort ?

Q31_B ...de vous sentir seul(e) ?

Q31_C ...de vous sentir triste ?

Q31_D ...de ne rien être capable de faire ?

[EMPTY+1]

TRANSITION

Les questions suivantes portent sur vos heures en dehors de votre emploi rémunéré.

À TOUS

Q32

En moyenne, combien d'heures par semaine consacrez-vous à la recherche d'un emploi/à postuler à un futur emploi ?

(Veuillez saisir un chiffre entier sans décimale et sans autre caractère - lettre, espace, ponctuation)

Répondre 0 si vous n'y consacrer pas d'heure ou n'êtes pas concerné(e).

[Champ numérique] heure(s)/semaine

[EMPTY]

À TOUS

Q33

En moyenne, combien d'heures par semaine consacrez-vous à la préparation/à l'entraînement/à la formation à l'emploi en dehors de votre emploi principal rémunéré ou pour décrocher un emploi rémunéré ?

(Veuillez saisir un chiffre entier sans décimale et sans autre caractère - lettre, espace, ponctuation)

Répondre 0 si vous n'y consacrer pas d'heure ou n'êtes pas concerné(e).

[Champ numérique] heure(s)/semaine

[EMPTY]

RESPECTME_202310

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À TOUS

Q34

En moyenne, combien d'heures par semaine consacrez-vous à des activités bénévoles ou caritatives (comme des activités syndicales ou un engagement communautaire) en dehors de votre emploi rémunéré ?

(Veuillez saisir un chiffre entier sans décimale et sans autre caractère - lettre, espace, ponctuation)

Répondre 0 si vous n'y consacrer pas d'heure ou n'êtes pas concerné(e).

[Champ numérique] heure(s)/semaine

[EMPTY]

À TOUS

TRANSITION

Nous aimerions à présent revenir sur votre emploi principal et vous poser des questions sur vos heures de travail.

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX35A

Habituellement, dans votre emploi principal, combien de fois par mois travaillez-vous... ?

(Veuillez saisir un chiffre entier sans décimale et sans autre caractère - lettre, espace, ponctuation)

- De nuit, pendant au moins 2 heures entre 22 h et 5 h du matin

[Champ numérique] nuit(s)/mois

[EMPTY]

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX35B

Habituellement, dans votre emploi principal, combien de fois par mois travaillez-vous... ?

(Veuillez saisir un chiffre entier sans décimale et sans autre caractère - lettre, espace, ponctuation)

- Le week-end

[Champ numérique] week-end(s)/mois

[EMPTY]

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX35C

Habituellement, dans votre emploi principal, combien de fois par mois travaillez-vous... ?

(Veuillez saisir un chiffre entier sans décimale et sans autre caractère - lettre, espace, ponctuation)

- Plus de 10 heures par jour

[Champ numérique] jour(s)/mois

[EMPTY]

RESPECTME_202310

-19-

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX37

Dans votre emploi principal, travaillez-vous le même nombre d'heures chaque semaine ?

1. Oui

2. Non

[EMPTY]

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX38

Dans votre emploi principal, y a-t-il régulièrement des changements dans vos horaires ? Si oui, combien de temps à l'avance êtes-vous informé(e) de ces changements ?

1. Non, il n'y a pas de changement

2. Oui, et je suis informé(e) le jour même

3. Oui, et je suis informé(e) la veille

4. Oui, et je suis informé(e) plusieurs jours à l'avance

5. Oui, et je suis informé(e) plusieurs semaines à l'avance

[EMPTY]

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

TRANSITION

Les questions suivantes portent sur la flexibilité et le contrôle dont vous disposez dans votre emploi principal.

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX39

Dans votre emploi principal, pouvez-vous décider... ?

1.

Jamais

2.

Rarement

3.

Parfois

4.

La plupart

du temps

5.

Tout le

temps

QX39_A Du nombre d'heures de travail

QX39_B Du lieu où vous travaillez

QX39_C De l'ordre de vos tâches

QX39_D De vos méthodes de travail

[EMPTY+1]

RESPECTME_202310

-20-

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX40

Les formules de travail flexibles incluent le temps partiel, le flexitime (horaire de début et de fin de journée de travail adaptés), le travail à domicile (télétravail) ou le fait de pouvoir prendre des congés pour les urgences privées (problèmes médicaux, enfant malade, etc.). Parlons à présent de votre situation professionnelle personnelle.

À votre connaissance, existe-t-il des formules de travail flexibles dans l'entreprise ou la structure dans laquelle vous travaillez actuellement ?

1. Oui, et vous utilisez actuellement ou avez utilisé personnellement de telles formules
2. Oui, mais vous n'avez jamais personnellement utilisé de telles formules
3. Non, il n'existe aucune formule de travail flexible dans l'entreprise ou la structure dans laquelle vous travaillez actuellement

[EMPTY]

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

TRANSITION

Nous aimerions à présent vous demander comment vous conciliez vie professionnelle et vie privée.

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX45 Au cours des 12 derniers mois, à quelle fréquence... ?

1. Tout le temps
2. La plupart du temps
3. Parfois
4. Rarement
5. Jamais

QX45_A Vous vous êtes préoccupé(e) des questions liées au travail alors que vous ne travailliez pas

QX45_B Vous vous êtes senti(e) fatigué(e) après le travail pour accomplir certaines tâches ménagères nécessaires

QX45_C Vous avez trouvé que votre travail vous empêchait de consacrer le temps voulu à votre famille

QX45_D Vous avez trouvé difficile de vous concentrer sur votre travail à cause de vos responsabilités familiales

QX45_E Vous avez trouvé que vos responsabilités familiales vous empêchaient de consacrer du temps à votre travail

[EMPTY+1]

RESPECTME_202310

-21-

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

TRANSITION

Les questions suivantes portent sur la protection sociale.

À TOUS

Q46

Avez-vous une maladie ou un problème de santé chronique ou de caractère durable ?
Une maladie chronique est une maladie qui dure depuis au moins 6 mois (ou durera longtemps) ou qui revient (reviendra) régulièrement.

1. Oui

2. Non

[EMPTY]

À TOUS

Q49

En cas de maladie, pensez-vous que votre ménage puisse joindre les deux bouts ?

1. Oui

2. Non

[EMPTY]

Si Groupe A

QA50

En cas de perte d'emploi, pensez-vous que votre ménage puisse joindre les deux bouts ?

1. Oui

2. Non

[EMPTY]

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX52

Dans votre emploi principal, pensez-vous courir un risque pour votre santé ou votre sécurité à cause de votre travail ?

1. Oui

2. Non

[EMPTY]

RESPECTME_202310

-22-

À TOUS

TRANSITION

Enfin, nous aimerions vous poser quelques questions sur vos revenus.

Si Groupe A ou Groupe B

QX54

Pourriez-vous nous donner votre salaire mensuel net de votre emploi principal avant prélèvement à la source ?

Si vous ne connaissez pas le chiffre exact, veuillez donner une estimation.

1. Moins de 1 150 €

2. De 1 150 € à 1 600 €

3. De 1 601 € à 1 900 €

4. De 1 901 € à 2 250 €

5. De 2 251 € à 2 650 €

6. De 2 651 € à 3 150 €

7. De 3 151 € à 3 750 €

8. De 3 751 € à 4 500 €

9. De 4 501 € à 5 750 €

10. Plus de 5 750 €

[EMPTY]

À TOUS

Q55

Pouvez-vous prévoir à l'avance combien vous allez gagner (dans votre emploi principal) au cours des 3 prochains mois ?

1. Oui, assez précisément
2. Oui, mais approximativement
3. Non

[EMPTY]

À TOUS

Q56

Êtes-vous, dans votre foyer, la personne qui contribue le plus au revenu du ménage ?

1. Oui
2. Non

[EMPTY]

RESPECTME_202310

-23-

À TOUS

Q57

En tenant compte de toutes les sources de revenu de votre ménage (par exemple revenu du partenaire, avantage social, revenu hors travail issu de propriétés, etc.), pourriez-vous nous donner le revenu mensuel net de votre ménage après impôts et déductions obligatoires ?

Si vous ne connaissez pas le chiffre exact, veuillez donner une estimation.

1. Moins de 1 150 €
2. De 1 150 € à 1 600 €
3. De 1 601 € à 1 900 €
4. De 1 901 € à 2 250 €
5. De 2 251 € à 2 650 €
6. De 2 651 € à 3 150 €
7. De 3 151 € à 3 750 €
8. De 3 751 € à 4 500 €
9. De 4 501 € à 5 750 €
10. Plus de 5 750 €

[EMPTY]

À TOUS

Q58

Un ménage peut avoir différentes sources de revenus et plusieurs membres du ménage peuvent apporter leur contribution. En pensant au revenu mensuel total de votre ménage, votre

foyer est-il en mesure de joindre les deux bouts :

1. Très facilement
2. Facilement
3. Assez facilement
4. Avec quelques difficultés
5. Avec difficultés
6. Avec de grandes difficultés

[EMPTY+1]

Appendix 3. Sweden Questionnaire

Start of Block: deltagaravtal

JS

q1
VÄLKOMMEN!

JS * X→

q2 Vi har uppdaterat Medborgarpanelens deltagarvillkor med avseende på den rättsliga grunden enligt GDPR samt vilka uppgifter vi samlar in. Du kan läsa de nya deltagarvillkoren här: [Deltagarvillkor och integritetspolicy](#). För att delta i Medborgarpanelen behöver du godkänna de nya villkoren och lämna ditt samtycke till att delta.

Genom att godkänna Medborgarpanelens "Deltagarvillkor och integritetspolicy" intygar du att du har läst och samtycker till att dina personuppgifter behandlas för forskningsändamål, för att underhålla och kvalitetssäkra Medborgarpanelen och till att Medborgarpanelen får kontakta dig med inbjudningar till framtida enkätundersökningar med de kontaktuppgifter du har angett till oss.

- Ja, jag godkänner Medborgarpanelens deltagarvillkor och integritetspolicy och ger mitt samtycke till fortsatt deltagande i Medborgarpanelen (1)
 - Nej, jag godkänner *inte* Medborgarpanelens deltagarvillkor och integritetspolicy och vill avanmäla mig från fortsatt deltagande i Medborgarpanelen (2)
-

q3 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Vi har uppdaterat Medborgarpanelens deltagarvillkor med avseende på den rättsliga grunden enligt... = Nej, jag godkänner *inte* Medborgarpanelens deltagarvillkor och integritetspolicy och vill avanmäla mig från fortsatt deltagande i Medborgarpanelen

q4 Du angav i föregående fråga att du inte längre vill delta i Medborgarpanelens undersökningar och kommer därför att avregistreras från framtida utskick. Vänligen observera att det kan ta upp till 30 dagar innan avanmälan har behandlats.

Är det korrekt att du vill avsluta ditt deltagande i Medborgarpanelen?

Ja, jag bekräftar att jag vill avsluta mitt deltagande i Medborgarpanelen (1)

q5 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

End of Block: deltagaravtal

Start of Block: studieintro

q6

VÄLKOMMEN!

Nu följer en studie i samarbete med forskare vid Centre of Sociological research, vid KU Leuven universitet i Belgien. Syftet med studien är att undersöka hur människor arbetar och ibland hanterar uppgifter i sitt arbete som inte är betalda.

Om du har några frågor om studien är du välkommen att kontakta huvudansvarig forskare Hyojin Seo (hyojin.seo@kuleuven.be), doktor i social policy vid KU Leuven universitet i Belgien.

För denna studie gäller i övrigt samma villkor och rättigheter för dig som i andra studier från Medborgarpanelen, dessa beskrivs i våra [Deltagarvillkor och integritetspolicy](#).

Du har inte godkänt att delta i studien.

Är du säker på att du vill gå vidare?

JS

q7 Browser Meta Info
Browser (1)
Version (2)
Operating System (3)
Screen Resolution (4)
Flash Version (5)
Java Support (6)
User Agent (7)

q8 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: studieintro

Start of Block: Bakgrund screening arbete

JS X→

q9 Vilken av de här grupperna beskriver bäst dig själv just nu?

- Har heltidsanställning (även kortvarigt sjukskriven, föräldraledig) (1)
- Har deltidsanställning (även kortvarigt sjukskriven, föräldraledig) (2)
- Egen företagare (3)
- Har arbete i arbetsmarknadspolitiska åtgärder/genomgår arbetsmarknadsutbildning (4)
- Arbetslös (5)
- Pensionär (6)
- Har sjukersättning/aktivitetsersättning (7)
- Studerande (8)
- Annan grupp: (9) _____

q10 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: Bakgrund screening arbete

Start of Block: outro arbetar inte

q11 Den här studien riktar sig till de som främst identifierar sig som arbetande. Du angav på föregående fråga att `#{e://Field/optout_outro_lmsit}` stämmer bäst in på dig. När du klickar dig vidare kommer enkäten därför att avslutas. Tack för din medverkan, och välkommen att delta i kommande undersökningar.

q12 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: outro arbetar inte

Start of Block: flera arbeten samtidigt

q13 Har du under den senaste månaden arbetat på mer än ett jobb?

Observera att detta inte gäller vid byte av jobb utan när du har flera jobb/anställningar samtidigt.

- Ja (1)
- Nej (2)
-

q14 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Display This Question:

If Har du under den senaste månaden arbetat på mer än ett jobb? Observera att detta inte gäller vid... = Ja

JS

q15 I den här enkäten ställs frågor om ditt arbete. Om du har fler än ett jobb ska du svara enbart utifrån ditt *huvudsakliga arbete*, vilket är där du arbetar flest timmar.

Om du har flera arbeten med exakt samma timmar ska du svara utifrån det arbete där du får mest betalt.

q16 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

End of Block: flera arbeten samtidigt

Start of Block: huvudarbete frågor

q17 Hur många arbetar totalt i $\${e://Field/arbetssituation}$?

Jag jobbar ensam (1)

2–9 (2)

10–24 (3)

25–99 (4)

100–249 (5)

250–499 (6)

500 eller fler (7)

q18 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

q19 Inom vilken sektor arbetar du?

- Statlig (1)
 - Kommunal (2)
 - Landstings- / regional (3)
 - Privat (4)
 - Icke vinstdrivande organisation/stiftelse (5)
-

q20 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Vilken av de här grupperna beskriver bäst dig själv just nu? = Egen företagare

q21 Välj den eller de kategorier som gäller för ditt arbete.

Ensam VD för eget företag (1)

Partner i ett företag eller yrkesverksamhet (2)

Arbetar för dig själv (3)

Arbetar som underleverantör (4)

Arbetar som frilans (5)

Arbetar via ett bemanningsföretag (6)

Annat, nämligen: (7)

q22 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Vilken av de här grupperna beskriver bäst dig själv just nu? = Egen företagare

And Välj den eller de kategorier som gäller för ditt arbete. != Arbetar via ett bemanningsföretag

q23 Vad av följande stämmer in på dig angående ditt företag?

	Ja (1)	Nej (2)
Du får betalt en bestämd lön varje månad (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Du har anställda (som jobbar åt dig) (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Du har befogenhet att anställa eller säga upp anställda (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Du har i allmänhet mer än en klient eller kund (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

q24 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Vilken av de här grupperna beskriver bäst dig själv just nu? = Har heltidsanställning (även kortvarigt sjukskriven, föräldraledig)

Or Vilken av de här grupperna beskriver bäst dig själv just nu? = Har deltidsanställning (även kortvarigt sjukskriven, föräldraledig)

Or Vilken av de här grupperna beskriver bäst dig själv just nu? = Har arbete i arbetsmarknadspolitiska åtgärder/genomgår arbetsmarknadsutbildning

Or Välj den eller de kategorier som gäller för ditt arbete. = Arbetar via ett bemanningsföretag

q25 Har du ett kontrakt eller anställningsavtal?

Ja (1)

Nej (2)

q26 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

Page Break

q27 Stämmer något av följande in på din arbetssituation?

Välj allt som stämmer.

- Arbetar i ett familje-eller hushållsföretag (1)
 - Arbetar som lärling/praktiserar (2)
 - Arbetar med en familjemedlem som arbetar för någon annan (3)
 - Inget av ovanstående (4)
-

q28 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

Page Break

q29 Vilken eller vilka av följande former stämmer för din anställning?

Välj allt som stämmer.

- Tillsvidareanställning (1)
 - Tidsbegränsad anställning (2)
 - Projektanställning (3)
 - Behovsanställning (4)
 - Vet ej (5)
-

q30 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

q31 Arbetsleder du andra i ditt arbete?

- Ja (1)
- Nej (2)
-

q32 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

q33
Vilket är ditt huvudsakliga yrke?

När du börjar skriva in ditt yrke kommer du få upp en lista med passande förslag. Välj det yrke i listan som ligger närmast dina arbetsuppgifter. Skriv annars vad du själv skulle kalla det.

- (1) _____
-

q34 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

q35 Nu följer några frågor om dina arbetstider.

`#{e://Field/multiarbeten}`

q36 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Vilken av de här grupperna beskriver bäst dig själv just nu? = Har heltidsanställning (även kortvarigt sjukskriven, föräldraledig)

Or Vilken av de här grupperna beskriver bäst dig själv just nu? = Har deltidsanställning (även kortvarigt sjukskriven, föräldraledig)

Or Vilken av de här grupperna beskriver bäst dig själv just nu? = Har arbete i arbetsmarknadspolitiska åtgärder/genomgår arbetsmarknadsutbildning

q37 Har du ett fast avtal om antalet timmar du ska arbeta?

- Ja (1)
- Nej (2)
-

q38 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Vilken eller vilka av följande former stämmer för din anställning? Välj allt som stämmer. = Behovsanställning

q39 Garanterar ditt kontrakt ett minsta antal timmar eller arbete för dig?

Ja (1)

Nej (2)

q40 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

q41 Arbetar du samma antal timmar varje vecka?

Ja (1)

Nej (2)

q42 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Har du ett kontrakt eller anställningsavtal? = Ja

JS

q43 Under en typisk arbetsvecka, hur många timmar förväntas du arbeta enligt ditt anställningsavtal?

Räkna bara med de timmar som är betalda, uteslut obetalda matraster. Avrunda till hela timmar.

JS

q44 Hur många timmar per vecka arbetar du vanligtvis i ditt arbete?

Räkna bara med de timmar som är betalda, uteslut obetalda matraster. Avrunda till hela timmar.

q45 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Har du under den senaste månaden arbetat på mer än ett jobb? Observera att detta inte gäller vid... = Ja

JS

q46 Hur många timmar arbetar du vanligtvis per vecka för ditt/dina andra jobb *utöver* ditt huvudsakliga arbete?

q47 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

Page Break

q48 Hur många gånger i månaden arbetar du följande arbetstider?

Svara i siffror.

	Antal gånger (1)
På natten, i minst 2 timmar mellan 22.00–05.00 (1)	
På helgen (2)	
Mer än 10 timmar om dagen (3)	

q49 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

End of Block: huvudarbete frågor

Start of Block: obetald arbetstid

q50 Folk får betalt när de arbetar, men ibland utför folk obetalda uppgifter, vilket kallas "obetald arbetstid". Nästa frågor handlar om din betalda och obetalda arbetstid på ditt arbete.

q51 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

q52 Hur ofta har du arbetat övertid de senaste 12 månaderna?

Övertid är den arbetstid som sker utöver normal (avtalad) arbetstid under en dag, en vecka eller en månad.

- En gång i månaden eller mindre (1)
 - Flera gånger i månaden (2)
 - Flera gånger i veckan (3)
 - Dagligen (4)
 - Jag har inte arbetat övertid (5)*
-

q53 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

Display This Question:

If Hur ofta har du arbetat övertid de senaste 12 månaderna? Övertid är den arbetstid som sker utöver... = En gång i månaden eller mindre

Or Hur ofta har du arbetat övertid de senaste 12 månaderna? Övertid är den arbetstid som sker utöver... = Flera gånger i månaden

Or Hur ofta har du arbetat övertid de senaste 12 månaderna? Övertid är den arbetstid som sker utöver... = Flera gånger i veckan

Or Hur ofta har du arbetat övertid de senaste 12 månaderna? Övertid är den arbetstid som sker utöver... = Dagligen

q54 Har du fått någon lön eller ersättning för ditt övertidsarbete under de senaste 12 månaderna?

- Nej (1)
 - Ja, men majoriteten obetalt och en del betalt (2)
 - Ja, majoriteten betalt men en del obetalt (3)
 - Ja, jag får full ersättning (4)
-

q55 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

End of Block: obetald arbetstid

Start of Block: arbetsuppgifter verktyg kostnad/ägande

q56 Nu följer några frågor som handlar om olika arbetsuppgifter och om du får betalt för dem av din arbetsgivare eller uppdragsgivare/klient.

q57 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

Page Break

q58 Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det?

	Ja, dagligen (1)	Ja, flera gånger i veckan (2)	Ja, flera gånger i månaden (3)	Ja, men mer sällan (4)	Aldrig (5)
Vänta mellan uppgifter/kunder (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Kommunikation med kunder/arbetsgivare (t.ex. förhandlingar, e-post, möten) (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Administration/pappersarbete (t.ex. att hantera HR, skriva rapporter) (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resa mellan arbete och uppgifter (exklusive pendlingstid mellan hem och arbete) (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Underhållning av arbetsutrustning eller verktyg (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Nätverkande (t.ex. allt arbete för att få fler kunder/order/företag eller behålla dem över tid, som att kontakta eller träffa människor, delta i evenemang) (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Förberedelser inför huvuduppgiften (t.ex. förbereda sig eller öva eller samla material, upprätta schema eller plan för dagen) (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Utbildning/träning för sitt arbete (inklusive workshops, konferens) (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

q59 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Ja, dagligen

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Ja, flera gånger i veckan

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Ja, flera gånger i månaden

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Ja, men mer sällan

q60 I vilken utsträckning betalas följande uppgifter av din arbetsgivare eller uppdragsgivare?

Display This Choice:

If Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Vänta mellan uppgifter/kunder [Ja, dagligen]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Vänta mellan uppgifter/kunder [Ja, flera gånger i veckan]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Vänta mellan uppgifter/kunder [Ja, flera gånger i månaden]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Vänta mellan uppgifter/kunder [Ja, men mer sällan]

Display This Choice:

If Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Kommunikation med kunder/arbetsgivare (t.ex. förhandlingar, e-post, möten) [Ja, dagligen]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Kommunikation med kunder/arbetsgivare (t.ex. förhandlingar, e-post, möten) [Ja, flera gånger i veckan]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Kommunikation med kunder/arbetsgivare (t.ex. förhandlingar, e-post, möten) [Ja, flera gånger i månaden]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Kommunikation med kunder/arbetsgivare (t.ex. förhandlingar, e-post, möten) [Ja, men mer sällan]

Display This Choice:

If Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Administration/pappersarbete (t.ex. att hantera HR, skriva rapporter) [Ja, dagligen]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Administration/pappersarbete (t.ex. att hantera HR, skriva rapporter) [Ja, flera gånger i veckan]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Administration/pappersarbete (t.ex. att hantera HR, skriva rapporter) [Ja, flera gånger i månaden]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Administration/pappersarbete (t.ex. att hantera HR, skriva rapporter) [Ja, men mer sällan]

Display This Choice:

If Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Resa mellan arbete och uppgifter (exklusive pendlingstid mellan hem och arbete) [Ja, dagligen]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Resa mellan arbete och uppgifter (exklusive pendlingstid mellan hem och arbete) [Ja, flera gånger i veckan]

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Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Resa mellan arbete och uppgifter (exklusive pendlingstid mellan hem och arbete) [Ja, men mer sällan]

Display This Choice:

If Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Underhållning av arbetsutrustning eller verktyg [Ja, dagligen]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Underhållning av arbetsutrustning eller verktyg [Ja, flera gånger i veckan]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Underhållning av arbetsutrustning eller verktyg [Ja, flera gånger i månaden]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Underhållning av arbetsutrustning eller verktyg [Ja, men mer sällan]

Display This Choice:

If Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Nätverkande (t.ex. allt arbete för att få fler kunder/order/företag eller behålla dem över tid, som att kontakta eller träffa människor, delta i evenemang) [Ja, dagligen]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Nätverkande (t.ex. allt arbete för att få fler kunder/order/företag eller behålla dem över tid, som att kontakta eller träffa människor, delta i evenemang) [Ja, flera gånger i veckan]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Nätverkande (t.ex. allt arbete för att få fler kunder/order/företag eller behålla dem över tid, som att kontakta eller träffa människor, delta i evenemang) [Ja, flera gånger i månaden]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Nätverkande (t.ex. allt arbete för att få fler kunder/order/företag eller behålla dem över tid, som att kontakta eller träffa människor, delta i evenemang) [Ja, flera gånger i månaden]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Nätverkande (t.ex. allt arbete för att få fler kunder/order/företag eller behålla dem över tid, som att kontakta eller träffa människor, delta i evenemang) [Ja, men mer sällan]

Display This Choice:

If Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Förberedelser inför huvuduppgiften (t.ex. förbereda sig eller öva eller samla material, upprätta schema eller plan för dagen) [Ja, dagligen]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Förberedelser inför huvuduppgiften (t.ex. förbereda sig eller öva eller samla material, upprätta schema eller plan för dagen) [Ja, flera gånger i veckan]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Förberedelser inför huvuduppgiften (t.ex. förbereda sig eller öva eller samla material, upprätta schema eller plan för dagen) [Ja, flera gånger i månaden]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Förberedelser inför huvuduppgiften (t.ex. förbereda sig eller öva eller samla material, upprätta schema eller plan för dagen) [Ja, men mer sällan]

Display This Choice:

If Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Utbildning/träning för sitt arbete (inklusive workshops, konferens) [Ja, dagligen]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Utbildning/träning för sitt arbete (inklusive workshops, konferens) [Ja, flera gånger i veckan]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Utbildning/träning för sitt arbete (inklusive workshops, konferens) [Ja, flera gånger i månaden]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Utbildning/träning för sitt arbete (inklusive workshops, konferens) [Ja, men mer sällan]

	Betalas helt (1)	Majoriteten betalt, en del obetalt (2)	Majoriteten obetalt, en del betalt (3)	Betalas inte alls (4)
<input type="checkbox"/> <i>Display This Choice:</i>				
<input type="checkbox"/> <i>If Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Vänta mellan uppgifter/kunder [Ja, dagligen]</i>				
<input type="checkbox"/> <i>Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Vänta mellan uppgifter/kunder [Ja, flera gånger i veckan]</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> <i>Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Vänta mellan uppgifter/kunder [Ja, flera gånger i månaden]</i>				
<input type="checkbox"/> <i>Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Vänta mellan uppgifter/kunder [Ja, men mer sällan]</i>				
Vänta mellan uppgifter/kunder (1)				

Display This Choice:

If Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Kommunikation med kunder/arbetsgivare (t.ex. förhandlingar, e-post, möten) [Ja, dagligen]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Kommunikation med kunder/arbetsgivare (t.ex. förhandlingar, e-post, möten) [Ja, flera gånger i veckan]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Kommunikation med kunder/arbetsgivare (t.ex. förhandlingar, e-post, möten) [Ja, flera gånger i månaden]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Kommunikation med kunder/arbetsgivare (t.ex. förhandlingar, e-post, möten) [Ja, men mer sällan]

Kommunikation med kunder/arbetsgivare (2)

Display This Choice:

If Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Administration/pappersarbete (t.ex. att hantera HR, skriva rapporter) [Ja, dagligen]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Administration/pappersarbete (t.ex. att hantera HR, skriva rapporter) [Ja, flera gånger i veckan]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Administration/pappersarbete (t.ex. att hantera HR, skriva rapporter) [Ja, flera gånger i månaden]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Administration/pappersarbete (t.ex. att hantera HR, skriva rapporter) [Ja, men mer sällan]

Administration/pappersarbete
(3)

Display This Choice:

If Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Resa mellan arbete och uppgifter (exklusive pendlingstid mellan hem och arbete) [Ja, dagligen]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Resa mellan arbete och uppgifter (exklusive pendlingstid mellan hem och arbete) [Ja, flera gånger i veckan]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Resa mellan arbete och uppgifter (exklusive pendlingstid mellan hem och arbete) [Ja, flera gånger i månaden]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Resa mellan arbete och uppgifter (exklusive pendlingstid mellan hem och arbete) [Ja, men mer sällan]

Resa mellan arbete och uppgifter (exklusive pendlingstid mellan hem och arbete) (4)

Display This Choice:

If Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Underhållning av arbetsutrustning eller verktyg [Ja, dagligen]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Underhållning av arbetsutrustning eller verktyg [Ja, flera gånger i veckan]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Underhållning av arbetsutrustning eller verktyg [Ja, flera gånger i månaden]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Underhållning av arbetsutrustning eller verktyg [Ja, men mer sällan]

Underhållning av arbetsutrustning eller verktyg (5)

Display This Choice:

If Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Nätverkande (t.ex. allt arbete för att få fler kunder/order/företag eller behålla dem över tid, som att kontakta eller träffa människor, delta i evenemang) [Ja, dagligen]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Nätverkande (t.ex. allt arbete för att få fler kunder/order/företag eller behålla dem över tid, som att kontakta eller träffa människor, delta i evenemang) [Ja, flera gånger i veckan]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Nätverkande (t.ex. allt arbete för att få fler kunder/order/företag eller behålla dem över tid, som att kontakta eller träffa människor, delta i evenemang) [Ja, flera gånger i månaden]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Nätverkande (t.ex. allt arbete för att få fler kunder/order/företag eller behålla dem över tid, som att kontakta eller träffa människor, delta i evenemang) [Ja, flera gånger i månaden]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Nätverkande (t.ex. allt arbete för att få fler kunder/order/företag eller behålla dem över tid, som att kontakta eller träffa människor, delta i evenemang) [Ja, men mer sällan]

Nätverkande (6)

Display This Choice:

If Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Förberedelser inför huvuduppgiften (t.ex. förbereda sig eller öva eller samla material, upprätta schema eller plan för dagen)
[Ja, dagligen]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Förberedelser inför huvuduppgiften (t.ex. förbereda sig eller öva eller samla material, upprätta schema eller plan för dagen)
[Ja, flera gånger i veckan]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Förberedelser inför huvuduppgiften (t.ex. förbereda sig eller öva eller samla material, upprätta schema eller plan för dagen)
[Ja, flera gånger i månaden]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Förberedelser inför huvuduppgiften (t.ex. förbereda sig eller öva eller samla material, upprätta schema eller plan för dagen)
[Ja, men mer sällan]

Förberedelser inför huvuduppgiften (7)

Display This Choice:

If Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Utbildning/träning för sitt arbete (inklusive workshops, konferens) [Ja, dagligen]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Utbildning/träning för sitt arbete (inklusive workshops, konferens) [Ja, flera gånger i veckan]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Utbildning/träning för sitt arbete (inklusive workshops, konferens) [Ja, flera gånger i månaden]

Or Hur ofta ingår följande uppgifter som en del av ditt arbete? Om de ingår, hur ofta gör du det? = Utbildning/träning för sitt arbete (inklusive workshops, konferens) [Ja, men mer sällan]

Utbildning/träning för sitt arbete (8)

q61 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

q62 Följande frågor handlar om vilka utgifter du behöver göra i ditt arbete.

q63 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

q64 Behöver du följande för ditt arbete?

	Ja (1)	Nej (2)
Transportmedel som används under arbetstiden (t.ex. bil, cykel, lastbil, osv.) exklusive pendling mellan hem och arbete (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Säkerhetsutrustning (t.ex. personlig skyddsutrustning, handskar, osv.) (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Specifika kläder eller tillbehör/uniform (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Dator/surfplatta (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Telefon (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Internet (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Gåvor/belöningar till kunder (inklusive affärsmiddagar) (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Arbetsyta (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

q65 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Ja

q66 Står din arbetsgivare eller uppdragsgivare för kostnaderna att köpa eller underhålla följande?

Display This Choice:

If Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Transportmedel som används under arbetstiden (t.ex. bil, cykel, lastbil, osv.) exklusive pendling mellan hem och arbete [Ja]

Display This Choice:

If Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Säkerhetsutrustning (t.ex. personlig skyddsutrustning, handskar, osv.) [Ja]

Display This Choice:

If Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Specifika kläder eller tillbehör/uniform [Ja]

Display This Choice:

If Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Dator/surfplatta [Ja]

Display This Choice:

If Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Telefon [Ja]

Display This Choice:

If Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Internet [Ja]

Display This Choice:

If Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Gåvor/belöningar till kunder (inklusive affärsmiddagar) [Ja]

Display This Choice:

If Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Arbetsyta [Ja]

	Betalas helt (1)	Majoriteten betalt, en del obetalt (2)	Majoriteten obetalt, en del betalt (3)	Betalas inte alls (4)
<input type="checkbox"/> <i>Display This Choice:</i> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>If</i> Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Transportmedel som används under arbetstiden (t.ex. bil, cykel, lastbil, osv.) exklusive pendling mellan hem och arbete [Ja]	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Transportmedel som används under arbetstiden (1)				
<input type="checkbox"/> <i>Display This Choice:</i> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>If</i> Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Säkerhetsutrustning (t.ex. personlig skyddsutrustning, handskar, osv.) [Ja]	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Säkerhetsutrustning (2)				
<input type="checkbox"/> <i>Display This Choice:</i> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>If</i> Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Specifika kläder eller tillbehör/uniform [Ja]	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Specifika kläder eller tillbehör/uniform (3)				

*Display
This Choice:*

If
*Behöver du följande
för ditt arbete? =
Dator/surfplatta [Ja
]*

Dator/surfplatta (4)

*Display
This Choice:*

If
*Behöver du följande
för ditt arbete? =
Telefon [Ja]*

Telefon (5)

*Display
This Choice:*

If
*Behöver du följande
för ditt arbete? =
Internet [Ja]*

Internet (6)

*Display
This Choice:*

If
*Behöver du följande
för ditt arbete? =
Gåvor/belöningar till
kunder (inklusive
affärsmiddagar) [Ja
]*

Gåvor/belöningar till
kunder (7)

*Display
This Choice:*

*If
Behöver du följande
för ditt arbete? =
Arbetsyta [Ja]*

Arbetsyta (8)

q67 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Transportmedel som används under arbetstiden (t.ex. bil, cykel, lastbil, osv.) exklusive pendling mellan hem och arbete [Ja]

Or Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Säkerhetsutrustning (t.ex. personlig skyddsutrustning, handskar, osv.) [Ja]

Or Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Specifika kläder eller tillbehör/uniform [Ja]

Or Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Dator/surfplatta [Ja]

Or Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Telefon [Ja]

Or Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Internet [Ja]

q68 Vem äger följande och vem står för utgifterna förknippade med dess användning?

Display This Choice:

If Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Transportmedel som används under arbetstiden (t.ex. bil, cykel, lastbil, osv.) exklusive pendling mellan hem och arbete [Ja]

Display This Choice:

If Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Säkerhetsutrustning (t.ex. personlig skyddsutrustning, handskar, osv.) [Ja]

Display This Choice:

If Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Specifika kläder eller tillbehör/uniform [Ja]

Display This Choice:

If Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Dator/surfplatta [Ja]

Display This Choice:

If Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Telefon [Ja]

Display This Choice:

If Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Internet [Ja]

	Jag äger det och står för utgifterna (1)	Jag äger det men mitt arbete står för utgifterna (2)	Mitt arbete äger det men jag står för utgifterna (3)	Mitt arbete äger det och står för utgifterna (4)	Annat (5)
<input type="checkbox"/> <i>Display This Choice:</i> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>If</i> Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Transportmedel som används under arbetstiden (t.ex. bil, cykel, lastbil, osv.) exklusive pendling mellan hem och arbete [Ja]	○	○	○	○	○
Transportmedel som används under arbetstiden (1)					
<input type="checkbox"/> <i>Display This Choice:</i> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>If</i> Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Säkerhetsutrustning (t.ex. personlig skyddsutrustning, handskar, osv.) [Ja]	○	○	○	○	○
Säkerhetsutrustning (2)					

Display This Choice:

If

Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Specifika kläder eller tillbehör/uniform [Ja]

Specifika kläder eller tillbehör/uniform (3)

○ ○ ○ ○ ○

Display This Choice:

If

Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Dator/surfplatta [Ja]

Dator/surfplatta (4)

○ ○ ○ ○ ○

Display This Choice:

If

Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Telefon [Ja]

Telefon (5)

○ ○ ○ ○ ○

Display This Choice:

If

Behöver du följande för ditt arbete? = Internet [Ja]

Internet (6)

○ ○ ○ ○ ○

q69 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: arbetsuppgifter verktyg kostnad/ägande

Start of Block: obetalt arbete + känslor för jobb

q70 I denna undersökning definieras oavlönat arbete som alla slags uppgifter som utförs som en del av arbetet men utan att betalas, eller som utförs vid sidan av den betalda arbetstiden. För egenföretagare innebär det uppgifter eller tid som inte omfattas av kontraktet och därför inte är betalda.

q71 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

q72 I vilken utsträckning instämmer du med följande påståenden?

	Instämmer till fullo (1)	Instämmer till viss del (2)	Varken eller (3)	Instämmer inte (4)	Instämmer inte alls (5)
Oavlönat arbete är en del av mitt jobb (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Det finns ingen som kan utföra mina arbetsuppgifter istället för mig (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Oavlönat arbete kan hjälpa mig i min karriär (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Oavlönat arbete ses positivt av kollegor/klienter/arbetsgivare (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Jag visar vänlighet och omsorg om människor jag arbetar med (t.ex. kollegor, klienter) genom oavlönat arbete (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Att avstå från oavlönat arbete skulle få mig att känna skuld (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Kollegor/klienter/arbetsgivare ser negativt på att man avstår oavlönat arbete (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Det kan skada min karriär om jag avstår oavlönat arbete (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

q73 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

Page Break

q74 Följande frågor handlar om hur du känner för ditt arbete.

q75 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

q76 Välj det svar som bäst beskriver din arbetsituation för varje påstående.

	Instämmer till fullo (1)	Instämmer till viss del (2)	Varken eller (3)	Instämmer inte (4)	Instämmer inte alls (5)
Mitt jobb ger mig känslan av ett väl utfört arbete (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Jag känner att jag utför ett viktigt arbete (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Jag känner att mitt arbete erkänns (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Jag känner mig uppskattad i samhället på grund av mitt arbete (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Jag känner att jag får rätt betalt med tanke på mina ansträngningar och arbetsprestationer (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Mitt arbete ger goda möjligheter till karriärutveckling (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Jag skulle kunna förlora mitt arbete inom de närmaste sex månaderna (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Om jag skulle förlora eller sluta på mitt nuvarande arbete skulle det vara lätt för mig att hitta ett arbete med liknande lön (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

q77 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

q78 Hur ofta känner du följande för ditt arbete?

	Alltid (1)	Oftast (2)	Ibland (3)	Sällan (4)	Aldrig (5)
Jag är entusiastisk över mitt arbete (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
Jag känner mig fysiskt utmattad i slutet av arbetsdagen (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
Jag känner mig känslomässigt dränerad av mitt arbete (3)	<input type="radio"/>				

q79 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

q80 Hur ofta sker följande i ditt arbete?

	Alltid (1)	Oftast (2)	Ibland (3)	Sällan (4)	Aldrig (5)
Det känns som att du måste motstå att uttrycka dina sanna känslor (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
Du låtsas som att du har känslor som du egentligen inte har (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
Du döljer dina sanna känslor om en situation (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
Du försöker faktiskt känna de känslor som du behöver visa för andra (kunder/arbetsgivare/kollegor) (4)	<input type="radio"/>				

q81 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

Page Break

q82 I vilken utsträckning instämmer du med följande påståenden?

	Instämmer till fullo (1)	Instämmer till viss del (2)	Varken eller (3)	Instämmer inte (4)	Instämmer inte alls (5)
Andra ser ner på människor med mitt typ av arbete (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Människor med samma typ av arbete som jag tycker generellt att vi inte är lika bra som andra (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Andra människor diskriminerar mig på grund av mitt arbete (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

q83 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

q84 Hur stor del av tiden under den senaste veckan ...?

	Hela eller nästan hela tiden (1)	För det mesta av tiden (2)	En del av tiden (3)	Ingen eller nästan ingen del av tiden (4)
... kände du att allt du gjorde var en ansträngning (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... kände du dig ensam (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... kände du dig ledsen (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... kunde du inte sätta igång med arbetet (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

q85 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

End of Block: obetalt arbete + känslor för jobb

Start of Block: trygghet

q86 Följande frågor handlar om den flexibilitet och kontroll du har i ditt arbete.

q87 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

Page Break

q88 I vilken utsträckning kan du bestämma följande i ditt arbete?

	Alltid (1)	Ofta (2)	Ibland (3)	Sällan (4)	Inte alls (5)
Antalet arbetstimmar (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
Var du arbetar (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
Den ordning i vilken du utför arbetsuppgifter (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
Dina arbetsmetoder (4)	<input type="radio"/>				

q89 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

Page Break

q90 Finns det, såvitt du vet, flexibla arbetsformer i det företag eller den organisation där du arbetar?

Flexibla arbetsformer omfattar flexibelt arbete, flextid (anpassade tider för när arbetet börjar och slutar) och arbete hemifrån (distansarbete).

- Ja, och jag använder/har använt flexibla arbetsformer personligen (1)
 - Ja, men jag har aldrig använt flexibla arbetsformer personligen (2)
 - Nej, flexibla arbetsformer finns inte tillgängligt där jag arbetar (3)
-

q91 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

q92 Finns det ett fackförbund, företagsråd eller liknande kommitté som representerar de anställda på din arbetsplats?

- Ja (1)
 - Nej (2)
 - Vet ej (3)
-

q93 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

q94 Hur ofta under de senaste 12 månaderna (eller sedan du började arbeta) har du upplevt följande?

	Alltid (1)	Ofta (2)	Ibland (3)	Sällan (4)	Aldrig (5)	<i>Ej tillämpligt</i> (6)
Fortsatt att oroa dig för arbetet utanför arbetstid (1)	<input type="radio"/>					
Känt dig för trött efter arbetet för att göra några av de hushållssysslor som måste göras (2)	<input type="radio"/>					
Känt att ditt arbete hindrar dig från att ge den tid du vill till din familj (3)	<input type="radio"/>					
Haft svårt att koncentrera dig på arbetet på grund av ansvar för familjen (4)	<input type="radio"/>					
Känt att ditt ansvar för familj hindrat dig från att ge ditt arbete den tid du borde (5)	<input type="radio"/>					

q95 Timing
 First Click (1)
 Last Click (2)
 Page Submit (3)
 Click Count (4)

Page Break

q96 Tror du att din hälsa eller säkerhet är i fara på grund av ditt arbete?

Ja (1)

Nej (2)

q97 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

End of Block: trygghet

Start of Block: bakgrund/inkomst

q98 Nu följer några avslutande bakgrundsfrågor om bland annat din inkomst.

q99 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

Page Break

q100 Vad är din *egen* genomsnittliga lön per månad *efter* skatt och obligatoriska avdrag från ditt arbete?

Om du inte vet den exakta siffran, ge en uppskattning. [\\${e://Field/multiarbeten}](#)

- Upp till 12 999 (1)
 - 13 000 - 15 999 (2)
 - 16 000 - 21 999 (3)
 - 22 000 - 25 999 (4)
 - 26 000 - 30 999 (5)
 - 31 000 - 38 999 (6)
 - 39 000 - 46 999 (7)
 - 47 000 - 56 999 (8)
 - 57 000 - 71 999 (9)
 - 72 000 eller mer (10)
 - Vet ej /vill ej ange (11)
-

q101 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

q102 Kan du i förväg förutsäga hur mycket du kommer att tjäna i ditt arbete under de kommande 3 månaderna?

- Ja, ganska exakt (1)
 - Ja, ungefär (2)
 - Nej (3)
-

q103 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

q104 Hur många personer bor regelbundet med dig i ditt hushåll, inklusive dig själv?

Svara i siffror.

Vuxna (inklusive dig själv) (1)

Barn 0-3 år (2) _____

Barn 4-13 år (3) _____

Barn 14-17 år (4) _____

q105 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

Page Break _____

q106 Är du den person i ditt hushåll som bidrar mest till hushållets inkomster?

- Ja (1)
 - Nej (2)
-

q107 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

q108 Med hänsyn till alla inkomstkällor i ditt hushåll (t.ex. partners inkomst, ekonomiskt bistånd, intäkter från fastigheter), vad är din totala *hushållsinkomst efter* skatt per månad?

Om du inte vet den exakta siffran, ge en uppskattning.

- Upp till 12 999 (1)
- 13 000 - 15 999 (2)
- 16 000 - 21 999 (3)
- 22 000 - 25 999 (4)
- 26 000 - 30 999 (5)
- 31 000 - 38 999 (6)
- 39 000 - 46 999 (7)
- 47 000 - 56 999 (8)
- 57 000 - 71 999 (9)
- 72 000 eller mer (10)
- Vet ej/ vill ej ange* (11)

q109 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

q110 Ett hushåll kan ha olika inkomstkällor och mer än en hushållsmedlem kan bidra till det. Om du tänker på ditt hushålls totala månadsinkomst, hur klarar sig ditt hushåll?

- Mycket bra (1)
- Bra (2)
- Ganska bra (3)
- Med viss svårighet (4)
- Med svårighet (5)
- Med stor svårighet (6)

q111 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

q112 Är du svensk medborgare?

- Ja (1)
 - Nej (2)
-

q113 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

Page Break

q114 I vilken typ av område bor du?

- Storstad: centralt (1)
 - Storstad: ytterområde/förort (2)
 - Stad: centralt (3)
 - Stad: ytterområde (4)
 - Större tätort (5)
 - Mindre tätort (6)
 - Ren landsbygd (7)
-

q115 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: bakgrund/inkomst

Start of Block: studieoutro

JS

q116 Nu följer några frågor om din upplevelse av att besvara den här enkäten. Tyckte du att det...

(Observera att du måste klicka på varje slider för att ge ett svar)

JS

q117 Vad tyckte du om enkäten som helhet?

JS

q118

Tack för din medverkan!

Föregående fråga avslutar studien om obetalt arbete. Syftet med studien var att undersöka hur människor arbetar och ibland hanterar uppgifter i sitt arbete som inte är betalda.

Om du har några frågor om studien är du välkommen att kontakta huvudansvarig forskare Hyojin Seo (hyojin.seo@kuleuven.be), doktor i social policy vid KU Leuvens universitet i Belgien.

Klicka på "Skicka in enkäten" nere till höger för att avsluta undersökningen.

Om du några kommentarer kring studien är du välkommen att lämna dem här: *Observera dock att du inte kan få några svar på frågor du ställer här. Vänligen skicka oss ett e-postmeddelande om du har frågor.*

q119 Browser Meta Info

Browser (1)

Version (2)

Operating System (3)

Screen Resolution (4)

Flash Version (5)

Java Support (6)

User Agent (7)

q120 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

End of Block: studieoutro

Appendix 4. The Netherlands Questionnaire

Questions

Page 1

all respondents

{Intro}

Deze vragenlijst gaat over werken en onbetaalde werkzaamheden.

Answer type: None

Page 2

all respondents

{Intro2}

We stellen u eerst een aantal vragen over uw huidige werk.

Answer type: None

Page 3

all respondents

p_bel bezig

In het onderstaande overzicht staat welke situatie of bezigheid op u van toepassing is volgens onze gegevens.

Wilt u de gegevens controleren en zo nodig wijzigen?

Kies alle opties die van toepassing zijn.

Answer type: Checkboxes

Categories:

1. Verricht betaald werk in loondienst
 2. Werkt of is meewerkend in gezins- of familiebedrijf
 3. Is vrijeberoepsbeoefenaar, freelancer of zelfstandige
 4. Zoekt werk na verlies werkkring
 5. Zoekt voor het eerst werk
 6. Vrijgesteld van werkzoeken na verlies van werkkring
 7. Gaat naar school of studeert
 8. Verzorgt de huishouding
 9. Is met pensioen (vervroegd, AOW of VUT)
 10. Is (gedeeltelijk) arbeidsongeschikt
 11. Verricht onbetaald werk met behoud van uitkering
 12. Verricht vrijwilligerswerk
 13. Doet iets anders
 14. Is te jong, heeft nog geen bezigheden
-

Page 4

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q2

Hebt u de afgelopen maand 2 of meer banen gecombineerd?

We bedoelen dat u tegelijkertijd meerdere banen had, niet dat u van baan veranderd bent.

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. Nee
2. Ja

Page 5

if (Q2 = 2)

{Intro_BelangrijksteBaan}

We stellen u nu een paar vragen over de baan waar u het meeste tijd aan besteedt. Dit noemen we in deze vragenlijst uw **belangrijkste baan**.

Als u evenveel tijd besteedt aan twee banen, beantwoord de vragen dan over de baan waar u het meeste voor betaald krijgt.

Answer type: None

Page 6

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q3

[Ik werk... / In mijn belangrijkste baan, werk ik...]

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. als werknemer
2. in mijn eigen zaak
3. in een familiebedrijf
4. als leerling, stagiair
5. als hulp voor een familielid dat voor iemand anders werkt
6. anders, namelijk:

Q3_text

Question type: Inline text field attached to code 6 of question "Q3"

Answer type: String

Page 7

if (ISCO8 is response and sector is response)

JobSwitch

Bent u in de afgelopen 12 maanden van baan veranderd?

Als een andere functie hebt gekregen binnen dezelfde organisatie telt dit ook als verandering.

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. Nee
2. Ja

Page 8

if ((ISCO8 is empty and sector is empty) or JobSwitch = 2)

Q4

Wat is de functietitel van uw [/ belangrijkste]baan?

Answer type: String

Page 9

if ((ISCO8 is empty and sector is empty) or JobSwitch = 2)

Q5

Wat zijn de belangrijkste taken van uw [/ belangrijkste]baan?

Answer type: Text

Page 10

if (Q3 = 2)

Q6

Als u denkt aan uw [/ belangrijkste]baan, welke van de onderstaande beschrijvingen zijn dan van toepassing?

Answer type: Checkboxes

Categories:

1. Enige directeur van uw eigen zaak
2. Partner in een zaak of professionele praktijk
3. Zelfstandige
4. Onderaannemer
5. Freelancer
6. Uitzendkracht voor een uitzendbureau
7. Anders namelijk:

Q6_text

Question type: Inline text field attached to code 7 of question "Q6"

Answer type: String

Page 11

if (Q3 = 2)

Q7_table

Beantwoord de volgende vragen over uw werk.

Question type: Table

Answer type: Radio buttons

Sub-questions:

Q7A Hebt u de bevoegdheid om werknemers aan te nemen of te ontslaan?

Q7B Krijgt u regelmatig uitbetaald? (dus elke week of elke maand)?

Q7C Hebt u werknemers (die voor u werken)?

Q7D Hebt u in het algemeen meer dan één klant?

Categories:

1. Nee

2. Ja

Page 12

if (Q3 = 1)

Q8

Hebt u een arbeidscontract of arbeidsovereenkomst?

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. Nee

2. Ja

Page 13

if (Q3 = 1)

Q9

Is het aantal uren dat u werkt vastgelegd in een overeenkomst?

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. Nee

2. Ja

Page 14

if (Q9 = 1)

Q10

Hoeveel uur wordt u verwacht in een gemiddelde werkweek te werken volgens uw arbeidsovereenkomst?

Tel hier onbetaalde pauzes, zoals de lunch niet in mee

Answer type: Integer

Min: 0

Max: 168

Label-right: uur per week

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q11

Hoeveel uur per week werkt u gemiddeld in uw [/ belangrijkste]baan?

Tel hier onbetaalde pauzes, zoals de lunch niet in mee

Answer type: Integer

Min: 0

Max: 168

Label-right: uur per week

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q12

Wat voor een type contract hebt u?

Meerdere antwoorden mogelijk

Answer type: Checkboxes

Categories:

1. Een contract voor bepaalde tijd (tijdelijk)
 2. Een contract tot dat een bepaalde taak voltooid is
 3. Een contract voor onbepaalde tijd (vast)
 4. Oproepcontract (bijv. nuluren of min-max)
 5. Uitzendovereenkomst
 6. Detacheringscontract (interim)
 7. Leerwerkovereenkomst (bijv. BBL)
 8. Payroll contract
 - 1. Ik weet het niet
-

if (Q8 = 2 or -1 not in Q12)

Q13

Is in uw contract een minimaal aantal uren of opdrachten gegarandeerd?

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. Nee
 2. Ja
-

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q14

Hoeveel werknemers werken er in totaal in uw [zaak / bedrijf of organisatie]?

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. Ik werk alleen
2. 2-9
3. 10-24
4. 25-99
5. 100-249
6. 250-499
7. 500 of meer

Page 19

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q15

In welke sector werkt u?

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. De private sector (commercieel)
2. De publieke sector (overheid)
3. Een gezamenlijke privaat-publieke organisatie of onderneming
4. De non-profitsector of een ngo
5. Anders, namelijk:

Q15_text

Question type: Inline text field attached to code 5 of question "Q15"

Answer type: String

Page 20

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q16

Geeft u in uw belangrijkste baan leiding aan andere mensen?

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. Nee
2. Ja

Page 21

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

{Intro_OnbetaaldWerk}

Mensen werken om geld te verdienen, maar soms doen mensen ook taken waar ze niet betaald voor worden. Dat zijn dan 'onbetaalde werkuren'. De volgende vragen gaan over de betaalde en onbetaalde werkuren in uw [/ belangrijkste]baan.

Answer type: None

Page 22

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q17

Hebt u de afgelopen maanden wel eens overuren gemaakt?

Overuren zijn werkuren die bovenop de normale (contractuele) uren worden gemaakt.

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. Nee, ik heb de afgelopen maanden geen overuren gemaakt
 2. Ja, één keer per maand of minder
 3. Ja, meerdere keren per maand
 4. Ja, meerdere keren per week
 5. Ja, dagelijks
-

Page 23

if (Q17 > 1)

Q18

Hebt u de afgelopen 12 maanden een vergoeding of loon ontvangen voor de gemaakte overuren?

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. Nee
 2. Ja, maar grotendeels niet betaald en deels betaald
 3. Ja, en grotendeels betaald, maar deels niet betaald
 4. Ja, volledig betaald
-

Page 24

if (Q2 = 2)

Q19

Hoeveel uren werkt u gewoonlijk per week bij uw andere baan/banen, naast uw betaalde belangrijkste baan?

Answer type: Integer

Min: 0

Max: 168

Label-right: uren per week

Page 25

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

{Intro_Taken}

Er volgen nu een aantal vragen over verschillende taken op werk, en of deze wel of niet betaald worden.

Answer type: None

Page 26

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q20_table

Zijn de volgende taken onderdeel van uw [/ belangrijkste]baan?

Question type: Table

Answer type: Radio buttons

Sub-questions:

Q20A Wachten tussen taken/klanten door

Q20B Communicatie met klanten/werkgevers (bijv. onderhandelingen, e-mailverkeer, vergaderingen)

Q20C Administratief werk/bureauwerk (bijv. contacten met HR, fysiek bureauwerk, opstellen van rapporten)

Q20D Verplaatsingen tussen werk en taken (exclusief woon-werkverkeer)

Q20E Onderhoud van werkapparatuur of instrumenten

Q20F Netwerken (bijv. inspanningen om meer klanten/bestellingen/zaken in de huidige job binnen te halen of te behouden, zoals contact opnemen met mensen of mensen ontmoeten, evenementen bijwonen)

Q20G Voorbereiding van de hoofdwerkzaamheden (bijv. voorbereiden, oefenen of materiaal verzamelen voor de hoofdtaken, roosters of dagplanning opstellen)

Q20H Opleidingen volgen (inclusief workshops, conferenties)

Categories:

4. Ja, dagelijks

3. Ja, meerdere keren per week

2. Ja, meerdere keren per maand

1. Ja, maar minder vaak

0. Nooit

Page 27

if (Q20A > 0 or Q20B > 0 or Q20C > 0 or Q20D > 0 or Q20E > 0 or Q20F > 0 or Q20G > 0 or Q20H > 0)

Q21_table

Krijgt u betaald voor de onderstaande taken bij uw [/ belangrijkste]baan?

Question type: Table

Answer type: Radio buttons

Sub-questions:

Q21A [Q20A>0] Wachten tussen taken/klanten door

Q21B [Q20B>0] Communicatie met klanten/werkgevers (bijv. onderhandelingen, e-mailverkeer, vergaderingen)

Q21C [Q20C>0] Administratief werk/bureauwerk (bijv. contacten met HR, fysiek bureauwerk, opstellen van rapporten)

Q21D [Q20D>0] Verplaatsingen tussen werk en taken (exclusief woon-werkverkeer)

Q21E [Q20E>0] Onderhoud van werkapparatuur of instrumenten

Q21F [Q20F>0] Netwerken (bijv. inspanningen om meer klanten/bestellingen/zaken in de huidige job binnen te halen of te behouden, zoals contact opnemen met mensen of mensen ontmoeten, evenementen bijwonen)

Q21G [Q20G>0] Voorbereiding van de hoofdwerkzaamheden (bijv. voorbereiden, oefenen of materiaal verzamelen voor de hoofdtaken, roosters of dagplanning opstellen)

Q21H [Q20H>0] Opleidingen volgen (inclusief workshops, conferenties)

Categories:

1. Volledig betaald
 2. Grotendeels betaald, maar deels onbetaald
 3. Grotendeels onbetaald, maar deels betaald
 4. Volledig onbetaald
-

Page 28

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

{Intro_Kosten}

De volgende vragen gaan over de kosten die u maakt voor uw [/ belangrijkste]baan.

Answer type: None

Page 29

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q22_table

Kunt u aangeven welke van de onderstaande zaken u nodig hebt in uw [/ belangrijkste]baan?

Question type: Table

Answer type: Radio buttons

Sub-questions:

Q22A Vervoer tijdens werkuren (bijv. auto, fiets, vrachtwagen enz.), met uitzondering van woon-werkverkeer

Q22B Veiligheidsuitrusting (bijv. persoonlijke beschermingsmiddelen (PBM), handschoenen enz.)

Q22C Specifieke kleding of accessoires (inclusief uniform)

Q22D Computer (bijv. pc, laptop, tablet en andere toestellen die verbonden zijn met het internet)

Q22E Telefoon

Q22F Internet

Q22G Geschenken/beloningen voor klanten (inclusief zakendiners)

Q22H Werkplek (bijv. bureaustoel, kantoor of gehuurde werkplek)

Categories:

1. Nee
 2. Ja
-

Page 30

if (Q22A > 1 or Q22B > 1 or Q22C > 1 or Q22D > 1 or Q22E > 1 or Q22F > 1 or Q22G > 1 or Q22H > 1)

Q23_table

Worden de kosten voor de aankoop of het onderhoud van de onderstaande zaken betaald door uw werkgever/klant?

Question type: Table

Answer type: Radio buttons

Sub-questions:

Q23A [Q22A=2] Vervoer tijdens werkuren (bijv. auto, fiets, vrachtwagen enz.), met uitzondering van woon-werkverkeer

Q23B [Q22B=2] Veiligheidsuitrusting (bijv. persoonlijke beschermingsmiddelen (PBM), handschoenen enz.)

Q23C [Q22C=2] Specifieke kleding of accessoires (inclusief uniform)

Q23D [Q22D=2] Computer (bijv. pc, laptop, tablet en andere toestellen die verbonden zijn met het internet)

Q23E [Q22E=2] Telefoon

Q23F [Q22F=2] Internet

Q23G [Q22G=2] Geschenken/beloningen voor klanten (inclusief zakendiners)

Q23H [Q22H=2] Werkplek (bijv. bureaustoel, kantoor of gehuurde werkplek)

Categories:

1. Volledig betaald
2. Grotendeels betaald, maar deels onbetaald
3. Grotendeels onbetaald, maar deels betaald
4. Volledig onbetaald

Page 31

if (Q22A > 1 or Q22B > 1 or Q22C > 1 or Q22D > 1 or Q22E > 1 or Q22F > 1)

Q24_table

Wie is de eigenaar van het volgende en wie neemt de kosten voor het gebruik ervan voor zijn rekening?

Question type: Table

Answer type: Radio buttons

Sub-questions:

Q24A [Q22A=2] Vervoer tijdens werkuren (bijv. auto, fiets, vrachtwagen enz.), met uitzondering van woon-werkverkeer

Q24B [Q22B=2] Veiligheidsuitrusting (bijv. persoonlijke beschermingsmiddelen (PBM), handschoenen enz.)

Q24C [Q22C=2] Specifieke kleding of accessoires (inclusief uniform)

Q24D [Q22D=2] Computer (bijv. pc, laptop, tablet en andere toestellen die verbonden zijn met het internet)

Q24E [Q22E=2] Telefoon

Q24F [Q22F=2] Internet

Categories:

1. Ik ben de eigenaar en ik betaal de kosten
2. Ik ben de eigenaar, maar mijn bedrijf betaalt de kosten
3. Mijn bedrijf is de eigenaar, maar ik betaal de kosten
4. Mijn bedrijf is de eigenaar en betaalt de kosten
5. Anders

Page 32

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q25_table

Onbetaald werk zijn alle mogelijke taken die je uitvoert voor je werk, maar die niet betaald worden of buiten werktijd gedaan worden.

Voor zelfstandigen zijn dit bijvoorbeeld alle taken of uren die niet zijn opgenomen in het contract met opdrachtgevers.

In hoeverre bent u het eens of oneens met de volgende uitspraken?

Question type: Table

Answer type: Radio buttons

Sub-questions:

Q25A Onbetaald werk maakt deel uit van mijn baan

Q25B Niemand anders kan de taken voor mijn baan uitvoeren behalve ik

Q25C Onbetaald werk kan mijn carrière vooruithelpen (bijv. promotie, loonsverhoging, bonus, een betere baan vinden enz.)

Q25D Onbetaald werk wordt positief ontvangen door collega's/klanten/werkgevers

Q25E Onbetaald werk is een teken van zorg of vriendelijkheid tegenover mensen met wie ik werk (bijv. collega's, klanten)

Q25F Als ik geen onbetaald werk zou doen, zou ik me schuldig voelen

Q25G Wie geen onbetaald werk doet, wordt negatief beoordeeld door collega's/klanten/werkgevers

Q25H Als ik geen onbetaald werk zou doen, kan dat mijn carrière schaden (bijv. promotie, een betere baan vinden in de toekomst, loon, verlies van klanten)

Categories:

1. Helemaal niet mee eens
2. Niet mee eens
3. Niet mee eens of oneens
4. Mee eens
5. Helemaal mee eens

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if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)**{Intro_Emotie}**

We stellen u nu een aantal vragen over hoe u zich voelt bij uw [/ belangrijkste]baan.

Answer type: None

Page 34

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)**Q26_table**

Kies voor elk van de volgende uitspraken het antwoord dat het beste bij uw werksituatie past.

Question type: Table

Answer type: Radio buttons

Sub-questions:

Q26A Mijn baan geeft me het gevoel dat ik goed werk heb verricht

Q26B Ik heb het gevoel dat ik nuttig werk doe

Q26C Ik heb het gevoel dat mijn baan gewaardeerd wordt

Q26D Ik voel me gewaardeerd in de samenleving dankzij mijn baan

Q26E Ik heb het gevoel dat ik goed betaald word voor al mijn inspanningen en prestaties in mijn baan

Q26F Mijn baan biedt goede vooruitzichten voor mijn toekomstige carrière

Q26G Het is mogelijk dat ik mijn baan in de komende 6 maanden verlies

Q26H Als ik mijn huidige baan zou verliezen of ontslag zou nemen, kan ik gemakkelijk een baan met een vergelijkbaar salaris vinden

Categories:

1. Helemaal niet mee eens
 2. Niet mee eens
 3. Niet mee eens of oneens
 4. Mee eens
 5. Helemaal mee eens
-

Page 35

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q27_table

Kunt u aangeven hoe vaak u zich als volgt voelt in uw huidige baan?

Question type: Table

Answer type: Radio buttons

Sub-questions:

Q27A Ik ben enthousiast over mijn baan

Q27B Ik voel me fysiek uitgeput aan het einde van de werkdag

Q27C Ik voel me emotioneel uitgeput door mijn werk

Categories:

1. Nooit
 2. Zelden
 3. Soms
 4. Meestal
 5. Altijd
-

Page 36

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q28_table

Hoe vaak komen de volgende dingen voor in uw [/ belangrijkste]baan?

Question type: Table

Answer type: Radio buttons

Sub-questions:

Q28A Het gevoel hebben dat u uw ware gevoelens niet kan uiten

Q28B Emoties tonen die u niet echt hebt

Q28C Uw ware gevoelens over een situatie verbergen

Q28D Moeite doen om de emoties te voelen die u aan anderen moet tonen (klanten/werkgevers/collega's)

Categories:

1. Nooit
2. Zelden
3. Soms

4. Meestal
5. Altijd

Page 37

if (1 in p_belbezig or 2 in p_belbezig or 3 in p_belbezig)

Q29_table

In hoeverre bent u het eens met de volgende uitspraken?

Question type: Table

Answer type: Radio buttons

Sub-questions:

Q29A Andere mensen kijken neer op mensen met een soortgelijke baan als de mijne

Q29B Mensen met een soortgelijke baan als ik vinden dat we niet zo goed zijn als anderen

Q29C Andere mensen discrimineren mij vanwege mijn baan

Categories:

1. Helemaal niet mee eens
2. Niet mee eens
3. Niet mee eens of oneens
4. Mee eens
5. Helemaal mee eens

Page 38

if (1 in p_belbezig or 2 in p_belbezig or 3 in p_belbezig)

Q30_table

Hoe vaak hebt u de afgelopen week...

Question type: Table

Answer type: Radio buttons

Sub-questions:

Q30A ...het gevoel gehad dat alles veel moeite kost?

Q30B ...zich eenzaam gevoeld?

Q30C ...zich verdrietig gevoeld?

Q30D ...het gevoel gehad dat u maar niet op gang kwam?

Categories:

1. Niet of bijna niet
2. Soms
3. Meestal
4. Altijd of bijna altijd

Page 39

if (1 in p_belbezig or 2 in p_belbezig or 3 in p_belbezig)

{Intro_urenbuitenbetaald}

De volgende vragen gaan over de uren die u buiten uw betaalde baan besteed.

Answer type: None

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q31

Hoeveel uren per week besteedt u gemiddeld aan het zoeken naar werk/solliciteren voor de volgende baan?

Als u niet op zoek bent naar werk/solliciteert, vul dan 0 in.

Answer type: Integer

Min: 0

Max: 168

Label-right: uren per week

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q32

Hoeveel uur besteedt u gemiddeld per week aan voorbereiding, oefening of training naast uw betaalde [/ belangrijkste]baan of om een betaalde baan te krijgen?

Answer type: Integer

Min: 0

Max: 168

Label-right: uren per week

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q33

Hoeveel uren per week besteedt u gemiddeld aan vrijwilligerswerk of liefdadigheidsactiviteiten (zoals vakbondsactiviteiten of gemeenschapswerk) naast uw betaalde baan?

Answer type: Integer

Min: 0

Max: 168

Label-right: uren per week

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

{Intro_WerkUren}

We stellen u nu een aantal vragen over uw werkuren in uw [/ belangrijkste]baan.

Answer type: None

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q34_table

Hoeveel keer per maand werkt u bij uw belangrijkste baan...

Vul hier een geheel getal in. Als iets nooit voorkomt, vul dan 0 in.

Question type: Table

Answer type: Integer

Min: 0

Max: 31

Label-right: keer

Sub-questions:

Q34A ...minstens 2 uur 's nachts tussen 22 uur en 5 uur?

Q34B ...in het weekend?

Q34C ...meer dan 10 uur per dag?

Page 45

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q35

Is het in de afgelopen maand voorgekomen dat u minder dan 11 uur rust hebt gehad tussen het einde van de werkdag en het begin van de volgende?

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. Nee

2. Ja

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if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q36_table

Werkt u in uw [/ belangrijkste]baan...

Question type: Table

Answer type: Radio buttons

Sub-questions:

Q36A elke dag evenveel uren?

Q36B elke week evenveel dagen?

Q36C elke week evenveel uren?

Q36D met vaste begin- en eindtijden?

Q36E in ploegen(dienst)?

Categories:

1. Nee

2. Ja

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if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q37

Worden uw werktijden in uw [/ belangrijkste]baan regelmatig gewijzigd? Zo ja, hoelang van tevoren wordt u daarvan op de hoogte gebracht?

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. Nee
2. Ja, dezelfde dag
3. Ja, een dag van tevoren
4. Ja, meerdere dagen van tevoren
5. Ja, enkele weken van tevoren

Page 48

if (1 in p_belbezig or 2 in p_belbezig or 3 in p_belbezig)
{Intro_Flexibiliteit}

De volgende vragen gaan over de flexibiliteit en controle die u hebt in uw [/ belangrijkste]baan.

Answer type: None

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if (1 in p_belbezig or 2 in p_belbezig or 3 in p_belbezig)

Q38_table

Kunt u in uw [/ belangrijkste]baan het onderstaande zelf bepalen?

Question type: Table

Answer type: Radio buttons

Sub-questions:

- Q38A** De volgorde van uw taken
Q38B Uw werkwijze
Q38C Het aantal werkuren
Q38D Op welke plek u werkt

Categories:

1. Helemaal niet
2. Zelden
3. Soms
4. Meestal
5. Altijd

Page 50

if (1 in p_belbezig or 2 in p_belbezig or 3 in p_belbezig)

Q39

Sommige banen hebben flexibele werkregelingen. Voorbeelden van flexibele werkregelingen zijn flexibel werk, het aanpassen van begin- en eindtijden en/of thuiswerken. Heeft het bedrijf of de organisatie van uw [/ belangrijkste]baan flexibele werkregelingen naar u weten?

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. Ja, en ik gebruik zo'n regeling op dit moment zelf of heb ze zelf gebruikt
2. Ja, maar ik heb zo'n regeling nog nooit zelf gebruikt
3. Nee, er zijn geen flexibele werkregelingen beschikbaar in het bedrijf of de organisatie waar ik momenteel werk

if (1 in p_belbezig or 2 in p_belbezig or 3 in p_belbezig)

{Intro_General}

We stellen u nu nog een paar algemene vragen over uw [/ belangrijkste]baan, en het evenwicht tussen uw werk en privé.

Answer type: None

if (1 in p_belbezig or 2 in p_belbezig or 3 in p_belbezig)

Q40

Is er een vakbond, ondernemingsraad of een vergelijkbare organisatie of orgaan dat de werknemers op uw werkplek vertegenwoordigt?

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. Nee
 2. Ja
-

if (1 in p_belbezig or 2 in p_belbezig or 3 in p_belbezig)

Q41_table

Hoe vaak is in de afgelopen 12 maanden het volgende voorgekomen?

Als u minder dan 12 maanden geleden bent begonnen met werken, vul dan de vraag in over de periode sinds dat u gestart bent met werken

Question type: Table

Answer type: Radio buttons

Sub-questions:

Q41A U blijft piekeren over het werk terwijl u niet aan het werken bent

Q41B U voelt zich te moe na het werk om een aantal van de huishoudelijke taken te doen die gedaan moesten worden

Q41C U hebt gevoel dat u door uw werk niet genoeg tijd kan besteden aan uw gezin zoals u zou willen

Q41D U vindt het moeilijk om u op uw werk te concentreren door familieverplichtingen

Q41E U komt tot de conclusie dat uw familieverplichtingen u verhinderden om genoeg tijd te maken voor uw werk

Categories:

1. Nooit
2. Zelden
3. Soms
4. Meestal
5. Altijd
- 1. Niet van toepassing

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q42

Denkt u dat er in uw [/ belangrijkste]baan een risico is voor uw gezondheid of veiligheid?

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. Nee
2. Ja

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q43

Kunt u ons vertellen wat u per jaar verdient, na aftrek van belastingen en andere inhoudingen met uw [/ belangrijkste]baan?

Als u het niet precies weet, mag u een schatting maken.

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. Minder dan €15.000
2. €15.001 tot €20.000
3. €20.001 tot €25.000
4. €25.001 tot €29.000
5. €29.001 tot €35.000
6. €35.001 tot €42.000
7. €42.001 tot €50.000
8. €50.001 tot €59.000
9. €59.001 tot €74.000
10. €74.001 of meer
- 1. Weet ik niet
- 2. Wil ik niet zeggen

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q44

Weet u van tevoren hoeveel u gaat verdienen de komende 3 maanden [/ met uw belangrijkste baan]?

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. Nee
2. Ja, maar niet precies
3. Ja, redelijk precies

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q45

Bent u degene die het meeste bijdraagt aan het inkomen van uw huishouden?

Als u een eenpersoonshuishouden hebt, kies dan "Ja"

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. Nee
2. Ja

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

Q47

Een gezin kan verschillende bronnen van inkomsten hebben en meer dan één gezinslid kan daaraan bijdragen. Hoe goed kan uw gezin rondkomen van het totale maandinkomen?

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. Heel makkelijk
2. Makkelijk
3. Vrij makkelijk
4. Met enige moeite
5. Met moeite
6. Met veel moeite

if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

eva2h

NB: Maakt u alstublieft de vragenlijst af totdat u weer bij het beginscherm komt. Pas dan registreert het systeem de vragenlijst als **volledig** ingevuld.

Tot slot. Wat vond u van deze vragenlijst:

Question type: Table

Answer type: Radio buttons

Sub-questions:

eva2t1 Vond u het moeilijk om de vragen te beantwoorden?

eva2t2 Vond u de vragen duidelijk?

eva2t3 Heeft de vragenlijst u aan het denken gezet?

eva2t4 Vond u het onderwerp interessant?

eva2t5 Vond u het plezierig om de vragen in te vullen?

Categories:

1. Beslist niet
1
 2. 2
 3. 3
 4. 4
 5. Beslist wel
5
-

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if (1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

opm

Hebt u nog opmerkingen over deze vragenlijst?

Answer type: Radio buttons

Categories:

1. Ja
2. Nee

evaopm

U kunt uw opmerking hieronder invullen.

Question type: Dependent question attached to code 1 of question "opm"

Answer type: Text

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if not(1 in p_bel bezig or 2 in p_bel bezig or 3 in p_bel bezig)

{outro_excluded}

Helaas u behoort niet tot de doelgroep voor dit onderzoek. Druk op volgende om de vragenlijst af te ronden.

Answer type: None